

FINAL RELEASE OF ACTIVITY PLANS

[Deliverable 4.3]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable addresses the third year of work in Work Package 4: “Pedagogical Design and Innovation for Educational Robotics”. In accordance to the Description of Work (DoW), D4.3 reports on the final version of activity plans developed for ER4STEM to be implemented in the third round of workshops. The final version of activity plans is based on the second year evaluation recommendations, on the activity blocks developed in year 2 and enriched in year 3, on partner interactions with the ETL research team, who is coordinating the design process, and on the revised version of the activity plan template.

1.2 CORRELATION TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

WP4 is connected to the following Work Packages (WPs): WP1 (Framework), WP2 (Educational Robotics Workshops), WP3 (Educational Robotics Conferences), WP5 (Technology for Educational Robotics – T.5.1 Creation and development of an educational repository) and WP6 (Evaluation). Especially during year 3, there was a strong interaction between UoA and AcrossLimits who were responsible for the development of the repository and specifically the development of an activity design tool which functions as a design instrument for users of the repository to develop their own activity plans. This activity design tool structures design around the main sections of the activity plan template. In year 3 UoA worked closely with AcrossLimits and CU, to revise the activity plan template and the activity design tool.

In year 3, significant effort was put on the finalization of the ER4STEM curriculum and thus there was a strong interaction between ESI CEE and UoA. This interaction was further facilitated by a meeting between ESI CEE and UoA organized by ESI CEE in Athens. After the meeting, the interaction continued through electronic communication and collaboration around shared documents.

Of course, there is two-way interaction between WP4 and the rest of the work packages, although we can observe some strong – one-way influence between D.4.3 and specific deliverables, described next.

Specifically, D4.3 draws from developments in:

- D.1.3, which describes adaptations to the framework and offers a roadmap for the third year
- D.6.4, which presents the evaluation results of the second year of workshop implementations

On the other hand, worked reported on D.4.3 has during year 3 offered input to:

- D.2.3 and D.3.2, which use the activity plans for the implementation of workshops and ECER conferences
- D.2.4 the ER4STEM curriculum
- D.5.4, which draws from the activity plan template for the development of the repository

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document begins by describing the revised version of the activity template, which was the design instrument for the ER4STEM partners to develop the final version of activity plans (section 2). Next, we present a set of new activity blocks, which were designed to support the partners to integrate the second year evaluation recommendations into their designs. The activity blocks are a new construct, developed for ER4STEM in year 2 as a response to the first year evaluation results. Activity blocks are short activities in the form of the activities described in the “How to in the classroom” section of the activity template” and can be integrated in an existing activity plan or can be extended to form a new design. In ER4STEM UoA developed 21 activity blocks in total aiming to support partners to design robotics activities that offer multiple entry points integrating in STEM arts and life skills, support resilience - collaboration, creativity, reflective thinking and contribute in changing attitudes towards STEM

In section 4 we present an overview of the third year activity plans to facilitate an understanding of the revisions described in the next section (section 5) where we discuss how the year 3 activity plans addressed the recommendations that were drawn from the evaluation of the workshops during year two. The recommendations reported in this section were the main axes around which the revision and the development of new activity plans evolved. This section is based on an analysis that cuts across all activity plans developed in year 3. It further offers information and examples about how activity plans integrated in their design the year 2 recommendations. In section 6, we resume the work done in WP4 during year 3 and in the final section (section 7) we include the activity plans developed by the partners.

2 ACTIVITY TEMPLATE FINAL VERSION

The revised version of the activity template keeps its initial orientation as a design instrument for teachers and stakeholders that are interested to design educational activities for Robotics. In D.4.1 we offered a definition for the activity plan template as an instrument that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics (for an extended definition see D.4.1 and D.4.2). In ER4STEM we argue that we developed an activity plan template that addresses Robotics as a multidisciplinary constructionist activity (i.e. drawing from the pedagogical theory of constructionism, Papert,1980) with an inherent social dimension which includes sharing ideas and learning from others.

The revised, final version of the activity plan template has the following changes: a) it involves some restructuring of its sections to enhance cohesion b) simplification and omission of some sections which included existing information and when discussed with the partners this information did not help them to further elaborate on their design ideas c) emphasis on evidence of learning d) emphasis on designer reflection and design revision based on the implementation of the design in practice.

The last two changes are integrated in a new section, which is called “Post activity report”. Its structure has the following elements: asks for information related to unexpected and interesting/critical events during the implementation of the workshop; requires information related to the ways teachers/tutors/instructors facilitated the interesting events or mitigated some critical or unexpected events; requires from the teachers/tutors/instructors to describe what they believe their students learned during the workshop and provide evidence of this learning using verbal descriptions; pictures or any other information they think is relevant. The collection of this information offers a basis for completing the final version of the post activity report, which includes ideas for revisions / extensions of the activity plan. The post activity report was expected to be completed after the

implementation of each workshop. Thus, in section 7 where one workshop might have been implemented multiple times there are respectively multiple post activity reports (one for each implementation). This practice aims at highlighting that a design might be concretised in completely different ways by the same tutors depending on the students, the context and numerous other variables, however, this reflection after each workshop supports the implementation of the next.

The rationale underlying these changes was to orientate activity plans towards year 2 evaluation recommendations; offering a functional instrument to the practitioners which is coherent and balanced in terms of the information required by the designers; having as output activity plans which are comprehensible and usable by other practitioners; being aligned with the ER4STEM framework.

2.1 ACTIVITY PLAN TEMPLATE

STEP 1. Basic information

Provide the title of the activity as it is mediated to students

AUTHOR:

Name(s) of teacher (s), designer(s), researcher(s)..

Short description of the activity (Summary)

Provide a short description of the activity so that it becomes clear the theme of the activity, the rationale behind its design and the final products students will construct.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

STEP 2. Domains

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

- Science (0-10) Technology (0-10) Business (0-10) Engineering (0-10) Arts (0-10) Mathematics (0-10)

0 0 0 0 0 0

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify).....

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 0 0

STEP 3. Learning outcomes

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	e.g.1 Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly
	e.g.2
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	e.g. Programming with Arduino, or with LEGO EV3 programming environment
	Skills to be fostered: <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Social and action related</i>	e.g. Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
	Skills to be fostered: <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	e.g. practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.
	Skills to be fostered: <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership

STEP 4. Interaction during the activity

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	e.g. Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	e.g. Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	e.g. pre-defined roles; emergent roles; role exchange in the group

<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate
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STEP 5. Artifacts**ARTIFACTS**

<i>Digital artifact</i>	e.g. programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	i.e. The technology and the robot form: LEGO WEDO – form: 'an insect', 'a car' ... 'a simple vehicle'

STEP 6. Who? Where? How long?**Time, students & space****TIME****Duration:** e.g. 4 weeks**Schedule:** e.g. 2 hours per week**STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)**

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	e.g. boys & girls, 12-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	e.g. little if any knowledge of Arduino but experts on electronics; basic knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts)
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	e.g. 5 pupils are from Albania and 10 from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	e.g. underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	e.g. ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders, gifted, other OR Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: For example: in school at the technology laboratory; OR during project time in/after school; OR established voluntary club activity; OR after school activity at Computer Lab.

Environment: indoors/outdoors**Social Orchestration**

POPULATION**Students:** e.g. 9 **Tutors:** e.g. 2 **Assistants:** e.g. 1**GROUPING:**

Grouping criteria	e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender OR mixed specialties (for Vocational Schools)
Setting (Style of room):	e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group

STEP 6. Technology

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash & Dot
 mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

Learning Procedures**EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY**

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	e.g. emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	e.g. students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot

“How to” in the classroom

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

TITLE: PHASE 1-INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): Children are engaged in discussion about robotic behaviors and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results on the class floor.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

TITLE: PHASE 2-SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot on a predefined path on the floor. The robotic vehicle is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming and debugging their own programs. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program by repeating the movements on the floor and ensuring that the robot returns to the initial position.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

TITLE: PHASE 3-USING LOOPS

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): Students try to find a way to simplify their programs by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program. Almost spontaneously they try to use loops with programming blocks. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

TITLE: PHASE 4-GIVING “SMART” BEHAVIOR: THE USAGE OF SELECTION/SWITCH BLOCKS

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): A robot in order to be “smart” (autonomous) has to avoid any obstacle that could be in its path. Students discuss the new problem and are introduced with a new programming block: “switch block”. Firstly they use the new block once to avoid one obstacle. Very soon they realize that this is not a very “smart” behavior and of course this is not a real-life solution. So, they are encouraged to combine the “switch block” with the “loop block” to have a permanent solution. Students experiment with the position of the two blocks in the program as well as with the various settings that read and control the sensors and motors.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

TITLE: PHASE 5-FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Step 9 Attachments / Supporting Material

Assessment Procedures

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	e.g. Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part and programming part too, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	e.g. Teacher's notes with a template of e.g. three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages.

2.2 POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK) TEMPLATE

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

Unexpected moment(s)

Please describe unexpected that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this moment as unexpected. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

How did you react during the critical unexpected moment(s)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier.

Interesting moment(s)

Please describe interesting moments that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

How did you react during the critical interesting moment(s)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier

Evidence of student learning

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

Ideas for changes/extensions/revisions of the initial activity plan

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible changes or extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

3 ACTIVITY BLOCKS

Activity blocks are a construct developed during year 2 of the project aiming to support partners – especially non-academic partners - to integrate the evaluation recommendations within the design of their activity plans and to demonstrate specific didactic approaches in practice. In D.4.2 we defined activity blocks as *“adjustable short activities (that can last from 10 minutes to 1 or 2 hours) a combination of which constitutes the “how to” in the classroom section of the activity plan. They are smaller units in comparison to the activity plans and they belong to the third level of the activity plan hierarchy: (i.e Activity template (1st level), Activity Plan (2nd Level) Activity Block (3rd level). An activity plan, and specifically the section “how to” consists of 3 - 7 or more activities or activity blocks. In several cases, the activity blocks are accompanied by relevant worksheets that are designed to facilitate the implementation of the activity.”*

In D.4.2, we defined the main properties of the activity blocks:

- They are adjustable. The descriptions provided can be altered and adjusted to fit various activity plans;
- They can be combined with other activity blocks, or can be integrated into an existing activity plan to enrich or strengthen specific pedagogical approaches (e.g. collaboration, reflection, etc.);
- They have a practical character showing how the theory of introducing creativity, collaborative and reflective learning in educational robotics can be transformed to educational practice. This characteristic makes activity blocks.

During year two, UoA developed 16 Activity blocks based on: a) best practices from year one workshops b) reflection on the year one workshops c) review of the literature and d) ETL’s expertise. In year two Activity blocks focused on creativity, collaboration, reflection and multiple entry points in robotics activities.

In year three we developed a smaller number of Activity blocks (five) which aimed at completing the list of year two by bringing in the foreground good practices encountered in the year two implementations. The “shared spaces” activity block is such an example, taken from the robotic competitions organized in year 1 and 2. Evaluation of robotic competitions (see D.6.3) showed that shared spaces have the potential of being rich learning environments as they offer opportunities for resilience, reflection, hypothesis formulation, asking and providing help. From year 2 implementations and best practices we drew the activity blocks of “differentiation” and “students helping each other”. Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM was evaluated in year 1 and 2 but it was not explicitly addressed in terms of pedagogical design. Thus, in year 3 we suggested a specific activity block for partners to consider integrating in their designs activities that involve students in reflecting and discussing their attitudes towards STEM, aiming to provide more data on this aspect and to investigate if such a design could further support students to change their attitudes towards STEM. Finally, argumentation was an aspect integrated explicitly in the design of the activity plans as it was seen as an integral part of collaboration and of the social dimension of robotic constructions.

To strengthen this aspect of activity plans we designed an activity block that focuses on argumentation and connects it to the evaluation process of the design cycle of a robotic artefact (see D.4.1)

3.1 SHARED SPACES

Shared spaces for robot testing: emergent intra group collaboration. Create a common space (e.g. a table) where all groups can go and observe the others and take turns to test their robot. In this context, testing time should be strictly defined in order to prevent one group from occupying the table without leaving the others to try out things. Common spaces for testing and discussing seem to offer good opportunities for more experienced/advanced students to provide help to the others, and for the less experienced students to ask for help, see others also fail and see different approaches and ideas implemented

3.2 CHANGING AND SUSTAINING ATTITUDES TO STEM

STEM is difficult vs STEM is interesting/ useful/ Important

Use a whiteboard where you create two columns. In one of the columns, students are expected to write down arguments about STEM being difficult or not for them. In the other column, students are expected to write down arguments about STEM being interesting/useful/important. Students are expected to populate the table individually and any time they want (i.e they are expected to leave their table and write on the whiteboard at any time during their engagement with the activity). Arguments should be short phrases. At the end of the workshop, the whole class revises the arguments written in both columns and vote which of the two opinions is better supported and thus the better supported wins.

3.3 ARGUMENTATION

Evaluate the robot of the other team

Ask students to evaluate the robot of another group. The students need to structure their evaluation providing judgement in relation to the goal/ objective (what the robot was supposed to do) and an argument justifying the judgement based on the performance on the robot, and the effort the group made. For the latter the groups can have a short discussion about their difficulties and the solutions they found. Finally, their evaluation should be concluded with suggestions for improvement. It is important that groups have the opportunity to consider these evaluations and refine their work based on these evaluations before presenting their work to the class.

3.4 DIFFERENTIATION

Reference to the activity plan created by ESI CEE “Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot” during Year 2.

The main concept around differentiation in the specific activity plan was to provide tasks of varying difficulty so that when a group of students completed the main task before the other groups could

move on working on optional, more demanding tasks. Furthermore, differentiation is considered inherent in constructionist tasks as students may come up with different implementations around a concept, or may end up with a construction, which is differentiated in terms of completeness.

3.5 STUDENTS HELPING EACH OTHER

This activity block is based on the implementation of the Cardiff University activity plans. The idea is that in each class there might be some students who are better acquainted with the technologies compared to other students (i.e. having extensive prior experience). The same might be happening with a team of students. Engaging these students with other teams or students to help them out with their task without providing ready-made solutions is proved to be an effective strategy as a) students communicate better with each other and they have a very good understanding of the difficulties of the concept at hand; b) allows for further elaboration and deeper understanding of the concepts at hand for the student or the team who acts as a Teaching assistant; c) addresses the problem of having students who are bored or less engaged because they have finished earlier than the others or they are already acquainted with what is the focus of the group work at a specific moment.

4 ACTIVITY PLANS: OVERVIEW AND REFLECTION

In this section of the deliverable, we present an overview of the activity plans designed for the third and final year of the project and we attempt a reflective presentation. During the second year, the project produced 21 activity plans. Eleven (11) of these activity plans are new productions and the rest (10 activity plans) are revisions of year two and year 1 activity plans. Revisions took into consideration: a) partner-teacher's own reflection on the first year implementation; b) second year evaluation recommendations; c) discussion on best practices in the second year activity plans during the project meeting in Athens and d) changes in the activity plan template.

No	Partner	Activity Plan	Technology	Domain – emphasis
NEW ACTIVITY PLANS				
1	ESI CEE	Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills	Scratch, RobotArm kit by CBIS Education	Technology, Mathematics
2	TUWien	Basic introduction into robotics and VPL	Thymio, programming language VPL	Engineering, Life skills
3	TUWien	Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V2)	Thymio, programming language VPL, programming language Blockly	Technology, Engineering,
4	TUWien	ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator	Thymio	Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics
5	PRIA	Robotics 4 KiDs	LEGO Mindstorms EV3	Technology, Engineering,
6	PRIA	Elementary Lego Mindstorms (Karl Loewe Gasse)	LEGO Mindstorms EV3	Technology, Engineering
7	UoA	Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine	LEGO Mindstorms NXT	Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, Societal

				Life skills
8	UoA	Robotic Olympics	LEGO Mindstorms EV3	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, History
9	CU	Basic Introduction to SLurtles	Slurtles, Virtual Worlds, Scratch for Open Sim	Technology, Mathematics
10	CU	Building Our Virtual World	Slurtles, Virtual Worlds, Scratch for Open Sim	Technology, Arts, Mathematics
11	CU	SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing	Slurtles, Virtual Worlds, Scratch for Open Sim	Technology, Mathematics
REVISED ACTIVITY PLANS				
12	AL	Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash	Dash, Scratch	Science, Technology, Mathematics
13	AL	Engaging with robots in a fun way	Dash, Scratch	Technology, Mathematics
14	UoA	Exploring Planet Ektonis	LEGO WeDo 2.0, Scratch	Science, Technology, Engineering
15	UoA	Building a robot and making it smart	LEGO Mindstorms NXT, LEGO programming environment	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
16	UoA	Robotic Insect	Arduino, Arduino IDE	Technology, Engineering
17	UoA	Park the robot	LEGO Mindstorms NXT	Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
18	UoA	Insect's Battle	Arduino	Science, Technology, Engineering
19	UoA	Design and program robots to solve the maze problem.	LEGO EV3	Technology, Engineering
20	ESI CEE	Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	Scratch or Snap visual programming software; Arduino IDE, python s2a_fm and pymata	Science, Technology, Engineering
21	ESI CEE	Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot	Scratch, The Finch robot by Birdbrain Technologies	Technology, Mathematics
22	PRIA	Design thinking and robotics workshop	Python, Hedgehog	Technology, Engineering, Life skills

Table 1: List of the final release of activity plans, their technologies and the domains they cover per partner

At a closer look at the table and the technologies used in year three, we observe no significant changes in comparison to year 2's activity plans. With respect to the focus of the activity plans we observe that the majority involves concepts related to technology, science, mathematics and

engineering. As in year 2, there are activity plans integrating arts explicitly in the activities. An analysis of the post activity reports showed that in activity plans like the Robotic insect students engaged in artistic expressions to decorate and make their robots look like insects (see evidence of learning section 8 and pictures in section 5.2). Furthermore, activities in the “how to section” like Robotic Theatre (in “Elementary Lego Mindstorms” activity plan) is another example of integration of arts in robotics activities offering multiple entry points for students. Last but not least, Life skills is a new domain introduced in some of the year 3 activity plans and it is connected to supporting students to develop resilience, problematize around ethical aspects of technology, etc.

The activity plans developed in year three are included in section 7. Furthermore, WP4 in collaboration with WP2 plan to create an e-book with all the activity plans developed in the project structured around the generic curriculum developed in WP2. All activity plans are edited by UoA to follow the latest activity plan template excluding the post activity report. (The post activity report is excluded because there is no data available from year 1 and 2 regarding the implementation of the activity plans).

5 COMPLIANCE WITH EVALUATION RECOMMENDATIONS

The revision of activity plans in year three was structured mainly around the recommendations emerging from the evaluation of Learning (WP6) during the second year of the project. What the recommendations meant and how they were addressed during year two of the project was discussed in the project meeting offering examples of existing activity plans (see D.4.2). As a follow up, UoA created a shared excel file where the recommendations of year 2 were listed. To further illustrate the meaning of recommendations and support their materialization in design choices, UoA offered next to each recommendation, examples in the form of activity blocks. In certain cases, new activity blocks were developed to address a recommendation.

	RECOMMENDATIONS	ACTIVITY BLOCKS
1.	Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills: highlight the importance of teaching and developing 21st Century skills by including prompts and examples within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation.	Focus on collaboration, creativity and critical thinking. See respective activity blocks. NEW ACTIVITY BLOCK: ARGUMENTATION: Ask students to evaluate the robot of another group. The students need to structure their evaluation providing judgement in relation to the goal/objective (what the robot was supposed to do) and an argument justifying the judgement based on the performance on the robot, and the effort the group made. For the latter the groups can have a short discussion about their difficulties and the solutions they found. Finally, their evaluation should be concluded with suggestions for improvement. It is important that groups have the opportunity to consider these evaluations and refine their work based on these evaluations before presenting their work to the class.
2.	Consider creativity as leading to innovation and entrepreneurship: provide examples of how creativity can be fostered using the year 2 evaluation findings.	See activity blocks "Being Creative - story paths" (D.4.2 section activity blocks)
3.	Examine critical thinking through a focus on reflective thinking: highlight the importance of teaching and developing critical thinking	See activity Blocks – Reflecting

	through reflection by including prompts within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation; provide examples of critical thinking activities using reflective tools; integrate reflection in student productions.	
4.	Provide evidence of learning: include examples of achievable and measureable objectives; provide examples of how student productions (artefacts of learning) and reflections (as a form of student production) can demonstrate achievement in a range of objectives, including domain, technical and 21st Century skills.	See section 1.2 Post activity Report on the Activity Plan Template V03
5.	Differentiate activities: within student productions, teaching methods and the sequence and description of activities, prompt activity designers to consider differentiation, providing examples of how this can be achieved in relation to sample objectives.	See activity block - Experimenting- tasks with gradual difficulty. NEW ACTIVITY BLOCK: New activity block was developed with reference to Year 2 ESI CEE activity plan where optional and more difficult activities were developed
6.	Developing new entry points: highlight alternative entry points by including this aspect in the student learning process with examples; similarly include suggestions and examples within the first phase of the sequence and description of activities	Ideas for new entry points: subject matter - connect robotics with other subject matters, with every-day life issues and with aspects related to student lives, consider also storytelling video making, and games
7.	Develop approaches to the orchestration of teamwork, with particular consideration of mixed-gender groups: develop tools to scaffold teamwork, collaboration and social interaction	See activity block on collaboration rules. NEW ACTIVITY BLOCK: Create a common space (e.g. a table) where all groups can go and observe the others and take turns to test their robot. In this context testing time should be strictly defined in order to prevent one group occupying the table without leaving the others to try out things. Common spaces for testing and discussing seem to offer good opportunities for more experienced/advanced students to provide help to the others, less experienced students to ask for help, see others also fail and see different approaches and ideas implemented
8.	Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM: identify points for discussions about the work of scientists (including who scientists are), experiences of STEM subjects and robotics in relation to STE(A)M subjects and careers.	NEW ACTIVITY BLOCK: Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM Role-play between invisibles: STEM is difficult vs STEM is interesting/ useful/ Important. Use a whiteboard where you create two columns. In one of the columns, students are expected to write down arguments about STEM being difficult or not for them. In the other column, students are expected to write down arguments about STEM being interesting/useful/important. Students are expected to populate the table individually and any time they want (i.e they are expected to leave their table and write on the whiteboard at any time during their engagement with the activity). Arguments should be short phrases. At the end of the workshop, the whole

		class revises the arguments written in both columns and vote which of the two opinions is better supported and thus the better supported wins.
9.	Raise awareness of pedagogic strategies and their impact: – identify effective pedagogic strategies, provide examples of how they can be used and why they are effective	See section 1.2 Post activity Report on the Activity Plan Template V03

Table 2. List of recommendations from D.6.3 and suggested activity blocks to support activity design during year 3 of the project.

As a next step, partners were asked before embarking on the design or on the revision of their activity plans for year three, to take into account the recommendations and integrate them in their activity plans. It was explained that not every activity plan should be addressing all recommendations. However, partners could try to address the recommendations as a whole in the set of activity plans they were going to develop since every partner was designing - implementing more than one activity plan. To better monitor and support this process, UoA asked the partners to use a shared spreadsheet to indicate which recommendations each activity plan was addressing (see Table x below) and provide a set of keywords explaining how these recommendations were addressed in their activity plan.

	PARTNER	ACTIVITY PLAN TITLE	RECOMMENDATIONS ADDRESSED
1	TU Wien	ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator	Creativity with a story telling, Critical thinking, evidence of learning and new entry points; 2. Creativity - Asking to create a story with the robots and if there is enough time implement it; 3. Critical Thinking - Participants are asked to come with a solution to an open problem and they must justify why they think it works; 4. Evidence of learning - In each session they are asked to write a letter to a friend telling him/her what they have done today; 6. Entry Points - The use of a real pole let participants to think about where they are in the real world.
2	TU Wien	Basic introduction into robotics and VPL,	3. Critical thinking - Participants are asked to think about what a robot is and which photos could be consider a robot 6. Entry Points - Participants were asked to think about examples that are connected with a real life
3	TU Wien	Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V2)	3. Critical thinking - Participants are asked to think about what a robot is and which photos could be consider a robot 6. Entry Points - Participants were asked to think about examples that are connected with a real life
4	ESI CEE	Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot	1. Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills; 4. Provide evidence of learning; 5. Differentiate activities; 6. Developing new entry points; 8. Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM;
5	ESI CEE	Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	1. Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills; 2. Consider creativity as leading to innovation and entrepreneurship; 6. Developing new entry points;

			8. Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM;
6	ESI CEE	Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills	1. Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills; 2. Consider creativity as leading to innovation and entrepreneurship; 3. Examine critical thinking through a focus on reflective thinking; 8. Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM;
7	UoA 432	Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine	3. Examine critical thinking through a focus on reflective thinking 4. Evidence of learning 6. Developing new entry points 8. Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM
8	UoA 437	Insects' battle	1,2,3,4,7,9
9	UoA 438	Park the Robot	1,2,3,5, 6, 8, 9
10	UoA 431	Exploring Planet Ektonis	1,3, 4,7,9
11	UoA 435	Robot Olympics	2,3,5,8
12	UoA 434a	Robotic Insects (a)- b	2,3,4,9,8
13	UoA 436	Design and program robots to solve the maze problem.	2,3,4,5,8
14	UoA 433	Building a robot and making it smart	2. expressing creative ideas in real life context. 4. Receiving feedback on real constructions or achievements.5. providing freedom to express their preferences through the robotic construction or the activity result.
15	CU	Basic Introduction to SLurtles	3; 7
16	CU	SLurtles Introduction: Orientation and Construction	3; 4; 7
17	CU	Building our Virtual World	2; 4; 6
18	AcrossLimits	Engaging with robots in a fun way	1,2,3,4
19	AcrossLimits	Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash	2,3,4,5
20	PRIA	Design Thinking and Robotics workshop	2. Creativity: Build something with the materials that are available, even when there are some (funny) constraints 3, 5, 6, 8
21	PRIA	Robotic 4 Kids	2, 3, 5
22	PRIA	Elementary Lego Mindstorms	2, 5

Table 3: Compliance of activity plans with year 2 recommendations

The table offers an overview of the activity plans and the actual recommendations in which each activity plan focuses. It has to be noted that this table depicts the partner's view on how they interpreted the recommendation and how they transformed it to design choices. The guideline for the partners was to provide a set of keywords indicating how they addressed the specific

recommendation in their activity plan. However this recommendation was not followed thoroughly by all partners. Next, we will attempt to further elaborate on the above table structuring our discussion around each recommendation and using information from the actual activity plans.

5.1 21ST CENTURY SKILLS

The first recommendation is phrased as following: *“Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills: highlight the importance of teaching and developing 21st Century skills by including prompts and examples within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation”*

Partners stated that 7, out of the 22 activity plans meet this recommendation:

1. Engaging with robots in a fun way (AL)
2. Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot
3. Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop
4. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills
5. Exploring Planet Ektonis
6. Insects' battle
7. Park the Robot

Unfortunately partners did not provide information on how they addressed this recommendation in their activity plans. Only ESI CEE indicated a focus of 21st century skills as a unit to encompass soft skills and industry skills (see lines 3,4,5). An examination of the respective activity plans showed that all involved group work, they stated in the skills cultivated communication, collaboration and problem solving. However, all but the activity plan coming from AcrossLimits, did not have a designed activity that focused on teaching and reflecting on collaboration.

The activity plans coming from ESI CEE consist a special case as they state clearly from the very beginning (in the short summary provided) that their activity plans aim at 21st century skills such as: Problem solving; Communication; Flexibility and adaptability; Coming up with innovative, unique or imaginative solutions; Cultivation of digital fluency through improving children’s technological knowledge. Furthermore, they seem to place a special emphasis on industry and soft skills when they refer to flexibility and adaptability, coming up with innovative solution and cultivating digital skills, which are connected with technological fluency. Although some of these skills (like adaptability and innovative solutions) might be encountered in several activity plans, they are not stated clearly as driving forces of the design.

5.2 CREATIVITY

“Consider creativity as leading to innovation and entrepreneurship: provide examples of how creativity can be fostered using the year 2 evaluation findings.” Fifteen out of the 22 activity plans claim to address creativity in their design.

1. ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator TU Wien
2. Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop ESI CEE
3. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills ESI CEE
4. Insects' battle UoA
5. Park the Robot UoA
6. Robot Olympics UoA

7. Robotic Insects a – b UoA
8. Design and program robots to solve the maze problem. UoA
9. Building a robot and making it smart UoA
10. Building our Virtual World CU
11. Engaging with robots in a fun way AcrossLimits
12. Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash AcrossLimits
13. Design thinking and robotics workshop PRIA
14. Robotic 4 Kids PRIA
15. Elementary Lego Mindstorms PRIA

From these activity plans only TUWien, UoA in one of their scenarios (“Building a robot and making it smart”), and PRIA in one of their scenarios (Design Thinking and Robotics workshop), explained how they addressed creativity in their design. Integration of creativity in these cases seems to involve:

- **The focus of the activity** (what are the students are expected to do and engage with). In this case falls the TUWien activity plan which involves story making with a robot. Story making and robots was identified as an interesting creative activity and was provided to the partners as an activity block (see D.4.2)
- **The materials of the construction:** This is the case of the PRIA activity plan “Design Thinking and Robotics workshop”. Here creativity involves overcoming the shortcomings of using everyday materials for constructing a robot *“Build something with the materials that are available, even when there are some (funny) constraints”*
- **The type of the problem:** Open ended problems that call for creative solutions which in the case of the UoA scenarios these are problems connected to real life situations *“expressing creative ideas in real life context”*.

A close view on the activity plans, which stated that they address creativity but haven’t explained their design choices, show that they can all fall under these three categories. Specifically, ESI CEE’s scenario, which involves Educational Robotics and Creativity falls under the first category: In this case students are asked to create a mind map with creative uses of robots. The workshop focuses on discussing creativity with the students and then engaging them to the solutions they provide. Furthermore, in this category also fall activity plans that involve artistic expressions (e.g. drawing a postcard for friends AL, making the nose of Finch to light up in different colors – ESI CEE, etc.).

The materials of the construction is another view to creativity, which seems to be closely connected to the concept of constructions. Apart from the PRIA scenario the robotic insects and Insect’s battle seem to fall under the same category as students need to combine everyday cheap materials in order to create a robot that manages to move. We consider this design approach to creativity interesting as it seems to be inherent to robotic constructions.

Fig 1. Student constructions of Robot insects (see evidence of learning section in the specific activity plan)

In the last category “Type of problem”, fall most of the activity plans, since the constructions with which students engage, involve different solutions in terms of programming and of Robot construction. For example students could use different combinations of sensors (e.g. tactile, color, etc.) to make their robot effective in avoiding obstacles (See for example PRIA’s activity plan Robotics 4 KiDs)

5.3 CRITICAL THINKING AS AN EXPRESSION OF REFLECTIVE THINKING

The third recommendation involves reflective thinking as an aspect of critical thinking and is phrased as follows: *“Examine critical thinking through a focus on reflective thinking: highlight the importance of teaching and developing critical thinking through reflection by including prompts within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation; provide examples of critical thinking activities using reflective tools; integrate reflection in student productions”*.

1. ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator TU Wien
2. Basic introduction into robotics and VPL TU Wien
3. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills ESI CEE
4. Building container houses with a CNC Drawing Machine UoA
5. Insects' battle UoA
6. Park the Robot UoA
7. Exploring Planet Ektonis UoA
8. Robot Olympics UoA
9. Robotic Insects (a)- b UoA
10. Design and program robots to solve the maze problem. UoA
11. Basic Introduction to SLurtles- CU
12. SLurtles Introduction: Orientation and Construction- CU
13. Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash AcrossLimits
14. Engaging with robots in a fun way AcrossLimits
15. Design Thinking and Robotics workshop PRIA
16. Robotic4Kids PRIA

From the list presented in this section, 16 out of the 22 activity plans claim to be aligned with this recommendation. However, only TUWien provided an insight on their design choices regarding critical – reflective thinking: *“- Participants are asked to come up with a solution to an open problem and they must justify why they think it works”* and *“Participants are asked to think about what a robot is and which photos could be considered as a robot”*. From these two phrases it appears that critical – reflective thinking is related to the focus of the task which involves students evaluating their solution and existing knowledge to justify their answers.

In a similar vein most of the activities listed here involve activities where teams present their solutions to the classroom and evaluate their performance and results. For example in the “Robotic Olympics” scenario the designer devotes a session of the activity plan called “Feedback and evaluation” which involves demonstration of robots, analysis of the construction procedure and exchange advice and refinement of the robots: *“All teams exhibit (demonstrate) the construction type. A small contest is taking place. Students observe rival robots. They analyze the plan of their construction, receive observations and advice from other groups, and try to improve their robotics.”*. Most of the activity plans listed here involve a session where reflective thinking is linked to feedback and evaluation of

student constructions. In these cases, reflection takes the form of classroom discussion and if there is time available, it might be integrated in the initial construction with the aim to improve it.

Concrete outputs of reflective thinking are encountered in different digital or physical forms:

- **Social media posts:** In UoA activity plans listed here students reflect on their constructions using an educational social media platform called e-me. Reflective thinking here takes place twice in the course of the activity plan: once when the students brainstorm about their construction and then at the end of the session when they have completed their construction.
- **Constructs:** In the activity plan “SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing” designed by CU where reflective and critical thinking is supported by a specific software “Sway” and there is a concrete output “Sway books”. A similar role-play the diary entries and the postcards integrated in the activity plans designed by Across Limits.

5.4 PROVIDE EVIDENCE OF LEARNING

***Provide evidence of learning:** include examples of achievable and measureable objectives; provide examples of how student productions (artefacts of learning) and reflections (as a form of student production) can demonstrate achievement in a range of objectives, including domain, technical and 21st Century skills.*

The recommendation regarding evidence of learning was considered an important aspect of the design of activity plans. In the previous version of the activity plan template it was emphasized in the “how to in the classroom” section where designers were expected to include an evaluation section. This is something that all activity plans from year 3 have followed. In most cases, evaluation is connected to some sort of reflective thinking on what students have created and in one case “Robot Olympics”, students have at their disposal a set of variables – axes against which they evaluate their constructions. Overall evidence of learning is linked to the methods and the ways of evaluating student learning and it involves a) self- assessment (see for example “Designing a Robot and making it smart” by UoA) b) reflection on student constructs by presentation and discussion in the classroom and c) Reflective constructs (see for example CU activity plan “SLurtles, Introduction, Construction and Orientation”, section Reflection and Evidencing Learning).

Evidence of learning was considered a priority in year 3, and thus UoA further supported it by the new section in the activity plan template called “Post activity Report” See section 2. The post activity report was expected to offer to the designers an opportunity to reflect on their evaluation methods and provide more thorough and concrete information (descriptions and pictures) based on the implementation of their design. Specifically, in the post activity report partners were expected to specify what they believe that their students learned during the implementation of the activity plan, provide a short description, identify specific concepts related to STE(A)M. Designers were also prompted to enrich their descriptions with photographs of student constructions and student comments. All partners were expected to complete the post activity report for each workshop they were implementing (i.e. if an activity plan was implemented twice then two post activity reports were expected identifying the special characteristics of each implementation). Based on post activity report being an integral part of the activity plan, according to year 3 revision, we would expect that evidence of learning would be integrated in all activity plans. However, not all partners completed the post activity report and only 12 out of the 21 activity plans claimed to have addressed this recommendation.

1. Robot Elevator **TU Wien**
2. Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot **ESI CEE**
3. Building container houses with a CNC Drawing Machine **UoA**
4. Insects' battle **UoA**
5. Exploring Planet Ektonis **UoA**
6. Robotic Insects (a)- (b) **UoA**
7. Design and program robots to solve the maze problem. **UoA**
8. Building a robot and making it smart **UoA**
9. SLurtles Introduction: Orientation and Construction **CU**
10. Building our Virtual World **CU**
11. Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash **AcrossLimits**
12. Engaging with robots in a fun way **AcrossLimits**

Out of the 12 activity plans only TUWien provided an explanation of how they documented student learning. Specifically, they mentioned that students documented their learning by writing a letter to a friend explaining what they learned. This activity is closely related to the reflective – critical thinking analysed earlier. As we mentioned earlier, evidence of learning is also connected to the evaluation activities integrated in the activity plans, the main forms of which were described earlier in this section.

Leaving aside the list above we looked at year 3 activity plans and specifically in the section evidence of learning out of the 22 activity plans provide information regarding evidence of student learning. 8 out of the 12 activity plans mentioned in the list above provided information in the evidence for learning activity plan and these plans are listed here:

1. ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator TUWien
2. Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot ESI CEE
3. Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine UoA
4. Design thinking and robotics workshop PRIA (emphasis on interesting – unexpected moments)
5. Insect's battle UoA
6. Exploring planet EKTONIS UoA
7. Robotic Insect UoA
8. Building a robot and making it smart

Our analysis of the provided activity plans showed that another five activity plans which did not indicate that they followed the recommendation “evidence for learning” provided the relevant information:

9. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills ESI-CEE
10. Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop ESI-CEE
11. Robotic 4 KiDs PRIA
12. Workshop Elementary Lego Mindstorms PRIA
13. Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V01 and V02) TU-Wien
14. Robotic Olympics UoA

Pre-defined Concepts

As shown in the activity plan template, apart from the descriptions and the documentation of evidence of learning, the template offered a set of concepts central to STEM for partners to choose.

Not all activity plans offered insights about learning of the specific concepts. However, we have some data from:

- ESI CEE Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills: Iteration; Proportion; Similarity
- UoA: ROBOTIC OLYMPICS: Proportion; Variables; Symmetry; Volume
- ESI CEE: Educational Robotics and Creativity workshop: Iteration; similarity
- ESI CEE: Visualizing Mathematics with MathBot: Iteration; similarity; proportion; symmetry
- UoA: Exploring Planet Ektonis: Iteration; proportion; variables
- UoA: Making a robot Smart: Iteration

From the list above it appears that there is an emphasis of the activity plans on student learning about iteration. Variables appear in 2 out of the 6 activity plans. Our interpretation is that although activities might use variables for programming, the focus of the activity plan could be on other concepts like iteration. Another observation for the pre-defined concepts offered by the activity plan template is that several activities include mathematics concepts like proportion, symmetry and similarity. A closer look at the pre-defined concepts integrated in the activity plans, shows that these activity plans focus on designing learning activities that integrate learning of programming with mathematics.

Designer specified focus

Apart from the specified concepts offered in the activity plan template, partners, identified a set of concepts which were specific to the activity plans they designed. To gain an overview of the concepts, we organized them into six different categories according to their focus.

PROGRAMMING

- Introduction to programming and the motor function block
- Using control structures (loops and branches)
- Students applied sequences of actions to program their robot;

ROBOT CONSTRUCTION

- Introduction to the Robot Set
- Building Robots
- The usage of sensors
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors;
- Students became familiar with technical vocabulary and robot parts
- They learned to recognize the different role of robot parts (motors, sensor).
- The different settings they applied and the solutions they gave to each task indicates that they understood the way a robot get “smart”, in other words the way the robot can be programmed.

SITUATING ROBOTS IN REAL LIFE

- How can robots make the world a better place? (PRIA – Robotics 4 KiDs)

- Draw a robot (to investigate student perceptions about robots and their ideas about the role of robots in people’s lives) - Basic introduction into robotics and VPL TU-Wien
- Introduction on robotics and different application fields (PRIA Elementary Lego Mindstorms)

MATHEMATICAL CONCEPTS

- Spatial Visualization and Imagery (Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine – UoA)
- Properties of 3d Shapes (cubes)- (Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine – UoA)
- Exercising knowledge of angles ESI CEE Visualizing mathematics with MathBot
- Using mathematical tools to perform accurate measurements ESI CEE Visualizing mathematics with MathBot
- Using positive, negative numbers and decimals to obtain accuracy in the robot performance ESI CEE Visualizing mathematics with MathBot; Educational robotics and creativity workshop.

SOFT SKILLS

- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas. (ESI CEE Visualizing mathematics with MathBot; Educational robotics and creativity workshop)
- Students identified and solved problems; (ESI CEE Visualizing mathematics with MathBot; Educational robotics and creativity workshop)
- Most of them managed to collaborate successfully with their team members - which were assigned and not selected by them- despite the disagreements that came up. (UoA Making a Robot Smart)

ENGAGEMENT WITH STEM - INTERDISCIPLINARITY

- Eventually, the discussions they had inside each group and with other groups are strong evidence their engagement with technology and STEM issues. (UoA Making a Robot Smart)
- They understood the importance of combining knowledge of different fields in order to achieve a goal. (UoA Making a Robot Smart)

Means to capture evidence of learning

In the activity plan “Basic introduction into robotics and VPL” the designers provided information on how they gathered evidence of student learning offering a wide range of techniques: including writing letter, solving a quiz, defining top 5 construction tips, teaching other children, constructing something of their own and participating in an interview with the tutor – teacher:

- Workshop 2 we made them write a letter.
- Workshop 3 was an interview.
- Workshop 4 was an own project with Lego
- Workshop 5 was a Quiz
- Workshop 6 was another kind of quiz
- Workshop 7 were their top 5 tips
- Workshop 8 was a blockly puzzle
- Workshop 9 was their own project with a language of their choice

- Workshop 10 was teaching other kids

The list above is illustrative of the evaluation methods the designers used but they do not provide information regarding what they evaluated and what were the results with respect to student learning.

Documenting evidence of learning

Most of the descriptions referring to evidence of learning indicated mainly what were the objectives of the activity plan, i.e. what the designers wanted their students to learn and not what the students learned and how this was inferred. In several cases what was mentioned as evidence of learning was a general objective like “Introduction on the Robot set”. In fewer cases like in “How to make a Robot Smart – UoA” the designer indicated what students learned and how he/she inferred student learning (e.g. using effectively STEM related concepts during group discussions).

Evidence of learning has been extensively documented with photographs and extracts from student discussions in the activity plan “Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine” (UoA).

Evidence of learning was also documented with Photographs of student constructions (UoA – Robotic Insect) and with photographs of students during their engagement with their constructions (TU-Wien, ESI-CEE) highlighting group work, collective constructions and group discussions.

Discussion

From the analysis on evidence of learning as provided 14 out of the 22 activity plans we draw the following observations:

- a) Evidence of learning focused on concepts related to programming, robot construction and mathematics. Interestingly in these 14 activity plans evidence of learning does not involve other STE(A)M concepts although the disciplines involved include Science (Robotic Olympics _ Exploring planet Ektonis, Building a robot and making it smart, Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop to mention a few from Table 1). There are also disciplines like History (Robotic Olympics) and Societal Life Skills (Building container Houses with A CNC Drawing machine) mentioned in the activity plans but designers’ reporting on evidence of learning did not seem to include concepts from these disciplines.
- b) In two out of the 14 activity plans, there is reference to soft skills like problem solving and collaboration.
- c) In three out of the 14 activity plans, designed by PRIA and TUWien, evidence of learning involves not only concepts related to robots and programming but also an understanding of what robots are, how they can be used in real life and what are their possible application fields. Although various activity plans might include introductory sessions that aim to situate robotic technologies to real life, they do not embark on evaluating what students learned from these sessions. Since connections to real – life is an aspect which is associated with robotic technologies and is also related with offering multiple entry points to raise student interest about robots, we consider that focusing on and capturing evidence of student learning might be pedagogically interesting for teaching and learning with Educational Robotics
- d) In one activity plan (Making a robot smart- UoA), evidence of learning involved explicitly STEM and the importance of interdisciplinarity. The importance of interdisciplinarity seems to be a meta-cognitive element inherent to robotic constructions. We consider this as a

valuable focus of learning with robotics because it makes a very good use of the special characteristics of robotic constructions.

- e) What designers described as evidence of learning is not consistent across the activity plans. In several cases evidence of learning is described as designer's objectives and the descriptions are too general failing to provide valuable information regarding what students learned during their engagement with these activities. On the other hand, in fewer cases, designers provided evidence of learning in the form of pictures, student discussions and descriptions explaining how they inferred that their students learned what they claimed that they learned.
- f) Based on the activity plans we analysed, evidence of learning was inferred mainly from student constructions (robots, programs), student discussions (in verbal and written forms) and from various types of evaluations like quizzes, puzzles, reflective products (like advice, letters, etc.)

Overall, evidence of learning as it was presented in the activity plans, provided valuable information with regards to the focus of learning (STEM concepts, Connection of robots to real life, soft skills and metacognitive skills) and provided few but useful insights to student learning through pictures and student comments. However, there is a need for consistency across activity plans regarding how evidence of learning is defined and how it is best documented. Furthermore, the fact that 1/3 of the activity plans (7 out of the 22) did not include the post activity reports, indicates that this is a time consuming activity that needs support to be implemented and needs to be better aligned with how teachers and designers identify and document evidence of learning in Robotics activities. Another reason that might be related to the lack of consistency and the partial response to the post activity reports, has probably to do with the nature of robotic activities: evidence of learning in most cases is situated in the student constructions, which more often than not involve group work. These are both challenging situations to analyse and extract evidence of learning from, however they consist a useful research and design challenge.

5.5 DIFFERENTIATE ACTIVITIES

Differentiate activities: within student productions, teaching methods and the sequence and description of activities, prompt activity designers to consider differentiation, providing examples of how this can be achieved in relation to sample objectives.

1. Visualizing Mathematics With The Mathbot ESI CEE-
2. Park the Robot UoA
3. Robot Olympics- UoA
4. Design and program robots to solve the maze problem.- UoA
5. Building a robot and making it smart - UoA
6. Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash - AcrossLimits
7. Design Thinking and Robotics workshop - PRIA
8. Robotic4Kids - PRIA
9. Elementary Lego Mindstorms - PRIA

9 out of the 22 activity plans indicated that they met the recommendation of offering differentiated activities. In the shared file only the designer of the activity "Building a robot and making it smart" offered a description of how this recommendation was implemented in their design: "*providing freedom to express their preferences through the robotic construction or the activity result*". From this statement, we can infer differentiation of activities is addressed through open-ended problems,

which can be addressed with different solutions in a varying degree of effectiveness. This is well demonstrated in the activity plans of PRIA where they include open-ended tasks like “Save the world”: *“The students had to think about a robot capable of making the world a better place. Afterwards they had to modify the construction and the software of the robot to fit their concept. After completing their robot, the students presented their work in front of the class.”* A similar approach was to design a robot to follow a theater script in the activity plan “Elementary Lego Mindstorms”.

Another approach to differentiated activities involves the creation of additional activities, usually more advanced, for students or teams who complete what is considered main or basic work and they might have a faster pace in comparison to other groups. This approach was introduced by ESI CEE in the activity plan “Visualizing Mathematics with MathBot” during year two and it was preserved in the revised version of the scenario in year 3. The same approach is found in the activity plan “Design thinking and robotics” designed by PRIA where there is an activity in the “how to” section called “Additional activities”. In this section, the designers show explicitly that they design for differentiation, as they take into account the different pace of the various teams: *“Additional activities: Depending on the pace of learning of the students, additional exercises are possible to be done by the different groups. Which activities as well as the number of executed activities are decided by the PRIA tutors.”*

In both cases where additional – more advanced activities are integrated into the activity plan, these involve mainly programming tasks (from the PRIA activity plan “Design thinking and robotics”):

- **Square and “for”-loops:** *First the students get told to let the robot drive a square with the until now learned knowledge. Afterwards the concept of “for”-loops is explained and applied to the previous task.*
- **Digital sensors and “while”-loops:** *During this exercise the students learned the usage of programming a tactile sensor using the programming concept of “while”-loops.*

5.6 NEW ENTRY POINTS

Developing new entry points: *highlight alternative entry points by including this aspect in the student learning process with examples; similarly include suggestions and examples within the first phase of the sequence and description of activities*

1. ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator **TU Wien**
2. Basic introduction into robotics and VPL **TU Wien**
3. Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V2) **TU Wien**
4. Visualizing Mathematics With The Mathbot **ESI CEE**
5. ER4STEM-ESICEE-Activity-Plan-Educational-Robotics-and-Creativity-v1 **ESI CEE**
6. Building container houses with a CNC Drawing Machine **UoA**
7. Make an automatic parking system **UoA**
8. Building our Virtual World **CU**
9. Design Thinking and Robotics **PRIA**

Nine out of the 22 activity plans stated that they addressed this recommendation. More information regarding is provided only from TUWien for two activity plans: *“The use of a real pole let participants to think about where they are in the real world”* (Robotic elevator); *Participants were asked to think about examples that are connected with a real life* (Basic introduction to robotics and VPL). These two

examples are aligned to the idea that new or multiple entry points are offered when robotics activities are integrated in authentic tasks or tasks connected to real life (see also D.4.2). This idea might be implemented in two ways: a) **Selecting a topic that is connected to real life**: For example in the UoA activity plan “Building container houses with a CNC Drawing Machine”, students program their robots to design the nets of container houses which are supposed to host people who suffered from a physical disaster. b) **Discussing with the students how robots can be used in real life**: This is the case of most activity plans and this discussion might take place in the introductory phase (see for example the ESI CEE activity plans) or at the end of the workshop when students have already worked with robots and are more aware of their potential and functionalities (see for example the PRIA activity plan where students engage into thinking how robots can make the world a better place).

5.7 TEAM WORK – MIXED GENDER GROUPS

Develop approaches to the orchestration of teamwork, with particular consideration of mixed-gender groups: develop tools to scaffold teamwork, collaboration and social interaction

Activity plans stating that they met the requirement for team work and mixed gender groups:

1. Insects' battle **UoA**
2. Exploring Planet Ektonis - **UoA**
3. Basic Introduction to SLurtles- **CU**
4. SLurtles Introduction: Orientation and Construction - **CU**

Only four out of the 22 activity plans stated that they followed this recommendation. Looking at the specific activity plans we observed that those designed by CU explicitly stated in the section of Social orchestration that mixed gender groups were expected to be formed when possible. In the other two activity plans designed by UoA, group formulation was based on a) random order (exploring planet ektonis) and b) on the different specialties of the students who were in a Vocational School (i.e. programming, electronics, etc.) – Insect Battles. However, none of these activity plans had a special design in addressing gender issues that might be emerging in collaborations of mixed gender groups. An exception here are the revised activity plans designed by AcrossLimits – which include activities and worksheets for students reflect and focus on teamwork. Similarly the Revised activity plan by ESI-CEE Visualizing mathematics with the MathBot, structured teamwork around roles and student rotation from all the different roles. Both approaches in collaborative work are analysed in the D.4.2 deliverable.

Apart from what it was stated at the shared documents regarding team worked and mixed gender groups, and considering that all activity plans of year three are based exclusively or include teamwork, we attempted an overview in the orchestration of teamwork in the form of table:

ACTIVITY PLAN	GROUP FORMATION
Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills	Students determined by the school teacher
Basic introduction into robotics and VPL	No mixed gender groups
Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V2)	Mixed gender groups

ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator	Based on subject preference (technology, engineering, arts and design, organization and leadership)
Robotic 4 KiDs	No grouping criteria
Workshop Elementary Lego Mindstorms	No grouping criteria
Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine	Mixed ability, mixed gender
Robotic Olympics	Grouping by age
Basic Introduction to SLurtles	Working individually at start. In matched ability pairs for problem solving with more able and talented leading learning
Building Our Virtual World	Students are in mixed-ability pairs. Girls working with boys where possible.
SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing	Working individually at start. Students are in mixed-ability pairs. Girls working with boys where possible.
Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash	Mixed abilities. Single or mixed gender.
Engaging with robots in a fun way	Mixed abilities. Single or mixed gender.
Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups
Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot	No specific criteria – students or schoolteachers decide how to form the groups based on pre-established friendships or due to disciplinary reasons. However, as this is a workshop intended for recurring participants of the ER4STEM project, students are encouraged to remain in the groups with which they were during the previous workshop
Design thinking and robotics workshop	No criteria
Exploring planet Ektonis	Random order
Building a robot and making it smart	Students that known each other before the workshop, chose their partners. In other cases the groups consisted of same-aged members trying to keep mixed-sex groups
Robotic Insect	Mixed ability, mixed gender where possible
Insects' battle	Mixed specialties (Vocational School)
Park the Robot	Students that have worked together as a team during Math Club's activities this year – students preferences

Table 4. Activity plans and designed social orchestration

Based on the information collected and presented in the table above, we draw the following observations regarding how teamwork was orchestrated in the different activity plans:

- No mixed groups: This was a choice mentioned in one of the TU Wien Activity plans. However, it is not clear if this statement refers to gender or to abilities as no further information was provided.
- Mixed groups: Again, no further information is provided so as to make clear if mixed groups refer to ability, gender or both.
- Mixed ability - mixed gender
- Mixed ability – mixed or single gender (Across Limits)
- No specific grouping criteria. In this case students form groups based on their preferences, friendships, prior acquaintance or on teacher decisions. This type of social orchestration is pursued in the ESI CEE workshops and in some UoA Workshops.
- Pre-formed teams: when participation in the specific workshop comes as a follow up of another activity - workshop (ESI CEE / UoA “The parking procedure).
- Random order
- Student interests and background (TU Wien – UoA robotic battles)

All these means of group formulations indicate that a) in some activity plans designers place emphasis on gender by making it a group formulation criterion and b) in cases where the criterion of group formulation is different e.g. teacher decisions, random order, student interests, it does not mean that mixed gender groups will not be emerging. Prior acquaintances and friendships when used as a team formulation criterion might result in single gender groups especially in primary school students.

5.8 CHANGING AND SUSTAINING ATTITUDES TO STEM

Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM: identify points for discussions about the work of scientists (including who scientists are), experiences of STEM subjects and robotics in relation to STE(A)M subjects and careers.

1. Visualizing Mathematics With The Mathbot **ESI CEE**
2. Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop **ESI CEE**
3. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills **ESI CEE**
4. Building container houses with a CNC Drawing Machine - **UoA**
5. Park the Robot - **UoA**
6. Robot Olympics - **UoA**
7. Robotic Insects (a)- b - **UoA**
8. Design and program robots to solve the maze problem- **UoA**
9. Design Thinking and Robotics - **PRIA**

9 out of the 22 activity plans are recorded as meeting the requirement for changing and sustaining attitudes to stem. From these, the ESI CEE activity plans include an introductory section which involves exploration of student attitudes towards STEM and Robots. Part of the introductory activity involves a “draw a scientist at work” activity in which students can integrate their experiences, beliefs and stereotypes and the drawings can become an interesting focus of discussion to change and/or sustain attitudes towards STEM. This recommendation could be seen also in relation to Raising students’ interest for Robotics and STEM through providing new entry points (see recommendation 6.6). An interesting activity in this context was introduced by PRIA, which focused on how making mistakes is not something to be avoided. This activity involved a clapping game and the expected

output was student laughs and cheers. As stated in the activity plan: “*The aim of the activity is to give the students the feeling, that making mistakes is not bad, but is rather something which is ok to happen to promote a more freely idea development process. Thus, the students are told to start laughing or cheering when errors occur to promote this. During the activity, the trainers try to emphasize that making mistakes is more than welcome during the task and in general.*” We consider that this activity is a good example for changing and sustaining attitudes towards stem as a) it demonstrates something essential in STEM methodology and epistemology, which is to hypothesis testing and feedback evaluation. Furthermore, following the constructionist tradition, which stresses that what is important in the learning process is not to know the right answer but to be able to evaluate your mistakes and formulate a hypothesis that will lead you closer to the desirable result.

5.9 PEDAGOGIC STRATEGIES: USE AND IMPACT

Raise awareness of pedagogic strategies and their impact: identify effective pedagogic strategies, provide examples of how they can be used and why they are effective

None of the partners has stated in the shared document that they addressed this recommendation. However, there are two sources from which we can draw information: one is the activity plans and the other is the post activity reports.

Awareness of pedagogic strategies in the activity plans

In the activity plan template in the section “How to in the classroom” designers are asked to provide information of what teaching methods they will be following per session or phase described there. Thus, the activity plan template functioning as a design instrument offered support to the designers to think about and decide which pedagogic strategy would be more appropriate for what they wanted to teach. Next, we provide an overview of the types of activities (e.g. introductory, construction, etc.) and the pedagogic strategies indicated by the partners.

Introductory activities, which are used to familiarize students with concepts, explain what they are going to do or introduce them to robots the most common pedagogical strategies are:

- Direct instruction
- Demonstration or demonstration by example
- Discussion

When introductory activities focus on construction or programming then, direct instruction might be combined with guided exploration, experimentation and peer teaching.

Activities that involve programming and robot construction most commonly exploit different combinations of the following pedagogical strategies:

- Experimentation
- Discussion
- Problem based instruction
- Inquiry based instruction
- Monitoring
- Peer teaching
- Structured tasks

Finally, evaluation and reflection sessions usually employ combinations of:

- Presentation
- Discussion
- Research

An overall analysis of the teaching methods and pedagogical strategies employed in the activity plans of year 3, shows that designers use a) combinations of various strategies and b) they adapt their strategies to the task – activity they want their students to engage with. For example, group direct instruction and/or demonstration by example can be a good starting point for students to be introduced to the activity or to new concepts and then use this information as a basis for discussion and brainstorming.

Post activity reports: Effectiveness of pedagogic strategies

The post activity reports include three subsections, which are relevant to our discussion here, i.e. “unexpected or interesting moments”, “facilitation of interesting moments” and “ideas for extensions / revisions of the initial activity plans”. These sections provide us with information from the implementations of workshops regarding how the pedagogical strategies specified in the activity plan worked or did not work as this became evidenced in interesting or unexpected moments and how they mitigated or encouraged some situations at the time being and how these actions could be a basis for the revision of the activity plan. As mentioned earlier, 15 out of the 21 activity plans provided information on their post activity reports at a different level of detail:

1. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills
2. Basic introduction into robotics and VPL
3. Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V2)
4. Robot Elevator
5. Robotic 4 KiDs
6. Workshop Elementary Lego Mindstorms
7. Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine
8. Robotic Olympics
9. Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop
10. Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot
11. Design thinking and robotics workshop
12. Exploring planet Ektonis
13. Building a robot and making it smart
14. Robotic Insect
15. Insects' battle

An analysis of the content of the post activity reports showed us that the interesting / unexpected moments and their involved the following aspects:

TEACHERS' CRITICISM

School teachers who became more acquainted with the activities i.e. they had the opportunity to observe what the students were doing or had an interest related to their duties at school, suggested that activities were too open ended for the students and that more information should be provided

for them. In one case (Robotics 4 KiDs - PRIA) this suggestion was grounded on the belief that students would not be able to successfully complete the tasks that were given. In this case the student productions – although criticized as not that creative by the tutor - gave evidence for the teacher to reconsider. Similar attitude was observed in one of the ESI CEE workshops in Bulgaria, where one of the teachers was present in the workshop due to the relationship of the focus with her future task (teach programming with Scratch next year for first time). The teacher had a similar criticism – she was also sitting with a group of students whom she tried to instruct “telling them what to do”. The result – according to the workshop organizers - was that the specific group was distracted and underperformed during the time the teacher interacted with them.

This criticism is interesting for the analysis we are doing here because it reveals that in some cases “teachers” would prefer to resort to more instructive tasks in the sense that they offer them more control and ensure that the students will not fail. The mitigation of this problem from the ESI CEE group involved a) making explicit that the pedagogical strategy was to involve students to exploration and discussion b) sharing the resources (i.e. activity plans and worksheets) with the teacher and c) asking the teacher to observe – without intervening - how the other teams were working. For both cases, the final student constructions seem to be convincing evidence that open-ended tasks might have interesting and successful results.

The ESI CEE team who organized robotics workshops in schools, suggested that a pre-workshop discussion with teachers and parents seemed important for such an organization to be convincing. According to this analysis, these discussions should address and explain the rationale underlying the open-ended – exploratory activities accompanied by some student constructions.

The experience of ESI CEE showed that the way teachers perceive these activities and how these activities are situated in the school life can influence greatly the parents’ attitude and the success of the workshop. In their report, they describe a situation where two teachers showed explicitly their dislike for the workshop in front of the students because the workshop was taking place during school hours and they had to change their schedule. As a result, the children’s parents were calling challenging the workshop and wondering why their children were not following their normal schedule. In several cases, children’s comments about the workshop after the first session made the parents to reconsider and call the organizers to apologize.

COOPERATION VS COMPETITION OF ROBOTS

ESI CEE has reported also from year 2 that they observed unhealthy competitive behavior between students. Thus, this year they integrated in their activity plan a task where the robots of the different teams were supposed to cooperate and keep the initial task where the robots were competing against each other. The organizers reported that starting with the competition task drove students out of control and it was very difficult to change the competitive mindset in the activities to follow. Thus, they decided to change the order of the tasks and in another implementation that followed, they focused only on robot cooperation which worked very well with the students.

TEAMWORK

Teamwork appeared to be a challenge in most of the reports. The activity plans this year based on the experience from year 2, the evaluation recommendations and the activity blocks regarding collaboration, included some ideas for structuring teamwork. However, the implementation shows that collaboration is always a challenging learning situation asking for tutor intervention and support,

especially in cases where the workshop is not implemented by the schoolteacher but from organizations outside schools who do not know the students and their difficulties in working together with other students.

Specifically, in several cases, there were students who could not work together with the other members of their allocated team and a change of team seemed to be a final – functional resort when nothing else worked. TUWien reported a case where one of the roles – that of the expert- was a reason of argument and competitive behaviour among the members of the team. The reason was that this role was perceived as more prestigious, all students wanted this role, and in some cases, a person undertaking this role was undermined “you are not going to make it anyway”. The instructors introduced turn taking as a mitigation method.

Another aspect reported in relation to teamwork had to do with students who were more experienced with programming or construction tasks. However, there were different behaviours observed in each case. A common reaction was that more experienced students were taking over and they marginalized other students. However, in ESI CEE workshops they reported two different instances. In one case, a student who had participated in the workshops of the previous years was inspired to take programming tasks. This knowledge seemed to contribute into turning her from a “bossy” collaborator to a member of the team that supports the other and gives advice. In another case, ESI CEE- took advantage of the “peer teaching activity block” and ask students who were more experienced in measuring angles to mentor other teams and in several cases the researchers reported the mentors returning to the team they supported to check how they were doing. In another occasion – Robotic Insect – UoA- a student who was experienced in constructions contributed his/her expertise in the teamwork resulting to an impressive construction. The teacher, asked the other students to study the solution applied in the specific construction and ask for explanations from the team who implemented it. Finally, ESI CEE reported a case where a student who was interested in robotics asked the organizers if he could show to the class his robot (a humanoid made by Lego who could move, shoot balls and talk). The organizers integrated this demonstration in the workshop as they saw an opportunity for a lively discussion related to interest for robotics and science.

Competition was an issue that was highlighted by the ESI CEE during the evaluation of year 2 (see also previous section), this year the team introduced an “inviting guests” activity where each team could invite a guest from other teams to show them what they did and discuss with them problems and different solutions. A similar approach – that of exchanging ideas and solution – was implemented in the presentation session of various activity plans where each team would present their construction and accept criticism along with ideas for improvement and advice. However, there was an occasion – TUWien- where teams accused other teams for stealing their ideas.

Overall, the post activity reports showed that in year 3 the implementation of activity plans involved some challenges regarding collaboration however, some interesting instances emerged involving exchange of ideas, peer teaching and mentoring, analysis and discussion around interesting implementations and solutions.

ENGAGEMENT WITH THE TASK – FOCUS OF ACTIVITIES

Various post activity reports mentioned that some of the students were distracted during the workshop. This was attributed in one case - TUWien, to the students’ familiarity with robotics and programming. Students who had no experience at all, tended to be distracted by the robotic parts and failed to pay the necessary attention to instructions. This resulted in students needing a lot of support by the tutors to complete their task. Similarly students with little technological experience

tended to be impatient and contributed to causing technical problems by clicking for example simultaneously to more than one buttons or pressing more than one keys. Technical problems also tended to disorient the students.

In one case – TUWien – a student’s low engagement with the task was attributed to the type of activity which was too theoretical. During the implementation of the workshop, instructors switched from lecturing to asking students to perform a google search about the history of robots. In their revision however, they seemed to consider that the specific task did not contribute much to the core activity of the activity plan and decided to reduce theory and emphasize more building end exploration activities. The latter suggestion for revision was encountered in several post activity reports, showing that students’ interest and high engagement with exploratory - construction activities can offer useful input for shifting the focus of the activity plan from an instructional – lecturing mode to a more exploratory – discussion oriented learning. This is not to say that instructional type of activities are not useful. On the contrary, what we are arguing here is that their timing and focus should be determined in relation to the feedback received from the implementation. That is why a presentation of the history of technology was received very positively from the students in the UoA activity plan robotic Olympics and offered opportunities for students to extend the discussion to aspects related to the ethics of technology in the context of Olympic Games.

TIMING OF ACTIVITIES

In the activity plan extensions / revisions several post – activity reports reported that the timing of the activities they had initially designed was not realistic, in the sense that students needed more time to complete mainly robot building tasks. An interesting instance is mentioned by PRIA where the timing of the activities was based on the assumption that older students would need less time than younger students for the building task. However, in the implementation it was proven that older students needed the same or more time for this type of task in comparison to younger students. The authors of the report offered an interpretation that younger students might be more experienced in building activities because of their engagement with Lego during their free time. In cases where an activity was taking more time than expected, especially when this was considered as core activity, instructors allowed the students to take the time they needed and then they omitted or adjusted other peripheral activities.

DIFFERENTIATION OF ACTIVITIES

In various post activity reports in the revision section, it was mentioned that the activity plan should be revised to include additional tasks for students who are faster than the other groups. An interesting alternative – to teachers or designers thinking beforehand about tasks and activities – came from the Insect’s battle where it was reported that a team of students who worked faster than the others came up with an idea to extend their construction by building a base for their insect. This can be an interesting option for designers to structure student activity so that all teams create some basic constructions and then extend them according to their knowledge and ability. The need to differentiate the activities allowing students to work on their own pace was highlighted in the evaluation recommendations from year 1 and year 2.

6 OUTPUTS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the second year of the project, WP4 had the following outputs:

- A revised version of the activity plan template which informed the activity design tool integrated in the repository
- The post activity report as part of the activity plan, in order to inform evidence of learning, reflection on the design and revision of the activity plans
- 5 new activity blocks to support some of the recommendations from year 2
- 11 new activity plans
- 9 revised activity plans (produced in year 1 and 2)

In terms of methods and activities in order to support the design of activity plans, ETL undertook the following actions:

- In collaboration with CU discussed with the partners the focus of the design on aspects of the learning process the year 2 evaluation recommendations
- Produced complementary activity blocks as a means to support with concrete examples the requirements for the 3rd year activity plans
- Organized and monitored the activity design process so as to comply with the 2nd year recommendations
- Enhanced the structured reflection form of year two and created the post activity report to support reflection and design revisions based on the implementation of the activity plans.

These activities, methodologies and design instruments developed during the third year supported the partners to design and revise their activity plans, so as to address the year 2 recommendations and integrate in the teaching and learning practice the key ideas of the ER4STEM framework.

Overall, the activity plans developed in year 3 show significant development with respect to the main pillars of ER4STEM as expressed in the 2nd and 3rd year evaluation recommendations. Specifically our analysis showed that:

- As in year 1 and 2, activity plans take place in collaborative settings and there are efforts in the design to support the collaborative process. As the analysis of the post activity reports showed, collaboration around robots was an aspect that drew the attention of tutors and brought to the surface interesting collaboration incidents and pedagogical strategies like supporting the sharing of information through peer mentoring, demonstration and analysis of best solutions.
- Integration of multiple disciplines in year 3 involves not only arts but also a new entry that of societal issues and life skills
- Evidence of learning showed that teachers, when they evaluate their students in robotics activities, emphasized more on aspects of STEM but there were also cases where they focused on soft skills and 21st century skills
- Post activity reports offered information that facilitated reflection on the activity design and brought to the surface aspects related to a) the need for differentiated activities b) a need for more emphasis for creative and exploratory tasks c) the importance of teacher attitudes towards workshops that are organized by practitioners and organizations outside school d) the need for conducting a pre-workshop discussion with teachers and parents supported by an explanation of the pedagogical approach and evidence from student constructions and impressions of the workshops.
- Reflection, creativity, and 21st century skills were included in the majority of the activity plans

In the next section, we include the new and the revised activity plans implemented during the 3rd year of the project. As mentioned earlier UoA in collaboration with ESI CEE plan to develop an e-book that will compile all the activity plans developed throughout the project and will offer alternative pathways to these activity plans using the curriculum developed in WP2.

7 FINAL RELEASE OF ACTIVITY PLANS

In this section, we present the actual activity plans designed according to the activity template presented in section 2. The post activity report which was an important addition to the template was presented and discussed in the project meeting in Athens (Sept 2017).

7.1 NEW ACTIVITY PLANS

Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills (V1)

AUTHOR:

ESI CEE Team: Christina Todorova, Ivaylo Gueorguiev, Pavel Varbanov, Dr. George Sharkov

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

The goal of this workshop is to introduce and exercise a multidisciplinary approach towards building general awareness on a variety of aspects of everyday life. Such aspects might be ecological thinking, applications of robotics, mathematical argumentation and coordinate system knowledge.

Participants play a set of games with the robotics arm. Every game introduces a problem, be it a mathematical problem, requiring the students to program the robot in order to place an item on a specific place of a coordinate system or be it a real-life problem engaging students in a game of sorting and recycling reusable materials. Through robot-enabled games, children cooperatively program robots to solve everyday life problems and improve on digital fluency skills and proportional thinking.

In addition, and of equal importance to raising awareness on real-life topics, this workshop is specifically designed to support and encourage the development of the following skills:

1. Problem solving skills are stimulated by encouraging students to solve different kind of problems in conventional ways, but also to seek innovative ways to find solutions. Also, we encourage students to think of robotics as a mechanism of solving real-life problems or gain knowledge through robotics on those subjects.
2. Communication is important for the successful outcome of the games. This includes the ability to articulate thoughts and ideas effectively in a group. Groups consist of student of diverse points of view, knowledge and abilities, which requires a certain ability to communicate complex ideas clearly, effectively and patiently. Including a variety of cooperative activities, this workshop aims to foster the effective communication skills, tolerance and collaboration.

3. Flexibility and adaptability are skills incorporated on many levels. Students have to be flexible in order to incorporate feedback from other team members and tutors effectively, and furthermore to understand, negotiate and balance diverse views and beliefs to reach workable solutions. Students will shift between roles and will be orchestrated to enter in counter-intuitive roles and role-play in order to gain a sense of resilience and assist the formation of a flexible character.

4. Through coming up with innovative, unique or imaginative solutions to problems, children will exercise their creativity and feel empowered to apply their creativity in their everyday life as a means to solve problems.

5. Creating environment for the cultivation on digital fluency and awareness through improving children’s technological knowledge will be supported through the inclusion of robotics and programming in a multidisciplinary activity plan.

Robotics is intriguing and fun, which is why we believe it makes a wonderful tool, in addition to the general school curriculum, for learning career and life skills.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES

This multidisciplinary workshop is designed to support the formation of key life skills and awareness on real-life issues and it serves in support of general education school curriculum.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	3	0	0	0	4

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	<p>Mathematics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn more about coordinate systems in the 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional space; Showcase the difference between whole numbers and fractions without going into theory;
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportions between time, distance and movement; <p>Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercise very basic Scratch programming skills; • Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; • Students understand that robots are programmable; • Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot; • Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative real-life problem solving; • Develop creative thinking skills to find different applications of robotics and programming in other fields
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming the RobotArm kit by CBiS Education through the visual programming software Scratch with the help of a basic HTTP server customized by ESI CEE.
<i>Social and action related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop problem solving skills; • Exercise effective communication skills; • Encourage flexibility and adaptability; • Foster collaboration skills;
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. • Encourage curiosity; • Encourage tinkering and experimentation; • The games require the decision-making process within a team; • Identifying and solving problems; • Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. • Exercise logical thinking;

TIME

Duration: 1 day (4 hours in total) or 2 days (4 hours in total)

Schedule: 1 session of 4 hours or 2 sessions of 2 hours

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Desktop version of Scratch visual programming software.</p> <p>A digital artifact of learning will be Scratch project files from teams. Students work only with</p>
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	the desktop version of Scratch in order to avoid connectivity issues.
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	The RobotArm kit by CBIS Education through the visual programming software Scratch. Children program a pre-constructed robot with USB cable and do not build one themselves.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Handouts with the anatomy of the robotic arm and the names of its respective degrees of freedom, namely base, shoulder, elbow, wrist, gripper. Handouts with the first two missions, namely the games with the two and three-dimensional coordinate systems. Additional materials necessary: markers, color pens, pencils, squared A1 paper, plain A4 paper, coffee capsules (or other blocks that can be built one over the other, necessary for the visualization of the third dimension of the coordinate system), felt balls of a diameter of 2 cm min. and 3.5 max., plastic bottle caps, optionally other objects that might look fun to play with or could be used to illustrate the concept of recycling – i.e. paper balls, AAA batteries, small plastic balls or cubes, others.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Activity plan, workshop checklists, copy of student handouts, source code, evaluation protocol, spare D-size batteries, USB cable extenders.

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 9-12 years old (fourth or fifth grade students)
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge is necessary. Knowledge on the basics of Scratch is useful, but not obligatory. The workshop applies mathematical concepts such as coordinate systems. At least third grade mathematics is useful but not obligatory, games and pedagogical approach could be adapted to fit various knowledge contexts and desired learning outcomes.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Bulgarian and Bulgaria-based minorities
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public schools;
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Children with physical disabilities or mental disorders might need additional help from specialized personnel according to their special education needs and obstructions, if any.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In a school, a club, or a spacious hall, with one computer and empty table per team, enough chairs, projector or smart TV screen, whiteboard and enough power plugs.

Useful but not required at all is internet access.

Physical characteristics: Indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: up to 28

Tutors: e.g. 1-2; **Assistants:** 1 (school teacher)

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups
<i>Setting:</i>	3-4 students in a group, indoors, in a spacious hall. Every group is seated around one table, with a computer and enough chairs. Every group works with one robot.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, engage in dialogues, negotiations, debates, suggestions; Program, give feedback, count; Test out concepts and ideas; Learning by experiencing;
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative;
<i>Roles in the group</i>	No specific roles defined; Teamwork; Rotation;
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate, encourage, suggest activities of different levels of complexity, based on a group's speed, previous experience and learning tempo.

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in effective communication within the team, with other teams and tutors in order to successfully complete their quests. A problem solving attitude is expected in order to experiment with new ideas to solve problems and observe results in order to improve or change strategy. Students are expected to be flexible and rotate or adapt to different roles in terms of responsibility within a team, and to be tolerant and patient with their classmates and the tutors.

Students are supposed to verbally and visually present their solutions to tutors and other teams, which requires them to communicate their expertise making the learner an expert. Students are supposed to collaborate with other teams and team members to successfully the last games.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	A designed conflict within this activity are the collaborative games at the end of each workshop, designed to contradict a probable attitude of competitiveness and self-centeredness. By promoting a game where a collaborative attitude makes the paramount importance to an outcome of a game, children are encouraged to support their peers,
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	share experience and expertise, rely on and trust their peers and their competence and to find ways to communicate through challenges and differences for the purpose of a common goal.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection and abstract conceptualization - talking with others and applying knowledge to solve a problem, reflecting on digital or analogue (robot) feedback and iterating previous approaches to problem-solving. • Active Experimentation - doing something new or doing the same thing in a more sophisticated way based on what is already learnt.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Alternative knowledge will be encouraged as the activity requires logical thinking, interpretation and creativity, negotiation, sustainability mindset, collaborative approach to problem-solving.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

The workshop is divided into 2 sessions of 2 hours each or is carried out in 1 four-hour session.

The ultimate goal of the games is to introduce students to work with robots and programming on a very basic level, but more importantly, to imply to students the importance of sustainability. Students gain a sense of the multi-disciplinary nature of mathematics, robotics and programming and the vast plethora of real-life applications of technology to solve everyday problems that we all face.

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND PRE-WORKSHOP EVALUATION

Duration: 60 minutes + 15 minutes break

Orchestration: Individual and group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: The tutors introduce themselves, explain what they do and why they came to the school. They also explain what is the purpose of this activity and what are the games that students will engage with through the robot. Next, they ask the students if they have had any robotics and/or programming experience, what is their attitude on mathematics and robotics in order to break the ice and put children in the mood for sharing and thinking about robotics. Children are also asked how robots could be applied to solve real-life problems, whether they think of robotics and mathematics as sciences that are abstract and distant from other domains, in order to **explore their attitudes on the applicability of robotics**. The purpose is to become familiar with the audience and vice versa and to explore their existing attitudes.

The researchers introduce themselves as **robot enthusiasts and math-lovers** and explain that in this workshop they will play and work together with the student teams in order to solve several mathematical games using the robotic arm and play a recycling game with the robots. Tutors introduce themselves as researchers and explain to students why their feedback is important to them and why their feedback is what shapes the future of robotics in education and why we believe robotics has a place in the education process.

Following this, children fill out the **Pre-Workshop Questionnaire** and the **Draw a Male or a Female Scientist at Work** evaluation activities. Children are briefly familiarized with the evaluation activities and how to go about them, how to fill them in, how their personal information will be anonymized and who will read what they wrote.

After the evaluation, the tutors introduce the students to the robotic arm, saying a few words about how it works, its parts and its degrees of freedom, as well as how we will program it. Students are handed out the Anatomy of the Arm handouts and are encouraged to explore the Scratch blocks that control every part of the arm to test out if everything works properly.

Meanwhile the tutors go around the groups to ensure all arms work properly and work closely with the groups with limited to no experience with Scratch programming, if such, answer the students' questions and troubleshoot technical issues. While talking to every groups, tutors emphasize on the following:

1. In order to complete the games, they will need to collaborate with their teammates and with students from other groups possibly.
2. Switching roles is of utmost experience to the success of the group and that everyone has to gain experience.
3. We are here to have fun, work together and learn new things – it is okay to not know something and it is okay to ask other students for their expertise and advice. We all work together.

In case of an argument or a noticeable group dysfunction, children are encouraged by tutors to find a way to work past possible differences and disagreement within a team, by supporting them on occasions with advice to:

- a) ask questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do);
- b) ask questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?);

- c) be open to trying new ideas;
- d) respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate;
- e) the group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion);
- f) trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work;
- g) try to engage all group members in the task.

Workshop objectives supported: Students gain basic understanding of the robotic arm and how it functions; They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on how a command might affect this particular robot's behavior; They know that commands could be programmed to last for a certain duration, i.e. 1 second; Students are aware that different robots are made to serve different purposes; Foster communication and collaboration skills; Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas; Decision-making within a team;

Expected student constructions: First pieces of code, robot movement.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration; Negotiation; Communication;

Teaching method: Evaluation activities – Instruction; Introduction activities – Discussion, experimentation, demonstration by example;

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING AND LOOPS

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: Students are explained the basics of coordinate systems so that they are able to determine the position of the points or other geometric elements on a Euclidian plane. After students know how to determine coordinates and know how to read them, they are given a handout where a set of coordinates are written. Their task is to move a felt ball from one coordinate to another. At the very beginning of the game, students are encouraged to take notes of their action, so as to be able to perform the second set of tasks of this game – to program the robot to pick up the ball from one coordinate and place it on another on a press of a given button.

Of course, as this arm is not equipped with any sensors that could support this task, students have to remember the initial position of the arm, so that the program would perform the programmed sequence of actions, so that a similar outcome is achieved. The coordinates are taken to be real numbers.

The focus of this game is placed not so much on precision, but on learning how the arm functions, learning how to determine coordinate and think proportionally. Moreover it is important that students cooperate and share knowledge. Students are expected to rotate and take turns taking notes, programming, reading coordinates, giving feedback and suggest movement.

Workshop objectives supported: Students program the RobotArm kit by CBiS Education through the visual programming software Scratch. Students learn about coordinate systems in the 2- dimensional space; Students are showcased the difference between whole numbers and fractions without going into theory; Students understand that robots are programmable; Exercise very basic Scratch programming skills; Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot; Develop creative thinking skills to find different applications of robotics and programming in other fields.

This game develops problem-solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

This game requires the decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Pieces of code, robot movement

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: MATHEMATICAL GAMES IN THREE DIMENSIONS

Duration: 30 minutes + 15 minutes break

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: The aim of this third game is to teach students, without going into theory, that every point in three-dimensional Euclidean space is determined by three coordinates. For the representation of the third dimension, we are using coffee capsules, due to their shape and indent at the bottom, which allows for multiple capsules to be built one on the other and for a ball to be placed on top without falling off. After students know how to determine coordinates in a three-dimensional coordinate system and know how to read them, they are given a handout where a set of coordinates are written. Their task is to move a felt ball from one coordinate to another, by building beforehand a “tower” of a given number of capsules (number of capsules = z) or moving a “tower” of capsules from one coordinate to another, adding capsules if needed. Students can construct the “tower” manually or using the robot arm.

The focus of this game is placed not so much on precision, but on learning how the arm functions, learning how to determine coordinate and think proportionally. Moreover, it is important that students cooperate and share knowledge. Students are expected to rotate and take turns taking notes, programming, reading coordinates, giving feedback and suggest movement. The coordinates are taken to be real numbers.

Workshop objectives supported: Students program the RobotArm kit by CBIS Education through the visual programming software Scratch. Students learn about coordinate systems in the 3- dimensional space; Students are showcased the difference between whole numbers and fractions without going into theory; Students understand that robots are programmable; Exercise very basic Scratch programming skills; Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot; Develop creative thinking skills to find different applications of robotics and programming in other fields.

This game develops problem solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

This game requires the decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Pieces of code, robot movement.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: THE WASTE SEPARATION CHALLENGE

Duration: 60 minutes + 15 minutes break

Orchestration: Group work, 2-4 groups work together. Groups consist of 3-4, if necessary 5 members.

Description: Students build on the knowledge, gained during the previous games to create a simulation of a waste separation station. Games are played by 3-4 students, ideally from different teams, so that every student relies on the support of 3-4 peers and could possibly switch with them at any point.

The setting of the game consists of 2-4 tables merged together with a sufficient amount of chairs around them so that 2-4 teams could work on them. Every team has their own computer and robotic arm (in case of PCs that can't be easily moved, USB extension cables will be needed). Arms are placed

on the same game board. The game board could be one of the sheets they previously worked on but should now be divided into three segments, similarly to as shown on the diagram below.

This way Arm 3 will be responsible for collecting textile (in our case felt balls), Arm 2 will collect bio waste (in our case it is represented by the coffee capsules) and Arm 1 will collect plastic (bottle caps). Elements are collected from all over the field and placed in respectively marked rectangle.

All elements are scattered in the middle of the field in a way that will prevent every arm being able to collect all objects of the material it is responsible for collecting, without relying on somebody else helping them out by pushing or dropping an element they need within their range.

The teams have 7 minutes for actual waste collection and 3 minutes to discuss or come up with a strategy before the game and to put the arm in a starting position of their choice. After the game, a collaborative reflection lead by the tutors takes place.

Score is formed by how many items are overall collected by all teams.

In case more time is left for this game, tutors might introduce a designed conflict – either by firstly playing this game competitively, or by not stating in advance that teams should work together and help each other. This way when students and tutors collaboratively reflect on the outcomes of the game after the game itself, tutors could lead them to reach the conclusion that a collaborative approach to the game is what ultimately would lead to success. In such case, the score might initially be measured in another way, depending on the context, for instance – winning team has more elements collected.

Students are left to organize their programming however they feel most comfortable and appropriate.

Workshop objectives supported: Students built on what they already know about coordinate systems and proportional argumentation of programming decisions. Game develops collaborative and team spirit, allowing for students to practice compassion and feel safe obtaining feedback by their peers and by the behavior of the robot.

This game develops problem solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas; They share and gain expertise and are encouraged by their teammates and peers from other groups.

This game requires the decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Expected student constructions: Organized robot movement

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation. Teachers refrain from instructions at this point, leaving students at a position where they have to experiment with different ideas and observe results to achieve the desired result.

PHASE 4: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION, FINAL GAMES AND CONCLUSIONS

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: In addition to the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience. Children are asked about their recommendations and their favorite games from both sessions.

Tutors give instructions on how to complete the evaluation papers and thanks children for participating in the workshop.

Students have time for their final experiments. They are left with the opportunity to ask questions and play a final game if time allows it.

Workshop objectives supported: Ultimately, students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students are aware that different sensors serve different purpose; They have already worked on the subjects of mathematics and informatics and have covered a lot of subject related material.

The final games are informal and serve as a conclusion to the workshop. They support the objectives related to fostering curiosity, experimentation and collaboration.

Expected student constructions: n/a

Teaching method: Evaluation activities – Instruction;

Other activities, if any – Discussion, Experimentation;

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Regarding direct workshop objectives

Objective	Activities to achieve the objective	Assessment (evaluation) procedures
Subject related – technology, engineering, science	<p>Mathematics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn more about coordinate systems in the 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional space; Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory; Showcase the difference between whole numbers and decimal 	<p>Opinions about STEM as well as preconceptions about scientists, scientists and robotics are measured by the pre and post workshop questionnaires as well as visualized through the draw a scientist exercise.</p> <p>. Group interviews assess and</p>

	<p>numbers without going into theory;</p> <p>Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercise very basic Scratch programming skills; • Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; • Students understand that robots are programmable; • Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot; • Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative real-life problem solving; • Develop creative thinking skills to find different applications of robotics and programming in other fields 	<p>record concepts regarding collaboration and digital fluency. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>
<i>Technology use related</i>	<p>Programming the RobotArm kit by CBiS Education through the visual programming software Scratch with the help of a basic HTTP server customized by ESI CEE.</p>	<p>Photos and videos of successfully performed tasks. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop problem solving skills; • Exercise effective communication skills; • Encourage flexibility and adaptability; • Foster collaboration skills; 	<p>Group discussions/interviews and focus group interviews are used as a tool to record students' progress, opinions and changing attitudes, along the with questionnaires. Attitudes towards team work are recorded and measured with the questionnaires as well. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. • Encourage curiosity; • Encourage tinkering and experimentation; • The games require the decision-making process within a team; • Identifying and solving problems; • Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. • Exercise logical thinking; 	<p>Group discussions and interviews, alongside with photos and videos are used to record children's attitude and productions. All forms of evaluation, applied within the ER4STEM projects are further relevant for measuring this objective. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>

Regarding research questions and tool for assessment

Research Question	Assessment Method or Tool
Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Draw a scientist (if applicable) ● Pre-Questionnaire ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections ● Tutor Observations & Reflections
Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections
Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand learners' experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-Questionnaire ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections
Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections ● Tutor Observations & Reflections

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 1**Workshop Code:** PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm**Partner Organization:** ESI CEE**Country:** Bulgaria**Post activity report completed by:** Christina Todorova**Number of Sessions:** 2**Workshop start date (first session):** 23.04.2018**Workshop end date (second session):** 30.04.2018**UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS**

During the game we played at the end of the workshop, students became really intense and competitive and the overall atmosphere was really tense and furthermore, the game was hard to facilitate and the tutors improvised and did not coordinate the well the rules of the game.

Furthermore, we had initially the idea to make two games – one competitive and one cooperative version of the game. However, time barely sufficed for the first set of games also and children managed to have time to play only the competitive version.

It was not this bad, though, as children reported having a lot of fun during this part of the session, and they did enjoy this game most out of the entire activity.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

On the spot, there was not much we did to help out the situation, as both tutors facilitated the workshop and not the environment itself. Moreover, the experience was so hectic that I feel before we realized the situation on the spot, half of it went by and we had only a few minutes left to attempt to facilitate the environment.

I think the game would be better if students had time to play the cooperative version of the game, instead of only competing against one another – but I think regardless of the overly competitive spirit in the classroom, that this was the part that excited the students the most and showed the real educational potential of the used technology. It was furthermore the first official workshop, carried under this activity plan.

Tutors should also have a better discussion on the desired learning outcomes of the game and the rules of the game itself.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students applied knowledge on two dimensional coordinate systems, used and created coordinates.
- Students applied knowledge on three-dimensional coordinate systems, used and created coordinates.
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students applied proportional reasoning in order to program the robot to perform and predict programmable movements]

Students performed iterations and similarity to derive the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to play games and experiment in the end.

- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Play and set the priority on a cooperative version of this game, maybe play only short version of the competitive game, as an experiment, just for making a point about cooperation.
- Improve the workshop handouts, making them clearer and easily understandable.
- Maybe integrate this activity plan as part of another activity plan, with different technology, so that the robotic arm would only complement the other activity. I feel it tends to get quite boring after a few hours and students lose interest in it.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 2

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 14.05.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 28.05.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

I cannot think of anything specific, apart from that it was very warm in the room, and opening the windows did not help, as the air was not circulating at all.

Otherwise, apart from turning the arm on, explaining the goal of today's game and resolving technical difficulties, students did not need any support from the tutors. Those students are recurring participants of ours, they have participated in activities organized by us outside of the project also and are already very familiar with the Scratch interface, basic programming concepts and motor control. Not much support, if any at all was needed, they worked by themselves, we just gave them challenges and explained the rules of the missions.

The game at the end was very successful. We played only a cooperative version of the game and it was very well received from the students. Also, compared to the other class, where we did this workshop, where we had time only to play a competitive version of the game, it felt very much better, a lot less tense and I think the students appreciated the experience more.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

The collaborative game was a huge success and could be further improved on in order to teach other real life principles.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students applied knowledge on two dimensional coordinate systems, used and created coordinates.
- Students applied knowledge on three-dimensional coordinate systems, used and created coordinates.
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;

- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students applied proportional reasoning in order to program the robot to perform and predict programmable movements]

Students performed iterations and similarity to derive the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
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- Similarity
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Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Maybe integrate this activity plan as part of another activity plan, with different technology, so that the robotic arm would only complement the other activity. I feel it tends to get quite boring after a few hours and students loose interest in it.
- Think of ways to even further improve on the collaborative game, refine its rules and define better the desired learning outcomes.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 3

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-Kuystendil

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 1

Workshop date (first session): 18.05.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

Initially, we had not received the consent forms in advance, we had to wait for every child to arrive and give their consent form to us, and we had to process everything on the spot, very little time prior to the actual workshop and figure out which children we could film. Furthermore, we had distributed the pre-questionnaires in advance in order to have more time for the actual workshop, so we also collected feedback, at the same time as we were collecting the consent and we had to check very thoroughly if everyone actually was permitted to provide us feedback.

In the same time, a group of reporters entered the hall and started asking for interviews. The other tutor, Ivaylo, gave one or two interviews, but meanwhile reporters were not allowing a few students to enter the hall, so that they would not disrupt the recording, while they were actually disrupting the onset of the workshop. They were even filming the students and when I told them that they shouldn't be filming the children without their parent's explicit consent, they were still asking children questions.

Following that it turned out that some of the students were not familiar with Scratch programming, the majority of the students even. We had to go around the groups initially to show them how to manipulate the robot and do basic code structures in Scratch. After that, we mainly explained the tasks and went around the groups to monitor their work and give additional directions and tasks to the groups, which were faster.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

The arm control was not too sophisticated for them to handle even in the case of no prior knowledge in programming or robotics. Furthermore, the tutors were making sure to go around all groups and provide the support necessary not to feel overwhelmed by the activity. Also, students were supported by their class teachers who came brought them to the activity and who also went around to help them out if needed and monitor their work.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students applied knowledge on two dimensional coordinate systems, used and created coordinates.
- Students applied knowledge on three-dimensional coordinate systems, used and created coordinates.
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students applied proportional reasoning in order to program the robot to perform and predict programmable movements]

Students performed iterations and similarity to derive the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Improve the workshop handouts, making them clearer and easily understandable.
- Maybe integrate this activity plan as part of another activity plan, with different technology, so that the robotic arm would only complement the other activity. I feel it tends to get quite boring after a few hours and students lose interest in it.

Basic introduction into robotics and VPL

AUTHORS:

Tatiana Velez Trucco, Nemanja Popovic

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

A first introduction to understand concept of robotics and how to work with them. Make first contact with the Thymio and teach them how to use the simple programming language VPL. In the last workshop they must prove their knowledge, to encourage them to experiment with the Thymio.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 10 0 6 0 0

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify).....

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 10 0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	What is a robot? How does it work? Which different kind of robots exist? What are they used for?
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with VPL; LEGO building stones, use of camera
<i>Social and action related</i>	Divide participants into six groups, each of them consists of two people, except for one group of three people to develop their communication and teamwork.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Make them interact with the sensors of the

	robot and develop an idea about what the robot can and cannot perceive.
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TIME

Duration: 4 weeks

Schedule: 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language VPL
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Construction of a maze with LEGO stones
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheets,
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Verbal explanation, visual presentation and ready-to-compile programs

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & Girls, 6-11 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	-----
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Serbia, Philippines, Austria, Turkey, China, Korea, Mexico
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: at university at the technology laboratory; after school activity at Computer Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 11

Tutors: 2

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No mixed groups, group of two and three people
<i>Setting:</i>	e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, justify ideas
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	Emergent roles, camera kid
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

The kids should learn to use VPL, understand how to use a robot the right way, interact with their group, solve problems, present their work to their group mates in the form of a letter, interrogate other about their work and use LEGO and the Thymio creatively in the last workshop.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Change their perspective on what a robot really is (misconception made by Hollywood)
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	The focus lies on using a very simple coding method to learn step by step how programming works.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	No alternative knowledge needed

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: Introduce the concept robot

- Prequestionnaires - 10 Min.
- Number distribution - 5 Min.
- Get-to-know game - 25 Min.
- Presentation: Power Point -30 Min.
- Draw a Scientist and a Robot -10 Min.
- Showing off Thymio and Wonder -10 Min.

Template: In the first workshop we will play a game called “Minesfeld” to make the kids feel comfortable in the new environment and to let them understand how a robots works. Based on that,

we will explain them, with what kind of robots we are going to work on the next 9 sessions. In this part of the Workshop kids are introduced to experiment with the parts, sensors and motor of the Thymnio, to get in contact with one of the Robots we will be working with.

PHASE 2: FIRST CONTACT WITH VPL

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: Introduction of Thymio and VPL

Explanation of sensors and functionalities, let them understand the change in local variables

Evidence of learning: Write a letter to your neighbor -30 min.

Exercises: - 90 min

- **Exercise 1:** Messe mit Thymion.
- **Exercise 2:** Drück mich.
- **Exercise 3:** Fahre auf Befehl.
- **Exercise 4:** Fall nicht vom Tisch.
- **Exercise 5:** Evidence of learning.

Template:

We would introduce in the first 30 min the basic language (**VLP**) of the program. After that the kids shall perform the first simple exercises. They will learn how to make use of the buttons, sensors and colors the Thymio has to offer. After a successful first day of programming, they are asked to write a letter to their neighbor about what they had learned on this workshop.

Note:

We just made it to the second exercise, due to the difference in ages. The students don't have the same learning level as we had to adjust to the youngest.

PHASE 3: USING ADVANCED VPL

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: Introduce the advanced version of VPL.

- **Exercise 1:** Unfallvermeidung.
- **Exercise 2:** Zielgerade
- **Exercise 3:** Ausflug im Korridor.
- **Exercise 4:** Anhängliches Haustier.

Evidence of learning: Kind of an interview, where each participant writes down three questions and let a person of their choice answer them. The answers will be written down as well.

Template: We will teach the Kids how to use the advanced Version of VPL. At the beginning we will explain how the Thymio works and then we will be giving them four exercises so they can learn how to use it.

Note:

We wanted to start with advanced version of VPL, but instead we did the exercises of the last week, because we couldn't do them then. Due to this delay we will do the advanced VPL in the second session.

PHASE 4: CREATIVITY AND GROUPWORKS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: See if they remembered what they learned in the previous workshops and encourage creative usage of the Thymio. Also we want them to understand the concept behind states.

- **Exercise 1:** Leuchtende Farbe.
- **Exercise 2:** LEGO → Evidence of learning

Template: This is the last workshop from section 1. Our idea is to give the kids an open exercise, where they can use all the functionalities VPL has to offer. We also want to stimulate the creativity and teamwork.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

We found the introductory presentation about robot to be unnecessary for younger kids, because they don't pay attention while explaining. They were more interested in playing with the robots and the computers.

Also it was very difficult to work with this range of ages, because the younger kids were easily bored when we talk about something. For Example: 13408 was bored in the last 30 minutes and was running around and screaming that he was bored.

13400, 13401, 13404, 1305 were very interested in our workshop, asking questions and telling about their experience. They were very interactive and tried their best to solve the exercises and answer our questions.

13403 complained why we had to do the "Minenfeld" exercise, but when it was his turn to do it he failed completely.

They are unknowledagable about computers so they press buttons randomly and freeze the program and the thymio.

The Pushbutton program didn't work sometimes.

In the 3rd workshop they did all the exercises unexpectedly fast. Which means that they are learning what we teach them. In this week only 5 kids were present, so we couldn't make groups of 2. On the other hand it was easier to work with them because we had time to explain it to them separately.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

When we realized that they were not paying attention while we were presenting the history of robots we let them search for robot videos on youtube to get them to do something.

During the "Minesfeld" game 13408 laughed when 13403 failed, but we told 13403 to continue being calm and not get irritated by his laughing.

One of the kids needed another patch for her finger, luckily we had some with us. Maybe we should consider having a mini med-kit.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

They had to draw a scientist and a robot. We wanted to see their perspective on what a robot and a scientist looks like, to see whether they think robots always look like people. They also thought a lot about the functionality of the robots(i.e. some of them drew cleaning robot)

We also planned an activity called "social robot" where we wanted them to create a concept for a robot in some aspects of life, but it didn't work out well because they didn't know much of the words.

Please indicate specifically what your students learned regarding STEM choosing from the concepts listed below

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

- No introductory presentation with boring theories
- Smaller difference in ages
- Raise age to 7, because the younger cannot read and are less concentrated

Basic introduction into robotics and VPL (V2)

AUTHORS:

Tatiana Velez Trucco, Nemanja Popovic

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

A first introduction to understand concept of robotics and how to work with them. Make first contact with the Thymio and teach them how to use the simple programming language VPL and the more advanced programming language Blockly. The first 4 workshop we will use VPL, then in the next 4 workshops Blockly and the 9th workshop will be a project where they think of a program on their own and present in to their parents. In the 10th workshop they will be the teachers themselves and teach programming to younger kids.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 10 0 6 0 0

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify).....

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 10 0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	What is a robot? How does it work? Which different kind of robots exist? What are they
------------------------	--

	used for? How are they programmed?
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with VPL, Blockly; LEGO building stones, use of camera
<i>Social and action related</i>	Divide participants into different size of groups, depending on the amount of kids present. Sometimes we mixed genders, to see how it worked out, sometimes we had them work alone to test their capabilities;
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Make them interact with the sensors, the LED's and the shock sensor of the robot and develop an idea about what the robot can and cannot perceive.

TIME

Duration: 10 weeks

Schedule: 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language VPL, Blockly
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Construction of a maze with LEGO stones
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheets, Evidence of learning
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Verbal explanation, visual presentation and ready-to-compile programs, Videos

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & Girls, 6-11 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	-----
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Serbia, Philippines, Austria, Turkey, Korea
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	-----
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: at university at the technology laboratory; after school activity at Computer Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: See Evaluation_v5 excel_sheet

Tutors: 2**GROUPING:**

Grouping criteria	Mixed groups and single groups; see Objectives social and action related
Setting:	Students in a normal classroom

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, justify ideas, presentation, team work
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	Emergent roles, camera kid, leader, maker
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, monitor, facilitate, videos, explain, example programs

LEARNING PROCEDURES**EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY**

The kids should learn to use VPL and Blockly, understand how to use a robot the right way, interact with their group, solve problems, present their work to their group mates in the form of a letter, interview others about their work and use LEGO and the Thymio creatively in the 5th and 9th workshop.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Change their perspective on what a robot really is (misconception made by Hollywood). Teach other kids to see what kind of problems they have while they are teaching programming. Present a project in front of the class and their parents. Making them argue their projects and codes.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	The focus lies on using a very simple coding method to learn step by step how programming works and how to work in a team and solo.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	No alternative knowledge needed

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION**Duration:** 2 hours**Orchestration:** group work**Objective:** Introduce the concept robot

-Prequestionnaires

- 10 Min.

-Number distribution	- 5 Min.
- “Minenfeld”-Game	- 25 Min.
-Presentation: Power Point	-30 Min.
- social robot exercises	-10 Min.
-Draw a scientist and draw a robot	-10 Min.

Template: In the first workshop we will play a game called “Minenfeld” to make the kids feel comfortable in the new environment and to let them understand how a robot works. Based on that, we will explain them, with what kind of robots we are going to work on the next 9 sessions. In this part of the Workshop kids are introduced to experiment with the parts, sensors and motor of the Thymio, to get in contact with one of the Robots we will be working with.

PHASE 2: FIRST CONTACT WITH VPL

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: Introduction of Thymio and VPL

Explanation of sensors and functionalities, let them understand the change in local variables

Evidence of learning: Write a letter to your neighbor -30 min.

Exercises: - 90 min

- **Exercise 1:** Messe mit Thymio.
- **Exercise 2:** Drück mich.
- **Exercise 3:** Evidence of learning-write a letter

Template:

We will introduce in the first 30 min the basic language (**VLP**) of the program. After that the kids shall perform the first simple exercises. They will learn how to make use of the buttons, sensors and colors the Thymio has to offer. After a successful first day of programming, they are asked to write a letter to their neighbor about what they had learned on this workshop.

PHASE 3: CONTINUING VPL

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: Introduce the advanced version of VPL.

- **Exercise 1:** Fahre auf Befehl
- **Exercise 2:** Fall nicht vom Tisch
- **Exercise 3:** Kombination mit Farbe und Licht
- **Exercise 4:** Evidence of learning - interview

Evidence of learning: An interview, where each participant writes down three questions and let a person of their choice answer them. The answers will be written down as well.

Template: We continued to do the exercises we couldn't complete in the last section.

PHASE 4: ROBOT FIGHT

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: We encouraged them to be creative with the lego stones we provided, so they started building fighting robots out of lego stones and started battling each other. Also, we brought the cranes with us to test their understanding of physical boundaries.

- **Exercise 1:** Thymio Kran
- **Exercise 2:** Erforschung des Aufbaus
- **Exercise 3:** Kontrolliere den Abstand
- **Exercise 2:** LEGO → Battle of robots

Template: This is the last workshop from section 1. Our idea is to give the kids an open exercise, where they can use all the functionalities VPL has to offer. We also want to stimulate the creativity and teamwork.

PHASE 5: ADVANCED VPL

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: The objective in this workshop is to make them understand the concept of states and their importance in programming with robots.

- **Exercise 1:** Unfallvermeidung
- **Exercise 2:** Zielgerade
- **Exercise 3:** Ausflug im Korridor
- **Exercise 4:** Balanciere dich gut aus!
- **Exercise 5:** Anhängliches Haustier
- **Evidence of learning:** Quiz

Template: We will try to do as much of the exercises as we can, because we would like to start with Blockly in the next workshop.

PHASE 6: MORE VPL PROBLEMS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Objective: Before starting with Blockly we did a last workshop with advanced VPL to make them understand the concept of states even better. Then we will start with Blockly.

- **Exercise 1:** Zustand

- **Exercise 2:** Party-Roboter
- **Exercise 3:** Mein erstes Blockly-Programm
- **Evidence of learning:** VPL Quiz

Template: During the party robot exercise they learned to use states and understand how they can use a single button for different tasks. Then we showed them a Blockly video we made ourselves to make them accustomed to the new programming language. They then tried to recreate the program in the video and then they played with the “Mein erstes Blockly-Programm”.

PHASE 7: MORE BLOCKLY

Objective: We would like them to get a better understanding of how to use blockly and especially try to reproduce old exercises with another programming language.

- **Exercise 1:** Fahre auf Befehl
- **Exercise 2:** Falle nicht vom Tisch!
- **Exercise 3:** Ausflug im Korridor
- **Evidence of learning:** Top 5 Tipps

Template: We showed them another video about Blockly, then we did two activities with them.

PHASE 8: EVEN MORE BLOCKLY

Objective: Gain a better understanding about their problems and how to help them with understanding Blockly. See whether their struggle with Blockly gets better with time or if it remains as hard to grasp as in the beginning.

- **Exercise 1:** Zweifache Labyrinthführung
- **Exercise 2:** Quadrat zeichnen
- **Evidence of Learning:** Sticking together cut out pieces of the blockly language to write a simple program.

Template: Since we noticed that the kids had problems using Blockly, we will do a kind of group discussion to see if our assumptions are right and how they feel about Blockly compared to VPL. Then we will let them play with printed Blockly pieces and make the put together a program out of these pieces. Then we will let them do some simple exercises so that they get used to stuff they already know and don't get confused even more by introducing new stuff.

PHASE 9

Objective: Let them utilize their gained knowledge to make a project on their own and be creative with Thymio. See if they can do anything sensible without our aid.

Template: We will tell them to prepare a presentation for their parents during which they showcase a program they wrote with either of the two programming languages they learned up until now. They may use anything we bring with us, like Legostones, different kind of pens, coloured paper, etc.

PHASE 10

Objective: The aim of this workshop was to let the kids use the knowledge they had earned in the past workshops and teach other, younger kids the basics of robot programming with VPL. This way we could test their progress and their ability to pass knowledge in an understandable way.

Template: We will be telling them what they have to do, but not how they should approach the teaching. Only if they have problems making the other kids understand we will be helping actively.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

We found the introductory presentation about robot to be unnecessary for younger kids, because they don't pay attention while explaining. They were more interested in playing with the robots and the computers.

Also it was very difficult to work with this range of ages, because the younger kids were easily bored when we talk about something. For Example: 13408 was bored in the last 30 minutes and was running around and screaming that he was bored.

13400, 13401,13404,1305 were very interested in our workshop, asking questions and telling about their experience. They were very interactive and tried their best to solve the exercises and answer our questions.

13403 complained why we had to do the "Minenfeld" exercise, but when it was his turn to do it he failed completely.

They are unknowledagable about computers, so they press buttons randomly and freeze the program and the Thymio.

The Pushbutton program didn't work sometimes.

In the 3rd workshop they did all the exercises unexpectedly fast. Which means that they are learning what we teach them. In this week only 5 kids were present, so we couldn't make groups of 2. On the other hand, it was easier to work with them because we had time to explain it to them separately.

In the 4th workshop we were fascinated with how creative they were in creating their fighting robot. The boys tried to build some super futuristic battle robot with wings and propeller, and the girls build a house like decoration for the robot. Except for one boy all the kids were very into the robot building and had very much fun.

In the 5th workshop we saw that 13403 and 13404 were working very good as a team, so we will consider letting them work together from now on. We noticed that 13408 understood how to do the exercises better than 13407 even though 13407 was in the workshop last week. 13405 was distracted the whole time and only drew picture and copied the programs of her sister, which is why her sister insisted that she wants to work with 13403. 13400 was a bit anxious when he heard that they would have to program with something new in this workshop.

In the 7th workshop 13403 could finish the evidence of learning exercise in time and when his parents appeared to take him home he started crying.

In the 8th workshop 13407 and 13408 were a little worked up and started running around in class and screaming. They didn't really care much about what we wanted them to do.

In the 9th workshop the VPL program crashed very often. The kids had to repeat their programming a lot of times, since they forgot to save their programs in time. Since they had to show their program to their parents in the last part of the workshop, time was scarce, and they became really stressed out near the end and more than cried for help.

The 10th workshop was really good, the only think unexpected was that 13401 and 13407 showed Blockly to the other kids. Because we only had one hour with the kids, we didn't do the pre- and post-questionnaire. Here only 4 kids provided a consent form.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

When we realized that they were not paying attention while we were presenting the history of robots we let them search for robot videos on youtube to get them to do something.

During the "Minenfeld" game 13408 laughed when 13403 failed, but we told 13403 to continue being calm and not get irritated by his laughing.

One of the kids needed another patch for her finger, luckily, we had some with us. Maybe we should consider having a mini med-kit.

Tatiana tried to consolidate 13403 when his parents came and even wrote an email asking about his wellbeing and whether he managed to calm down fast.

When 13407 and 13408 were worked up in the 8th workshop, we constantly told them to go back to their places and do the exercises. Sometimes we had to say it in a more harsh tone to make them stop and concentrate more.

When the program crashed we put them on another computer or gave them another Thymio and warned them to save a lot of times to prevent them of losing their programs.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

They had to draw a scientist and a robot. We wanted to see their perspective on what a robot and a scientist looks like, to see whether they think robots always look like people. They also thought a lot about the functionality of the robots (i.e. some of them drew cleaning robot)

We also planned an activity called "social robot" where we wanted them to create a concept for a robot in some aspects of life, but it didn't work out well because they didn't know much of the words we used on the provided sheet.

Workshop 2 we made them write a letter.

Workshop 3 was an interview.

Workshop 4 was an own project with Lego

Workshop 5 was a Quiz

Workshop 6 was another kind of quiz

Workshop 7 were their top 5 tips

Workshop 8 was a blockly puzzle

Workshop 9 was their own project with a language of their choice

Workshop 10 was teaching other kids

Please indicate specifically what your students learned regarding STEM choosing from the concepts listed below

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

- No introductory presentation with boring theory
- Smaller difference in ages
- Raise age to 7, because the younger cannot read and are less concentrated
- Show videos explaining VPI und Blockly

ER4STEM Workshops – Robot Elevator

AUTHORS:

Patrik Harner, Andreas Fenk and Julian Angel-Fernandez

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

As the result of the workshop, the children get a completed mechanical construction, where a Thymio lifts via deflection pulleys a mass or some other subjects. First, Participants will undergo some

exercises to learn how to control Thymio. After this basic introduction, the children will get the prepared construction, which they should use to reach the given task.

The lift has several limitations that participants should discover to limit the physical movement of the system, which will avoid damages to it. The first one is the maximum and minimum height that the elevator can reach. The second is the maximum speed that could be used to make the movement and still reach the desired point. It is important to remember that there is a delay on the stop command in high speeds. The completion of the activity involves the following steps: explore the given setup, and determine the maximum and minimum height they can go. Furthermore, there will be executed different concepts to control the present system.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
4	10	0	10	2	3

OBJECTIVES

Science related	Investigate why and how pulleys effect the elevating mechanism
Technology related	Use of Thymio robot, proper employment of its functions
Engineering related	Think about solutions on how to attach the robot to the system and think about where this kind of system is used
Arts related	Telling a story what the robots are doing, creating a design for the Thymio robots with Lego
Mathematics related	Basic physical and mathematic concepts of gear ratio and pulley mechanism (e.g. bicycle gear ratios) – to the old ones
Further: Social skills	School classes are split up into groups. Each group has its own area of responsibility (design, programming etc.). The children are told to collaborate and organize the necessary

	exchange of information on their own.
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TIME

Duration: 5 hours

Schedule: 2 workshop parts with a duration of 2.5 hours each

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Source code, videos, presentations
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Written descriptions and examples from tutors

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 6-18 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Mostly Austrian, cultural background diverse, capital city and surrounding
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public elementary school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Some students are deaf

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Workshops take place at the university. During regular school time.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 10-27

Tutors: 2 (+teacher and parents)

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	preference of subject (engineering and technology, arts and design, organization and leadership)
<i>Setting:</i>	Class is split up into 3-4 groups. Every group member should be able to collaborate. Tasks will be solved group wise

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Result oriented, solution oriented
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

In general the workshop consist of two parts:

In the first part, the children are taught the basic concepts needed to operate Thymio robots. They should be able to perform movements, use proximity sensors, follow a line (bottom sensors) use IR communication and use LED lightning.

In the second part, the participants will get a mechanism. The basic construction will be given to guide them into the right direction. They shall understand and try out two basic concepts. Minimizing force on a winder with pulleys and with gear ratios.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Participants have to come with a solution to connect the robot to the system, and the best solution is going to be selected. The tutors must provide the information about what
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on robot behavior and small exercises
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	No alternative knowledge used/needed

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

PHASE 1: BASIC KNOWLEDGE AND EXERCISES

In the first section the basic concepts of the thymio robot will be refreshed. It can be done like an interactive presentation. Selected exercises from the tutors can be chosen to show the children some simple programming examples, which should be used to bring the common commands in their mind.

General explanation: We have prepared some different videos, which explains some exercises of the first part of the workshop. They can be used to give the elementary school audience a first explanations for prograding thymio.

Exercise 1: Push buttons (app. 25 min)

In this exercise the children should learn how to use the robot’s push buttons. A program should be written to let Thymio react on specific push-button events.

Recommendations: If you want to use the motors of thymio it is good to know that there are two types of motors (motor-left.target and motor-right.target.) Each can be controlled by its own with a push button event. As a simple entrance it is useful to implement a push button event with the top or bottom lights of thymio.

Exercise 2: Horizontal sensors (app. 25 min)

This exercise should give the children a feeling for the use of the horizontal sensors. The robot should drive forwards if there was an obstacle behind it and backwards if there was an obstacle in front of it.

Recommendation: For the basic VPL programming language investigate the different types of the sensor attitudes. (if the box is blackened or white)

Exercise 3: See a line (app. 15 min)

This exercise focuses on the use of the ground sensors. The sensors should detect a black line on the ground and the robot should react to it.

Recommendation: Here it is important to understand the functionality of the ground sensors. (like mentioned before: in the VPL language the difference between a black and a white box for the proximity sensors)

Exercise 4 – What have you done today?

Tutors give a blank sheet with the instruction to write an e-mail about the activity that they have done today, telling him/her what they have done what they have like or not and what they have learned.

PHASE 2: THYMIO ELEVATOR

Duration: 150 min

In the following explanations, there will be one Thymio robot. The “Thymio” should regulate the elevation platform with different controlling settings. After a period of time the Thymio should be able to release the platform back to the ground.

Possible groups: Programmers, Construction workers (Engineers), Physicists, Managers

Exercise 1 – Set up (duration app. 10 + 20 of presentations)

The robot, a thread, the crane and Lego block are provided to the participants.

Without given any instruction about how to connect all the parts, participants are asked to come with a solution for this and explain possible limitations and problems that could have their solution:

- Young participants have to come with an example on real life where they have seen the system to justify their answer
- Old participants have to explain using physical concepts or mathematical ones. Also they have to explain where their solution could be used.

Participants have 10 minutes to come with a solution. Tutors remember them to consider the work done before.

Once the time ends, each group present their solution and explain pros and cons. Tutors explain that this will let them to see what the others have done and reflect about their own solution. They have 5 minutes to organize their ideas and each group has 2 minutes to present and one minute of suggestions from the tutors and other participants. At the end participants must select one design to work with based on consensus. If participants do not arrive to any consensus, tutors can suggest the predefine solution. Having one system will make things easier in the following exercises.

Exercise 2 – Exploration (duration: app. 20 min)

Objective: Make participants understand some considerations or precautions that they must consider when they are using the crane.

Now that they have come with a setup, they need to explore and find the two main limitations of the system: maximum and minimum height. To make them discover this two questions are asked:

1. Is it possible to move forward forever the robot? Why yes or not? If your answer was no, how would you solve this?
2. Is it possible to move backward forever the robot? Why yes or not? If your answer was no, how would you solve this?

Exercise 3 – Control the distance (duration: app. 40 min)

In the third task, the thymio should respond to the distance between a hand and his proximity sensors. Depending of the hand to the distance of the robot, it should move slower when approach and move faster when retracts. If no obstacle can be detected, the robot waits for further commands. The robot must be also stop when the limit is reach. If you push the center button the robot should stop respond to commands.

The following questions are asked to the participants to answer before they start solving the problem:

- Do your current design allows you to do this exercise? Why? If no, how would you modify it to make it work?
- What considerations you must keep in mind during the implementation?

Exercise 5 – Story (duration: app. 50 min)

Ask groups to collaborate with another group, this would create groups between 4 to 6 participants. Their task is to develop a story using two robots and one crane. They can work on robots appearance using paper and Lego blocks.

Exercise 6 – What have you done today? (duration: app. 10 min)

Tutors give a blank sheet with the instruction to write an e-mail or draw about the activity that they have done today, telling him/her what they have done what they have like or not and what they have learn.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Making a video in the second part of the workshop is kind of an assessment to see what the kids have learned and if they understood how to combine the skills of the robot.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_050318)**UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)**

The students had the same problems with the crane-elevator-exercise as the younger students. The crane model didn't seem to be properly executed. They still managed to solve the tasks.

It was not expected that they would be that good in all the exercises.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

We helped them out by repairing the cranes time to time.

We tried to challenge them and keep their interest with more complex exercises.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

It was interesting to see that the students were motivated to do the exercises most of the time, even though the exercises were sometimes too easy for them. After finishing the main exercises, they also started to try out different other things.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

We tried to encourage them to try out different features and solve other exercises.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_060418)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

In the first session some part of the activities (write a letter) had to be given as an in-school activity to the teacher, because we could not follow the time schedule because every thing took longer than planned.

There was a bit of `planned` time pressure during session 2 because of the school's availability, the workshop was limited to 2,5 hours (instead of usual 3 hrs). Therefore we were counting on having some stress with the exercises and possibly shortening/skipping some activities. However, the class was really motivated and interested in all the exercises, every one of them participated and listened carefully to the instructions. Because of that, in the end we could complete the activities in the shorter time too.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

In session 1 we tried to stick to the planned time schedule, but it was just not possible with the kids. So we decided to skip the letter writing during the session and give it to the teacher to let them write it in the school.

Because of the time pressure during session 2 sometimes there was not enough time to help all the groups who were having small issues like lost connection between Thymio and computer. We were busy all the time but tried to listen to every kid's needs.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

The class was very motivated and interested in all the exercises. Every one of them participated and listened carefully to the instructions. All of them managed the exercises and some of them even managed more difficult exercises.

During the presentation of the crane setups, a real group discussion emerged in a really good way - the class listened carefully to all the presentations. More kids gave good inputs and accepted and favored other solutions because they were better than their own.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

They only needed a bit of coordination of the group discussion so that it could flow very smoothly.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_100418)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

There were some students with solid programming /IT background, they mostly took the lead in their groups. The other teammates usually just watched by. However, there was a completely disinterested group (session 3, crane programming). They did not even make an attempt to solve the exercise, they did not even bother to act like as if they would have, were just hanging on their phones and chatting. When I asked them what they programmed, they used the "push the buttons" buttons to navigate Thymio in the crane setup. There were by far the most uninterested kids during the workshops.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

I tried to make them try some programming, so I addressed the students so seemed to be more opened to do something. It turned out that one of them was absent last session but were kind of interested and after some explanation of the VPL she managed to solve the exercise with some help (crane programming).

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

At the beginning of the third session we got some feedback from the teacher: She said, that the exercises were formulated too openly i.e. many students did not come to terms with the tasks because they were not concrete enough. She meant that first of all for the exercises of the first session (use of sensors in labyrinth etc.) As per the teacher, 50% of the students do not come to terms with the tasks, 25% are bored, 25% are not in the mood of doing it.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

It does not happen often that we receive such a concrete feedback concerning the activity plan so it was worth noting.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_110418)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

The class was really disinterested to do any programming or even to make an attempt to solve the tasks. Many of them were building stuff from Lego or hanging on their phones, or were even rather doing nothing than the exercises.

It seemed like that in case of teens they are either interested and engage with the exercises or they are not interested at all and don't do anything - there is nothing in between.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Those who made up their minds not to do anything and decided that they were simply not interested, there was no way to motivate them to try to solve the exercises. Since they did not want to do it, even though they tried they did not have much success.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

It was interesting to see, that a lot of students already started to program the Thymio during the crane setup (exercise 2.1, session 2). Some of them actually came up with a complete solution (i.e. crane setup incl programming) so they basically already solved the complete task.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

The students could mostly well explain their solutions, so they only needed a bit of coordination.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_140218)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

The students had difficulties to solve the exercises. They needed a lot of help and they needed a lot of time for every task. Especially in the first exercise (Push buttons) they needed a lot of time to understand the functions of the program.

The students also got distracted by the computer or the beamer during the exercises. They started to click on and icons on the computer and did not listen to the instructions.

In the second session there were many problems in the first exercise (Lifting a weight with cranes) because the students were too overexcited and did not use the crane carefully. The thread often got knotted so we had to repair the cranes all the time. That's the reason why the students could not focus on the actual tasks because they were too busy with the cranes.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Although they had problems to understand the tasks the students were very excited to work with the robots. After some more explanations they understood the exercises better and had even more fun doing them.

We tried to keep their attention by explaining tasks again in smaller groups.

While we were repairing the cranes, we gave other tasks to the students, using the standard programs of the robot.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

The students were very excited to work with the robots. They showed great interest and just wanted to do anything with them. Sometimes they also did not focus on the actual task and started to do something else.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

We tried to maintain their excitement and encourage them to solve the actual task. Therefore, we often explained to them the main functions of the robot and tried to help them with the first steps to solve the tasks.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_140318)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

The class was very motivated and excited to work with the robots, but they were not listening carefully to the tasks. In many teams there was very bad teamwork so there were many conflicts between the students.

The students also were distracted by different things like Lego blocks or other functions of the robot. So, it was very difficult to explain the exercises to them. They often just did what they want and were not listening to the instructions given.

Especially in the group discussion about the different solutions for the exercise to lift a weight with the crane were many problems. The students were distracted and not disciplined. This made it difficult to have a good discussion in class.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

We tried to explain the exercises and get their attention in different ways. We also put away distracting things so that they can completely focus on the exercises. The teacher did not intervene at all. She did not really care what was happening during the workshop. The class had no discipline at all. We also tried to solve conflicts in each group so that they can work together properly.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Although the class was not disciplined and had not listened to the instructions they were generally interested in doing the workshop. Some of them had a lot of fun to work with the robot and do different task even if it was not the actual tasks.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Despite all the problems we tried to get their attention and raise their interest in working with robots. We looked at what they were actually working on and, even though it was not the main exercise, we tried to elaborate on that to ensure a learning experience for the students.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUW_190318)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Despite of the fact that the class in general was interested and easy to handle, some kids were envious of the others i.e. when one switched to the expert mode, the other wanted it too, which triggered some `you cannot do it anyway`- reaction from the first group etc. Some groups accused each other of stealing the ideas from each other.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Since these were small fights going on all the time no special interfering was necessary. However, it was interesting to see how this behavior dominated in the class, like a class-mentality (especially during session 2).

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Overall the class was very calm and motivated. They listened carefully to the instructions and worked well together in a team (probably also the teacher's influence who helped a lot in coordination). They also learned more effectively after getting some basics explained and then learning by doing.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

The kids reacted the best when they could explore the functions on their own – like showing them some basics and then let them explore it in teams, they only needed some support now and then (especially session 1, the basic exercises like push the buttons and labyrinth).

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUV_220218)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

There were problems with the equipment. The beamer was not working correctly and there were problems in the connection between robots and the computer.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

During problems with the beamer we lost the attention of the class for a moment. But we managed the situation by explaining the tasks in small groups instead of using the beamer for the whole class.

During the connection problems the students got frustrated and bored. We then either exchanged the cable if possible or showed them other activities by using the standard programs of the robot.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

It was interesting to see how motivated the class in general was. The students were eager to program and work with the robot. Unfortunately, some students could not engage that much because of bad teamwork.

On the second day some students finished the tasks very quickly while others were still working on it.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

We tried to encourage the students to work better in a team by taking turns etc. Also the teacher supported us by telling the students to work together with their teammates.

On the second day we also improvised with new tasks when we saw that some students finished the main tasks too quickly.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (TUV_250418)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

One of the students had issues with her group teammates. First she complained about the others not letting her program and/or deleting what she changed etc. After the second time she came to me, she asked for a new group so she switched the team. Her old teammates “celebrated” that she was leaving very loudly. Later the old teammates also told their side of the story, where they were saying the leaving student was the one who did not let them work etc. However, the student fit well in the new group so the issue could be solved.

This situation was quite unexpected since the kids could basically make teams on their own, and there were no issues like that in the previous (9) workshops, however such fights are kind of common under kids of this age.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

The first time she complained I tried to clear the issue by discussing it with the whole group. The second time she came to me she looked quite desperate and it was obvious that the conflict influences their participation in the activity so I chose the simplest solution by letting her to another group. In the end every kid concerned seemed to be fine with this solution, new and old team both worked better after it.

The incident happened during the second session when programming the crane.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

It was interesting that the students were almost all very excited about the storytelling. Most of them were keen on telling their story the whole class. The class had a lot of fun during this section of the workshop.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

The class was taking extra attention to the ones telling the story – they were genuinely interested in the stories of the others’. The teachers also encouraged the students.

Robotic 4 KiDs (BRG Berndorf)

AUTHOR

PRIA

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This Activity plan was designed to allow children without prior knowledge to get in touch with Robotics and the LEGO Mindstorms EV3 set. The activity is designed for students aged 10 to 14 years and its goal is that the students can build and program their own robot, capable of fulfilling a task which the students plan beforehand.

The workshop was held in form of an extracurricular subject which the students can attend in their free time. The extracurricular subject comprised 26 hours in total. However, the Activity Plan only describes the sessions led by PRIA staff (18 hours). The remaining 8 hours were held by the class

teacher and were used to finish the tasks given during the sessions held by the PRIA tutor or planned by the teacher beforehand.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science (0-10) 3 Technology (0-10) 6 Business (0-10) 0 Engineering (0-10) 10 Arts (0-10) 3 Mathematics (0-10) 0

Societal Issues (0-10) 2 Life skills (0-10) 8 Other (please specify)..... (0-10) 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	<p>No subject Engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand that the product design process starts with a basic idea which must be refined subsequently • Gain some resilience against making errors • Use what is available <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what a robot is and of what parts it consists (motors, sensors, controller) • Understand basic programming concepts, like sequences
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	<p>Art:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Express your ideas through built artifacts which have a beauty of their own <p>Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss your ideas and get feedback from your peers Observe your robot and adjust your program based on your observations <p>Societal Issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussion on “How robots can make the world a better place” and in course of thematizing current societal issues <p>Life skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Problem solving Working in Teams Presenting
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	LEGO EV3 programming environment
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p>Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> ... Critical <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p>Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ... Critical <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p>Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ... Critical <input type="checkbox"/></p>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego Mindstorms EV3 Programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A prototype of a robot capable of making the world a better place

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 18 hours

Schedule: 2 – 3 hours per week

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 10-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	little if any knowledge of the Lego Mindstorms EV3 kit; reading and writing skills; basic knowledge of working with computers is advantageous
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Not relevant
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Not relevant
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Not relevant

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Open space for testing and building the robots, notebooks or computers, projector

Environment: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students	Tutors	Assistants
Up to 12	1	0
Up to 16	1	1
Up to 20	2	0
Up to 25	2	1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No criteria
Setting (Style of room):	students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group, with view of the blackboard (projector)

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash &

Dot
 mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

observe, communicate, create (design artifacts, code, robot), discuss their ideas with a classmate, present their work in front of their colleague.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

Designed Conflicts and misconceptions	No
Learning processes emphasized:	emphasis on testing and adapting code to solve given tasks, building and adapting robots to solve given tasks
Expected relevance of alternative knowledge	Not relevant

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

ACTIVITY 1: INTRODUCTION ON THE LEGO MINDSTORMS EV3 SET

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: individual and class work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): After a short introduction on “Who am I? What is PRIA? What are we going to do?”, the students fill out the “Pre-Questionnaire”, and “Draw a scientist”-form and the “Robotic-Mindmap”. Finally, the basic principles of robots are explained as well as the different components of the used robotic set (see slide deck A).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: Instruction, Discussion

ACTIVITY 2: BUILDING ROBOTS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 3 hours

Summary (Description): Each group must build a robot consisting of two big wheels and a support ball.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Art, Life skills

Teaching method: experimentation

Expected student constructions: finished robots

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 3: INTRODUCTION ON PROGRAMMING AND THE MOTOR FUNCTION BLOCK

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group and class work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): After an introduction on programming and the motor function block (see slide deck B and C), the students have to implement their first programs. The first programs must move the robot various predefined paths on the floor.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 4: THE USAGE OF SENSORS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group and class work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): After an introduction on using and programming sensors (see slide deck D), the students have to practice the usage of the tactile sensor, the color sensor, the ultrasonic sensor and the gyroscope. To this end, they must complete various tasks such as bypassing obstacles, controlling the robot using colors or turning the robot by specific angles.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 5: USING CONTROL STRUCTURES (LOOPS AND BRANCHES)

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): After an introduction on using and programming loops and branches (see slide deck E and F), the students practice the learned topics by completing tasks such as composing a melody or following a black line.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 6: CONSTRUCTION OF A GRIPPER ARM

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): After a very short presentation (see slide deck H) of how to build a gripper, the students must implement their own gripper arm capable of moving Objects from A to B.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Art, Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: added functional gripper arm onto the robots

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 7: HOW CAN ROBOTS MAKE THE WORLD A BETTER PLACE? - PROJECTS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group and class work

Duration: 5 hours

Summary (Description): The students must sketch a robot capable of making the world a better place. Furthermore, they must present their draft. Afterwards they have to modify the construction and the software of the robot to fit the drawing. After completing their robot, the students present their work in front of the class.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Art, Life skills, Societal issues

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: robot demonstrating a possibility to make the world a better place

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	no
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Slide set

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Building struggles

It was noticeable, that the children struggled with the building process and the idea finding during the **activities 2** (Building robots) **and 6** (Project: How can robots make the world a better place?). They needed more time than expected to finish their robots and the building tasks in general. Previous workshops I held, where the students must build the robots from scratch, show that the building process usually takes 2 to 3 hours. We usually use the Lego Mindstorms set for elementary school students and thus I believed that older students would need less time. This proved to be a wrong assumption and I believe that the reason for this might be that younger children are more used to the building process since they might play more with Lego in their free time.

Weakness in creativity

The mentioned groups are listed in the “Evaluation Tool - Group Information Session 8”.

Furthermore, especially during the **activity 6** an unexpected weakness in creativity was noticeable, which can be shown by the facts:

- Group 2 and 6 build robots with the same task (to transport things)
- Group 4 and 5 build robots with the same task (to collect garbage)
- Group 4 developed through the merging of three groups with the same initial idea of collecting garbage

During the idea development the students could use the internet and the task was formulated broadly to not restrict their creativity, thus I expected more diverse ideas. On the contrary the teacher stated prior to the task, that he would prefer activities with more additional explanations and new topics compared to task targeting creativity and knowledge from previous tasks. His reason for this was that he did not expect the students to come up with ideas to solve the tasks. After the activity, his opinion seemed changed, because he thought that the students came up with creative and diverse robots.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Building struggles and weakness in creativity

I gave the students more time to finish the robots during **activity 2 and 6**, but other than that I did not change the activities described earlier. The reasons for this are, that I did not want to demotivate the students by setting time limitations and stressing them to finish. Furthermore, I did not address the fact, that different groups had the same idea to prevent quarrels regarding “Who had the idea first?”. Furthermore, in my opinion having the same idea is not problematic, when the implementation is different.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Division of labor

The mentioned groups are listed in the “Evaluation Tool - Group Information Session 8”.

During **activity 6** I noticed interesting shifts in the division of labor in group 3 and 4. Group 3 did not work in this pairing during previous activities and I noticed, that especially the student, who

previously worked alone, seemed much more motivated and hard working. On the contrary in Group 4, students who previously worked alone seemed less motivated over time.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

The shift in group 3 led to a calmer working environment, thus the student who now worked concentrated tended to be restless and sometimes noisier. Group 4 tended to distract each other with private conversations. Group 4 was in the back of the room and thus did not influence the class climate. Whenever I noticed them not working for a longer period, I tried to intervene and talk to them about their progress. I did not confront the group directly to prevent negative feelings towards the end of the workshop and because I thought that the students still worked concentrated despite the talking breaks of the group.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

The students learned to work with the Lego Mindstorms Robotics sets. They learned things about the following topics:

- Introduction on the Robot Set
- Building Robots
- Introduction on programming and the motor function block
- The usage of sensors
- Using control structures (loops and branches)
- How can robots make the world a better place?

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

- I would schedule more time for activities including building tasks.
- I would not include the robotic Mind Map and reduce the evaluation workload in general.
- I would prepare sheets with additional tasks and topics for faster students and students with prior knowledge of the Lego Mindstorms Set.

Workshop Elementary Lego Mindstorms
(Karl Loewe Gasse)

AUTHOR:

PRIA

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This Activity plan was designed to get elementary school children without prior knowledge in touch with Robotics and the LEGO Mindstorms EV3 set. The activity is designed for students aged 6 to 10 years and its goal is that the students learn to let the robot drive along predefined paths.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

3 6 0 10 3 0

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify).....

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 8 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	<p>No subject</p> <p>Engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand that the product design process starts with a basic idea which must be refined subsequently • Gain some resilience against making errors • Use what is available <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what a robot is and of what parts it consists (motors, sensors, controller) • Understand basic programming concepts, like sequences <p>Art:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Express your ideas through built artifacts which have a beauty of their own <p>Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss your ideas and get feedback from your peers • Observe your robot and adjust your program based on your observations <p>Life skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem solving • Working in Teams • Presenting
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<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	LEGO EV3 programming environment
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership ... </p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership ... </p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership ... </p>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego Mindstorms EV3 Programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A prototype of a robot capable of making the world a better place

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: two sessions of in sum 8 hours

Schedule: 4 hours per session

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 6-10 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	little if any knowledge of the Lego Mindstorms EV3 kit; reading and writing skills
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Not relevant
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Not relevant
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Not relevant

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Open space for testing and building the robots, notebooks or computers, projector

Environment: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students	Tutors	Assistants
Up to 12	1	0
Up to 16	1	1
Up to 20	2	0
Up to 25	2	1

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	No criteria
<i>Setting (Style of room):</i>	students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group, with view of the blackboard (projector)

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash &

Dot
 mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

observe, communicate, create (design artifacts, code, robot), discuss their ideas with a classmate, present their work in front of their colleague.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	No
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	emphasis on testing and adapting code to solve given tasks, building and adapting robots to solve given tasks
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Not relevant

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

ACTIVITY 1: INTRODUCTION ON THE LEGO MINDSTORMS EV3 SET

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: individual and class work

Duration: 1 hours

Summary (Description): After a short introduction on “Who are we? What is PRIA? What do you expect from the workshop? What are we going to do?”, the students have to fill out the “Pre-Questionnaire” and the “Draw a scientist”-form.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: -

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: Instruction, Discussion

ACTIVITY 2: INTRODUCTION ON PROGRAMMING AND THE MOTOR FUNCTION BLOCK

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group and class work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): After an introduction on programming and the motor function block (see slide deck B and C), the students have to implement their first programs. The first programs must move the robot along various predefined paths on the floor.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 3: INTRODUCTION ON ROBOTICS

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: class work

Duration: 1 hour

Summary (Description): During this activity, the basic principles of robots are explained as well as the different components of the used robotic set (see slide deck A). Afterwards, the students have to fill out the “Robotic-Mindmap”.

Teaching method: Instruction

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

ACTIVITY 4: ROBOTIC-THEATER

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group and class work

Duration: 3 hours

Summary (Description): After a short revision on the learned things from the previous session, the students have to sketch a theater for their robot. Afterwards they had to modify the construction and the software of the robot to fit the drawing. After completing their robot, the students presented their work in front of the class.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Science, Life skills, Art

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: modified robot to fit the groups robot theater script

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 5: EVALUATION

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: individual work

Duration: 1 hour

Summary (Description): As a last task, the students have to fill out the “Post-Questionnaire” and the “Reflection Activity”.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: -

Teaching method: -

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	no
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Slide set

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Turmoil during free formulated driving tasks

After explaining the driving block, the students were asked to test the function. During their testing process the noise level increased and the students started to race with the robots. This was unexpected since the students were quite silent during previous explanations and tasks.

Velocity during the revision activities

Due to the long time period between the first and the second session we included a revision activity, which is described more in detail in section “Ideas for changes/extensions/revisions of the initial activity plan”. During this activity one group was noticeably faster compared to the other student groups.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Turmoil during free formulated driving tasks

At the beginning we accepted the volume and let them test the robots despite the turmoil, because they seemed to have fun and we believe that you learn better when you have fun while learning. After approximately 10 minutes we stopped the task due to the turmoil and due to the fact that, in our opinion, 10 minutes are sufficient to test the function block.

Velocity during the revision activities

Since one group finished early they got an additional task.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Group constellations

One teacher stated, that it was interesting that one girl did not argue with us, when we asked her to switch groups to allow an even distribution of people for the different groups. She was surprised by the fact, that she did not argue or even noticeably minded working not in her usual group. She was also surprised that the new formed group worked very well together even though the two students were not used to working together and were of opposite gender.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Group constellations

The two students (one male one female) worked well together and thus did not change the overall classroom behavior. Neither the class teacher nor I confronted the two students.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

The students learned to work with the Lego Mindstorms robotic set.

- Introduction on robotics and different application fields
- Introduction on the programming environment and programming the motor function block
- Project: robotic theater (how to make the robot do something you planned previously)

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Revision activity

Due to the long time period between the first and the second session we included a revision activity consisting of the following tasks:

- The robot should drive forward for 3 seconds with a velocity of 50. Afterwards, the robot should turn for 2 seconds with a velocity of 40 and finally drive forward for 2 seconds with a velocity of 70.
- The robot should drive a specific distance which is marked on the ground.
- The robot should drive forward starting and stopping at marked positions and afterwards drive the same distance backwards with a different velocity.

In general, it seemed beneficial to include revision activities to ensure that the students remember and understand the previous activities.

Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine

AUTHOR:

Christina Gkreka, UoA

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Students create physical models of temporary houses simulating the practices of professionals who design and build containers. Firstly they design virtual models of houses using a digital tool, then they create a robot similar to the real machine which cuts solids' nets and finally they program their robot to draw cube and other solids' nets on the paper. These drawings are cut and tiled in order to create physical models of container houses, which are placed on a maquet of a camp which is supposed to host people who have suffered from a physical disaster.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Mathematics, Geometry

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics
 (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
 0 10 0 7 0 10

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify)
 (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
 7 8 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop spatial skills like spatial orientation and spatial visualization. Study solids' nets, 2d and 3d shapes properties fostered by their spatial skills.
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Programming with Logo and LEGO NXT MINDSTORMS programming environment
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership </p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop collaborative skills Take roles within groups Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership </p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Argue about what a camp needs, therefore what solids they need to create and for what reasons. Argue about the spatial arrangement of the camp so that it will be able to support the needs of the people who live there. Practice making conjectures about how the real machine moves in order to cut steel nets which when tiled create container houses. Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models. Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other "makers".
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical </p>

	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership
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INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles; role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Students program in a Logo-like environment the path of a plane which draws solids Students program in Lego NXT MINDSORMS environment their robot in order to draw solids nets on a paper
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Using Lego NXT Mindstorms parts, students construct a 2 axes CNC drawing machine (a simulation of a CNC Milling machine)

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 3 sessions

Schedule: 2 hours per session

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 12 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	18 pupils from Greece, probably 4 of them Albanians
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Public primary school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: in school as an extracurricular activity

Environment: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 18 **Tutors:** 1 **Assistants:** 1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability, mixed gender
Setting (Style of room):	Students in a normal classroom in small groups in front of computers with one Lego NXT Mindstorms kit available for each group

TECHNOLOGY

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurttles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash &

Dot
 mBot
 Other Malt (digital tool)

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other .Logo programming...

LEARNING PROCEDURES**EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY**

Students during the activity are expected to engage in constructing, observing, communicating, creating, presenting their work in a blog, exchange ideas, arguing about possible solutions to their problems.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Educational research mentions difficulties of students in geometry and especially solids' properties and relates them to the absence of the linkage of geometry with spatial ability factors such as spatial visualization. While students try to construct solids nets programming their robot they have to mentally visualize the movements of the robots parts and their spatial orientation. This will help them develop their spatial skills and discover the properties of 3d shapes.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on analyzing, visualizing and describing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior and makes the robot draw a net which can tile into a solid.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to discover the properties of 3d shapes and their nets.

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1-INTRODUCTION TO PHYSICAL DISASTERS ISSUES**Type:**

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 20 min

Summary (Description): Teacher engages students to a discussion about what is a physical disaster, what problems people face in such a situation and how we can deal with these problems. Teacher guides students' discussion emphasizing on the need of providing at least a temporary house for these people. Students are introduced in the idea of camps and temporary houses which are used to provide to these people a place to live until they can inhabit their region again. Teacher informs students that the purpose of the workshop is to create a maquet-model of a camp for people who have suffered a physical disaster. At this point they watch images and videos concerning the building of camps and container houses. They are encouraged to think what the steps of building a camp are.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: -

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 2-DESIGNING A CAMP MAQUET

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 30 min

Summary (Description): Through discussion students are led to the definition of the steps which professionals may follow in order to build a camp with container houses. The first step is designing the camp. Teacher presents to the students a maquet on which models of container houses are to be placed. Students are engaged in discussion about what kind of buildings a camp would need, whether all buildings are going to be the same, where are they going to be placed in the camp so that the spatial arrangement can support the needs of the people who are going to live there. For example, a camp for people who have suffered a physical disaster would need a building which works as health center, a building probably bigger than buildings which would be used as houses. And probably it would be more practical for everybody if this health center would be placed somewhere in the center of the camp in order to be accessible from everybody in a short distance.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Argue about what a camp needs, therefore what solids they need to create and for what reasons.
- Argue about the spatial arrangement of the camp so that it will be able to support the needs of the people who live there.
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution

- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion, experimentation

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 3-DESIGNING VIRTUAL CONTEINER HOUSES

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 70 min

Summary (Description): After spatial arrangement is decided, students design the houses models. Students are introduced in MaLt (<http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/malt2/>), a digital tool in which guiding the path of a plane, they draw 3d shapes, which can simulate temporary houses. They use worksheets in order to guide them the basic functions of the tool through organized steps which help them think about how they can program the plane to move drawing a shape. At first teams create programs which draw different 2d shapes. They are asked to complete a half made program which draws a square, then they create a parallelogram. Next they create programs which draw different 3d shapes. Finally they are asked to use variation tool and observe the way their solids are untiled creating nets, when they reduce the variable of height. This way they can see the 2d representations of their solids, therefore the nets that have to draw, cut and tile in order to create physical models of their solids.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Study solids’ nets, 2d and 3d shapes properties
- Programming with Logo
- Develop collaborative skills
- Take roles within groups
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

Expected student constructions: Virtual 2d and 3d shapes

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 4-REFLECTING ON A REAL MACHINE

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 20 min

Summary (Description): Students are provided with the robotic kit and the parts of the robot that they are already constructed (Figure 1). The session begins reminding students what has already been done. Then students watch images and videos of real CNC machines (Figure 2). In this session students are going to construct a robot which simulates the real machine. Their robot will not cut the parts but it will draw the solids nets on the paper. These drawings will be then cut and tiled into houses models.

Figure 1: The parts that had already been constructed

Figure2: A real CNC machine.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Practice making conjectures about how the real machine moves in order to cut steel nets which when tiled create container houses.

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 5-DISCUSSING OUR PLANS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 20 min

Summary (Description): Before teams start the construction of the robot, they login the platform e-me. They are engaged in a discussion about the construction of the robot and about what movements each part of their robot will make. Teacher encourages students to watch many times the video with the machine in order to define how many movements and what kind of movements has the robot to make and then write their plan in the platform in order to have feedback and exchange ideas with other teams.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Practice making conjectures about how the real machine moves in order to cut steel nets which when tiled create container houses.
- Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models.
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.
- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice

Teaching method: Discussion

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 6-CONSTRUCTING THE ROBOT

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 20 min

Summary (Description): Students built their robots. They have to link the parts which were made in a way so that the machine will draw lines in two axes, simulating the movement of a 2 axes cnc milling machine. While constructing the robot students are encouraged to share their thoughts, plans, problems and solutions with other teams through e-me platform.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Develop collaborative skills
- Take roles within groups
- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
- Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models.
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

Teaching method: Discussion, experimentation

Expected student constructions: A CNC Drawing machine, simulation of a CNC Milling machine

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 7-PROGRAMMING THE ROBOT

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 120 min

Summary (Description): In this session students program their robot. They are given a A3 paper on which their robot is going to move and a pen which is adapted on one of the three vehicles. Teacher introduces them in the programming environment of Lego NXT Mindstorms and explains how they can program the robot to move by choosing a motor block and selecting the motor that they want to move each time. They have to decide the distance that corresponds to each movement given the fact that the drawing are nets which later will be tiled in order to create solids, models of container houses.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Study solids’ nets, 2d and 3d shapes properties.
- Programming with LEGO NXT MINDSTORMS programming environment
- Develop collaborative skills
- Take roles within groups
- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
- Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models.
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

Expected student constructions: Drawings of solids nets

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 8-CONSTRUCTING THE MAQUET

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 40 min

Summary (Description): The drawings are cut and tiled. At last they are placed on the maquet.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
- Argue about the spatial arrangement of the camp so that it will be able to support the needs of the people who live there.
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

Teaching method: Discussion, experimentation

Expected student constructions: The maquet of the camp, physical models of container houses

Expected forms of student dialogue:

PHASE 9-DISCUSSION

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 20 min

Summary (Description): Students log in e-me and they are asked to discuss about their projects, the difficulties they faced and the solution they came up with. At last they are challenged to think what other robotic inventions would be useful in other situations in real life.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice

Teaching method: Discussion, experimentation

Expected student constructions: The maquet of the camp, physical models of container houses

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Step 9 Attachments / Supporting Material

- Images of camps
- Images and videos concerning container houses and their construction
- Images and videos of CNC Milling machine
- Worksheets

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Worksheets about the use of malt digital tool
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	-

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

During the 3rd session, while students were programming their robot, they were trying constantly to imagine and describe the movements each part would make. They were trying to analyze the robot behavior so that each move would correspond to a line of the net. They were usually led to the drawing of a square instead of the drawing of a cube net. Although when reminded of the unfolding of the cube as this was achieved in a previous session, they could realize that drawing a square with their robot would not help them create a physical model of a solid.

A team of 4 girls, after trying to program their robot to draw a net many times, started a discussion about what exactly they wanted their robot to draw. A student explains:

"We don't want a square, but we cannot draw a cube. We have to make an "open cube", like this which we untiled last time, because this way if we cut it and then tile it, it will be a cube".

Another girl in the team suggested that before programming the robot they should draw a draft net like the one they saw when they untiled their virtual cube on malt. This was going to guide them in programming the robot.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Girls asked me if they could draw on the paper the net they wanted their robot to draw and I encouraged them to use this strategy and also share it with other teams.

They drew the net on the paper (Figure 3) and they started programming their robot showing on their drawing the line the robot would draw for each move that was programmed.

Figure 3: Girls add a concrete image as a representation of the net they want their robot to draw

This strategy added a representation to which they could refer every time they wanted to continue to a next step. For each line of their drawing they decided which motor/s would be selected to move and how much in order for the net to be accurately tiled into a cube.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

STUDENTS ARTIFACTS

All teams constructed functional robots which drew shapes on the paper.

Figure 4: Students' artefacts

SPATIAL ORIENTATION AND REFERENCE CONTEXTS THROUGH DYNAMIC AND KINAESTHETIC IMAGERY

To build the robot which would resemble the real machine it was necessary for the students to be able to communicate their ideas about the movements of its parts and its construction, so that everyone would follow a common line during the construction phase. To do that, they were constantly sharing their intuitive ideas moving the robot's parts, expressing their dynamic imagery, making their mental images concrete and reflecting on them. Problems arising from disagreements about the construction of the robot were being resolved through this exchange of dynamic imagery. It seemed from the beginning that the physical characteristics of the tool, such as the orientation of the wheels, helped students communicate their ideas and express not only what they had understood but also their misconceptions. When these misconceptions were expressed students reflected on their ideas in order to make changes and new decisions.

Figure 5: Students expressed their misconceptions about the robot's movements and tested them through dynamic and kinaesthetic imagery.

When students discussed about the robot's movements, they were representing them with gestures expressing their mental images kinesthetically. This made it easier for them to orient themselves with respect to the entities they wanted to move each time and to use the appropriate vocabulary that would describe the entity's movement respectively to its orientation. This facilitated their communication with regard to the concepts of the space in which the entity was moving as they could show exactly what they meant.

Figure 6: Students expressed through dynamic and kinaesthetic imagery.

Tool's physical characteristics lead to kinaesthetic imagery, supporting communication about spatial concepts and adoption of the appropriate reference context, helping to the development of spatial orientation skills by students.

USING MULTIPLE REPRESENTATIONAL SYSTEMS - MATCHING REPRESENTATIONS

In order to draw the desirable shape, students had to imagine which move would result in which line of the net that the robot would draw. To do this, it was necessary to translate the mental dynamic imagery about the robot's movements into the corresponding schematic representation that would be drawn on the paper. This led students to constantly move from one representation to another to check if the result of each movement resulted in the desirable shape.

An example of the above is the work of group 3, which adopts an enhanced strategy. While girls discuss about the robot's movements at first they use gestures to represent the movements of the vehicles so that they can come to a conclusion about the commands they are going to use and their

sequence. However this proves not to be enough, so they decide to create and use another, more concrete representation to their work. They draw the desirable net on the paper and for each line of that net, they represent kinesthetically the robot's movement which will draw it and for each of these movements they make a decision about the command they are going to use (Figure 6,7).

Episode 1

S2: So, at first we have to do this line (1)...

S1: And then this one (2).

Figure 6: The movements corresponding to lines.

S2: Yes, so the small vehicle goes forward (1) and then the two bigger vehicles go forward (2)...

S1: Yes and then we have to go like this (3)... so the small vehicle goes forward again.

Figure 7: The movements corresponding to lines.

In the above episode students facilitate their thinking using additional representations moving from one representational system to another. The schematic representation they designed on the paper guides them regarding the "steps" of the robot. DiSessa et al. (1991) conclude that when students are not only "consumers" of visual representations, but also their creators, who communicate and use them critically, develop meta-representational knowledge, creating and using criteria concerning quality and adequacy of representations.

SPATIAL VISUALISATION AND PROBLEM SOLVING

THE "DISCOVERY" OF THE CUBE NET

The students of the fourth group have given the first command to the robot and they discuss how to continue (Figure 8).

Episode 2

Figure 8: The movements programed so far.

S6: Now we have to move vehicle B forward.

S7: So these (A and C) move forward, right? This (B) moves back...Then these (A and C) move back...and then B moves...

S6: Back...

S7: We cannot move it back...

For the second command of the program that students have created, the vehicle B has moved back in a distance which has covered the length of the robot's rail. The vehicle B cannot move back because it has already reached the end of the rail. Then, S7 has an idea.

S6: We can do this longer (4) so that it will be tiled like this (he shows how the net is going to be tiled in order to create a cube).

S7: So we will not make a "cross"...

S6: We can do this longer so we will cover this side also (he shows the line of the other headquarter of the cube).

Figure 9: The fourth movement is proposed.

During this episode a difficulty because of the length of the robot's rail led to a new idea. Students imagined the right moves for the robot but they did not calculate the distance or the time they must move the vehicle on the rail so that it will be able to move again in the same direction. Necessarily, the strategy had to change. S6 proposed to draw a longer line "to cover this side". So they will not draw a "cross" net but another kind of a cube net.

The problem students faced led them to think about alternative solutions. Thinking about what movements the machine could make from the point where it had stopped, S6 came up with another shape which was going to create a cube.

THE "DISCOVERY" OF THE EQUALITY OF THE CUBE EDGES

Another group also faced a problem due to the robot structure. Students had already given the first three commands (Figure 10).

Figure 10: The first three movements and their graphical result

Then the robot has to draw line (c). However the vehicle which moves on axis x has no more space to move forward.

Episode 3

S2: *We cannot do it like this, there is no space.*

S3: *There is a little...*

S2: *But it won't be right because they have to have the same length because afterwards we will tile it and they need to be the same in order for the cube to close.*

S4: *We will do it from the start and we will move the first less...*

S2: *And then we will add the same value so it will be the same and the cube will close.*

S4: *Yes, put here 2 seconds instead of 4 and then we will move it again for 2 seconds.*

S2 imagines how the net will be folded and realizes that all lines must have the same length so that their cube closes. So students change their program.

Figure 11: Initial program.

Figure 12: Students change the duration of the first movement.

Motivated by the problem that occurred, students thought about the distance the third vehicle has to move. They realized that the distance had to be the same every time as they mentally visualized the net folding.

PATTERN IMAGES

The students of the fourth group have run the first three commands (Figure 13) and discuss how to continue.

Figure 13: The first three movements

S7: It has to do the same movements.

S8: All this again? And how is it going to close? B should go forward.

S7: This way it will draw a square...We need an open cube.

S8: B should move right then...

S7: We can only move it back or forward.

S8: Back!

S7: That is what I meant. B moves back and we are doing the same again, because then we will move these two (A and C).

S7 imagined the graphic result and realized that the robot draws a pattern. Spatial visualization of the vehicles' movements along with the virtual environment helped him identify the pattern.

Generally, during the activities:

- Students developed strategies of spatial orientation and spatial visualisation.
- Physical characteristics of the artifact helped students develop spatial orientation skills through dynamic and kinaesthetic imagery.
- Spatial orientation skills and adoption of the right reference context when referring to the robot's movements of three dimensional helped students mentally manipulate three dimensional objects.
- While working with the robots students faced problems which led them to critical reflection and unexpected solutions.
- Students used multiple systems of representation and they were engaged in representational interpretation procedures.
- Engaged with the artifacts in a realistic and purposeful context students "discovered" mathematical ideas such as the cube net, the property of the cube's lines' equality and patterns.

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

The activity described was mostly referred to cubes and cube nets. The activity plan can be extended by adding other kinds of solids nets which can be drawn by the robot.

Furthermore the CNC tool that was constructed was moving in 2 axes drawing two dimensional shapes. It would be an interesting extension if students constructed and programmed a 3 axes CNC machine (Figure 14). In this case the tool would be a milling machine and it would create 3d shapes (Figure 15).

Figure 14: A 3 axes CNC machine

Figure 15: A CNC milling machine creates 3d shapes.

Robotic Olympics

AUTHOR

Giannis Baras

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

The activity is aimed at students building robots that can compete in sports that people compete with. Students need to consider how people first struggle in a sport and the natural laws governing a match (what are the sensory organs and muscles they use) and then determine whether the principles of natural laws can be applied to robots . There will be 3 sports (chariot running, wrestling and throws). Each sport event will take a two-hour lesson.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

Focus:

physics, maths and programming (also on ancient history).

Set up:

robotics lab, teams of 2 or 3 pupils

Requirements:

one laptop and one robotics kit(LEgo ev3)/3 pupils

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Maths, Physics, Programming

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
7	9	0	8	3	9

Societal Issues Life skills History

(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
2	10	6

OBJECTIVES

<i>Maths, Physics, Programming</i>	Circle perimeter, calculating angles, trigonometry, Friction
<i>Technology use related</i>	LEGO EV3 programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips,
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	The aim of the work is to understand the importance of sensors in the control of robotic structures, as well as the natural laws behind human activity.

TIME

Duration: 3 weeks

Schedule: 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Vehicle – Projectile launcher
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	step-by-step instructions for the basic construction, example Video, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Presentation, teacher notes

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 9-12 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	little knowledge of Robotics; basic knowledge of programming ;
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	All students from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	50% mainstream public school, 50% elite private school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: After school activity at Robotics Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 15**Tutors:** 1**GROUPING:**

Grouping criteria	By age
Setting:	Students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas,
Relationships	Collaborative, competitive
Roles in the group	Role exchange in the group
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, monitor

LEARNING PROCEDURES**EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY**

Make hypothesis, create, observe, exchange ideas, evaluate

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	The students will act as researchers where they will make assumptions and try to confirm or break down their ideas. At the same time, they will try to win through co-operation and noble competition from the other groups.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Students will try to investigate whether laws of physics are common to robots and humans.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students will try to find out whether a well-engineered, intelligent programming can compete with one's strategy.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM**PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION- QUESTIONS TO RAISE INTEREST****Duration:** 15 minutes**Orchestration:** class work**Description:** During the first phase there is a presentation of the main Olympic games as well as the development of the robotic structures. A video where robots compete with people is demonstrated.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Investigation, Hypothesis, Research

Expected forms of student dialogue: Exchange of ideas

Teaching method: demonstration by example, discussion, Inquired-Based

PHASE 2: HYPOTHESIS

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group and class work

Description: Students make their initial assumptions and try to develop a plan to solve the problem.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected forms of student dialogue: exchange of arguments

Teaching method: Monitor, try to guide into conclusions

PHASE 3: CONSTRUCTION - PROGRAMMING

Duration: 45 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students make their construction and plan it according to their polarity. They also try to understand the parameters that can influence the outcome of the effort.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions : Basic vehicle with additional parts to be able to compete in the sport.

Teaching method: experimentation

PHASE 4: TESTING

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Robotic structures are tested. Students observe their constructions, where they are experiencing problems, they record basic parameters that they had assumed from the previous steps that they would affect their constructions. They add new parameters that affect their robots. They check if their hypotheses are verified.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions : small variations in construction

Teaching method: discussion,

PHASE 5: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: All teams exhibit the construction type. A small contest is taking place. Students observe rival robots. They analyze the plan of their construction, receive observations and advice from other groups, and try to improve their robotics.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: small variations in construction

Expected forms of student dialogue: exchange of ideas, position support, position analysis

Teaching method: discussion,

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

All teams record specific parameters they have set during the phase of the case. They constantly control their results, make comparisons with other groups and diversify their plan. In the end, they complete an evaluation report.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

There have been interesting assumptions about how we can use sensors to control robots. Unfortunately, the low level of material we use did not leave room for control of students' ideas. Also, moral issues were raised during sporting events among people and whether there are similar moral problems in human-robot or only robot-related events.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

The question of the use of sensors was searched on the Internet to find relevant documentation. Correspondingly on ethical issues, a brief discussion took place.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

The students realized that even behind the human movement and behind the robot programming, there are natural laws that affect them.

Please indicate specifically what your students learned regarding STEM choosing from the concepts listed below

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

The students liked the history of technology. It could be expanded with the addition of art (creating robots that will try to imitate people in the arts). Also, as students have understood natural laws, then

they can go a step further and try to introduce the strategy into their robot programming. This will make an introduction to Artificial Intelligence.

Basic Introduction to SLurtles

AUTHOR:

Dr Carina Girvan (Cardiff University)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This short activity introduces students to SLurtles (robot), Scratch for OpenSim (programming tool) and the virtual world (Slurtle World), familiarising them with the technology through guided discovery. Following open exploration of the virtual world and SLurtles to familiarise students with basic controls, students engage in a series of short directed tasks which progressively develop into more open ended activities to develop their familiarity with using and controlling SLurtles by programming them. These activities are based on existing mathematical knowledge (properties of shapes) and provide an opportunity to explore the programming environment.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Computing.....

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

- | | | | | | |
|----------------------------------|--|-----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|-------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Science | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology | <input type="checkbox"/> Business | <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering | <input type="checkbox"/> Arts | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics |
| (0-10) | (0-10) | (0-10) | (0-10) | (0-10) | (0-10) |
| 0 | 10 | 0 | 0 | 0 | 3 |
-
- | | | |
|--|--------------------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Societal Issues | <input type="checkbox"/> Life skills | <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)..... |
| (0-10) | (0-10) | (0-10) |

0 0 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	Moving between multiple applications Use knowledge of the properties of shapes to solve problems
	Skills to be fostered: <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it. Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim)
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world.
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning.
	Skills to be fostered: <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Share ideas and experiences with others, peer learning, problem solving.
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Monitor and facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim. Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only) Robot – Slurtles (cuboids)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	SLurtles: Programmable turtle in a virtual world which creates cuboids

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 3weeks

Schedule: 1 hour per week

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 13-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	None
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	UK, Wales.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Low socio-economic area.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school computer lab, part of scheduled lessons.

Environment: Indoors.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 30

Tutors: 1 teacher, 1 assistant

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Working individually at start. In matched ability pairs for problem solving with more able and talented leading learning.
<i>Setting (Style of room):</i>	Students in a normal computer lab. In virtual world.

TECHNOLOGY

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo Arduino Hedgehog SLurtles LEGO Mindstorms MOSS Robotic Dreams Thymio 2 Dash &

Dot mBot Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop Scratch: Open SIM C++ Python Java C Arduino Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

In world: explore, communicate, programme and create.

In classroom: communicate, present work and exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	None planned as this is an introduction to the technology. Maths: Assumptions that the SLurtle turns through the internal angle.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on exploring and becoming familiar with virtual worlds and the control of SLurtles.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to know the properties of squares and triangles, and to apply this knowledge. If there are knowledge gaps the activity can be modified to provide an opportunity for individual students to discover the properties of these shapes through programming their robot.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1- INTRODUCTION TO THE VIRTUAL WORLD

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: At the start of the lesson, the whole class is introduced to the virtual world before individually deciding on the name on their avatar and password, creating them with the teacher on the server (up to 30 minutes depending on the size of the class). In the rest of the lesson, students explore the virtual world individually, freely exploring or following a path around the island with guided orientation activities.

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it.

Expected student constructions: Avatar customisation

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing, demonstration and instruction of peers.

Teaching method: Guided discovery and peer-teaching

PHASE 2-FOCUSED EXPLORATION AND SANDBOXING SLURTLES

Type:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Introductory	Reflection	Assessment	Evaluation	Exploration	Experimentation	Construction	Other	

Orchestration: individual

Duration: 1 hour

Summary (Description): Students consolidate and further their understanding and skills within the virtual world through structured activities. To support this, students are given a physical guide to refer to and scavenger hunt activities to practice targeted skills (communication, flying, inventory use, camera tools). During this time the teacher can work with students who missed the previous lesson to create an avatar etc. By the end of the lesson, all students should have moved to the class island (through the red door).

On the class island the teacher provides a demonstration of SLurtles and S4OS. Student task: make the SLurtles move use various commands. Experiment to find out what else it can do.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing, demonstration and instruction of peers.

Teaching method: Guided discovery and peer-teaching

PHASE 3-PROGRAMMING SLURTLES TO BUILD – AN INTRODUCTION

Type:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Introductory	Reflection	Assessment	Evaluation	Exploration	Experimentation	Construction	Other	

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 1 hour

Summary (Description): Students are re-introduced to SLurtles and Scratch for OpenSim (S4OS) and given a series of simple directed tasks to gain familiarity with the tools, switching between programmes and programming SLurtles to build – programme the SLurtle to move, draw a line, draw a multi-coloured line.

Following this, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurtle to draw a square. Working in pairs (on computers next to each other, students work together to solve the challenge. Extension problems: 1) Explain why there is a gap at each of the external corners of the square. 2) Programme the SLurtle to draw a square without these gaps. 3) What’s the minimum number of lines that this your programme could be written in? 4) Draw another shape.

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes; communicating with others.

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed lines and squares.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

Step 9 Attachments / Supporting Material

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Virtual world orientation guide and scavenger hunt.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	None

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Please describe unexpected that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this moment as unexpected. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Please describe interesting moments that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible changes or extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

Building Our Virtual World

AUTHOR:

Dr Carina Girvan (Cardiff University) in collaboration with Mr Adam Speight (Mary Immaculate High School, Cardiff. Wales)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity uses SLurtles (robot), Scratch for OpenSim (programming tool) and the virtual world (SLurtle World), where students apply their knowledge to the construction of their own virtual world island.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other: School lesson.....

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:Computing/ICT.....

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science (0-10) 0
 Technology (0-10) 10
 Business (0-10) 0
 Engineering (0-10) 0
 Arts (0-10) 3
 Mathematics (0-10) 3

Societal Issues (0-10) 0
 Life skills (0-10) 0
 Other (please specify)..... (0-10) 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	Moving between multiple applications Communicating and collaborating online Be able to use loops effectively in programmes Apply knowledge of the properties of shapes to solve problems Identify problems and develop solutions.
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	Practice and develop programming skills with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim) Develop 3D spatial awareness.
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop an awareness of how to communicate effectively with others in a virtual world.
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Design and create an interactive object within

	<p>the virtual world Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Explain ideas to others. Identify and solve problems together. Reflection for learning.</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p>

STEP 4. Interaction during the activity

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Share ideas and experiences with others, peer learning, problem solving; design and creation of a shared space.
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative; peer-learning
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Instruct, monitor and facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim. Virtual world – Slurtle World (internal access only) Robot – Slurtles (cuboids) Sways to document learning</p>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	SLurtles: Programmable turtle in a virtual world which creates cuboids

STEP 6. Who? Where? How long?

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 5 weeks

Schedule: 50 minutes twice a week

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 13-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Experience in virtual worlds, programming Slurtles to build 2D shapes, communicating with others in the virtual world, documenting their work using screenshots and Sways.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	UK, Wales
<i>Social status and social</i>	Low socio-economic area. Catholic school.

<i>environment</i>	
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Range of cognitive and physical needs.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school computer lab, part of scheduled lessons.

Environment: Indoors.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 30

Tutors: 1 teacher

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Students are in mixed-ability pairs. Girls working with boys where possible. Typically students do not sit next to each other.
<i>Setting (Style of room):</i>	Students in a normal computer lab. In virtual world.

TECHNOLOGY

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash &

Dot
 mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

In world: explore, communicate, programme and create.

In classroom: communicate, present work, exchange ideas and engage in peer-learning.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	None planne. Maths: Assumptions that the SLurtle turns through the internal angle.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on developing knowledge by engaging in the construction of a personally meaningful artefact.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Some students may have knowledge of constructing 3D shapes in virtual worlds.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1-RE-INTRODUCTION TO THE VIRTUAL WOLRD AND TASK

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 50 minutes

Orchestration: Students log into the virtual world individually. Pairs assigned by the teacher. Group space assigned by teacher.

Description: Students are introduced to the task: The whole class will create a virtual world island. Whole-class discussion on what should be on the island. Each group is assigned a 40x40 meter space on the island in which to create an installation. Students are provided with brainstorming and planning time face-to-face to develop an idea for what will be in their space.

Supported objectives: Design and create an interactive object within the virtual world

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion

Teaching method: Instruction and monitoring

PHASE 2-CONSTRUCTING AND RECORDING THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARTEFACTS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: pairs

Duration: 8x 50 minutes

Summary (Description): In their pairs, students create the artefacts in their space. This may be collaboratively or cooperatively. Communication should happen online.

Students can use a mixture of virtual world building tools and SLurtles but must include one SLurtle built artefact.

Every fourth lesson, students are provided with dedicated and directed time to document their progress in their Sways. They should identify problems that they encountered and explain how they solved them. They should also take time to visit other groups' spaces for inspiration.

Expected student constructions: Various artefacts in the virtual world; Sway book

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; communicating and collaborating online; be able to use loops effectively in programmes; apply knowledge of the properties of shapes to solve problems; identify problems and develop solutions; practice and develop programming skills with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); develop 3D spatial awareness; Design and create an interactive object within the virtual world; application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems; awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem; explain ideas to others; identify and solve problems together; and reflection on learning.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Sharing ideas, support, guidance, demonstration, peer-learning

Teaching method: Monitoring and facilitating.

PHASE 3-PRESENTATION, REFLECTION AND EVIDENCING LEARNING

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: pairs and individual

Duration: 50 minutes

Summary (Description): Students present their completed artefacts and share their ideas with others. This can be done to the whole class in the room or by pairs visiting each other in the virtual world.

Complete individual Sways with final snapshot of their creation and a personal reflection on what they are most proud of and how they could improve (their artefacts and/or how they worked in a team).

Supported objectives: Communicating ideas to others

Expected student constructions: None

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Presentations

Step 9 Attachments / Supporting Material

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Sway for students to complete, with video tutorials.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	None

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Please describe unexpected that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this moment as unexpected. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Please describe interesting moments that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible changes or extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing

AUTHOR:

Dr Carina Girvan (Cardiff University) in collaboration with Mr Adam Speight (Mary Immaculate High School, Cardiff. Wales)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity introduces students to SLurtles (robot), Scratch for OpenSim (programming tool) and the virtual world (Slurtle World), familiarising them with the technology through guided discovery. Following open exploration of the virtual world and SLurtles to familiarise students with basic controls, students engage in a series of short directed tasks which progressively develop into more open ended activities to develop their familiarity with using and controlling SLurtles by programming them. These activities are based on existing mathematical knowledge (properties of shapes) and provide an opportunity to explore the programming environment.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other: School lesson.....

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:Computing/ICT.....

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 10 0 0 0 3

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify).....

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

0 0 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	Moving between multiple applications Communicating and collaborating online Be able to use loops effectively in programmes Use knowledge of the properties of shapes to solve problems
------------------------	---

	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	<p>Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it. Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim)</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	<p>Develop an awareness of how to communicate effectively with others in a virtual world.</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	<p>Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning.</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership <input type="checkbox"/></p>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Share ideas and experiences with others, peer learning, problem solving.
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative; peer-learning
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Instruct, monitor and facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim. Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only) Robot – SLurtles (cuboids) Sways to document learning</p>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	<p>SLurtles: Programmable turtle in a virtual world which creates cuboids</p>

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 5 weeks

Schedule: 50 minutes twice a week

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 13-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	None
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	UK, Wales
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Low socio-economic area. Catholic school.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Range of cognitive and physical needs.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school computer lab, part of scheduled lessons.

Environment: Indoors.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 30

Tutors: 1 teacher

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Working individually at start. Students are in mixed-ability pairs. Girls working with boys where possible.
<i>Setting (Style of room):</i>	Students in a normal computer lab. In virtual world.

TECHNOLOGY

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash & Dot
 mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

In world: explore, communicate, programme and create.

In classroom: communicate, present work and exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	None planned as this is an introduction to the technology. Maths: Assumptions that the SLurtle turns through the internal angle.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on exploring and becoming familiar with virtual worlds and the control of SLurtles.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to know the properties of squares and triangles, and to apply this knowledge. If there are knowledge gaps the activity can be modified to provide an opportunity for individual students to discover the properties of these shapes through programming their robot.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1-INTRODUCTION TO THE VIRTUAL WOLRD

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Duration: 50 minutes

Orchestration: At the start of the lesson, the whole class is introduced to the virtual world before individually deciding on the name and password for their avatar. Students begin to explore the virtual world individually.

Description: Children are introduced to the virtual world and provided with an opportunity to name and create a password for their avatar. Students then log into the virtual world for the first time and are given the opportunity to freely explore or following a path around the island with guided orientation activities.

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Guided discovery and peer-teaching.

PHASE 2-EXPLORING THE VIRTUAL WORLD AND CUSTOMISING AN AVATAR

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: individual

Duration: 2x 50 minutes

Summary (Description): Students continue their exploration of the virtual world and start to experiment with the capabilities of their avatar and the virtual world programme. The teacher demonstrates how to customize an avatar and how to take screenshots. Students take screenshots of places they have found in the virtual world.

Expected student constructions: Avatar customisation

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Direct instruction, guided discovery and peer-teaching.

PHASE 3-REFLECTION AND EVIDENCING LEARNING

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: individual

Duration: 50 minutes

Summary (Description): Students are introduced to the Sway where they will be documenting their learning. The Sway also contains videos to support learners through future activities. Following a short whole-class discussion, students complete independent research and write in the Sways about what a virtual world is. Students include screenshots from the virtual world to demonstrate how they customized their avatar and interesting places they found in the virtual world, along with a brief description.

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is

Expected student constructions: Sway book

Expected forms of student dialogue: Whole-class discussion

Teaching method: Research

PHASE 4- INTRODUCTION TO SLURTLES – SANDBOXING AND SQUARES

Type:

- Introductory
- Reflection
- Assessment
- Evaluation
- Exploration
- Experimentation
- Construction
- Other

Orchestration: Informal pairs

Duration: 4x 50 minute lessons

Description: Students are introduced to SLurtles and Scratch for OpenSim (S4OS) and given a series of simple directed tasks to gain familiarity with the tools and switching between programmes – programme the SLurtle to move, draw a line, draw a multi-coloured line. Students are then given one lesson to freely explore what they can create by programming the SLurtle.

Following this, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurtle to draw a square. Extension problems: 1) Explain why there is a gap at each of the external corners of the square. 2) Programme the SLurtle to draw a square without these gaps. 3) What’s the minimum number of lines that this your programme could be written in?

Students are introduced to loops and as a whole-class discuss how their programme could be shortened by using a loop.

Throughout the first three lessons, students are encouraged to take screenshots of their constructions and programmes ready to add to their Sway in the fourth lesson. In this lesson they document what they have created and what they have learned.

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes; communicating with others; using loops.

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed lines and squares; Sway book

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing, demonstration and instruction.

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

PHASE 5-SLURTLE CHALLENGES

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2x 50 minute lessons

Summary (Description): In their allocated pairs (not normally sat together), students complete a series of mathematical problems based around 2D and 3D shapes with increasing complexity. Students are reminded about how to use the communication tools and how to communicate effectively in world. Throughout they record success and failure using screenshots and document this with explanations in their Sway books.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes; communicating with others; using loops.

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed shapes; Sway book

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing, demonstration, cooperative and instruction.

Teaching method: Structured tasks, facilitation and peer-teaching.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Virtual world orientation guide and scavenger hunt. Sways with weekly lesson objectives and supporting videos.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	None

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Please describe unexpected that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this moment as unexpected. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Please describe interesting moments that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible changes or extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

7.2 REVISED ACTIVITY PLANS

Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash

AUTHORS:

JoannaPullicino, Annalise Duca, Angele Giuliano

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

These were workshops run with students whose average age was 10 years, and, at primary level. The robots used were Dash and Dot although the practical aspects were explored with Dash. Dash is a ready made robot and our activities focused mostly around discovering the functionalities of Dash, using its sensors, and programming Dash to move in a maze, race or move between two fixed posts.

During these sessions, run between October and December 2016, the tutors reflected with the students about teamwork and collaboration (Annex 1 to this document), creativity (held a spontaneous draw a postcard session - WORKSHEET 2) and sustaining attitudes to STEM by expanding on career prospects and brushing on gender in Science.

Furthermore, a set of questions were handed out to Learning Support Assistants (Annex 1 to this document) to hear their views about how their students could/could not engage with robots.

PS during these months, AcrossLimits was holding sessions still with Primary students - same age/school level as had been done during Spring 2016. Nonetheless, certain aspects from the ten commandments¹ were included to upgrade the workshops accordingly.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

¹ Reference to the recommendations that resulted from the first year evaluations.

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
6	8	0	0	0	3

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	e.g. Basic programming and loops (If then, repeat until)
<i>Technology use related</i>	e.g. Using remote control and Drag and Drop visuals
<i>Social and action related</i>	e.g. Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	e.g. Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once. They were encouraged to test before they tell the tutors that their work was ready.

TIME

Duration: e.g. 8 hours split across two mornings

Schedule: e.g. 2 sessions of 4 hours each.

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	e.g. Drag and Drop visual
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	i.e. Not applicable
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	e.g. worksheets with a set of graded exercises
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	e.g. Powerpoint presentations

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys& girls, average 10 years of age. Classes were at times single gender; other times they were a mixed group.
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	None of the students had prior knowledge on Dash. Around 5% of students attended short summer courses outside their school on Lego

	Mindstorm
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	around 96% Maltese. Reminder from Europe or outside European countries.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school, Private and Church schools.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Autism, Down's syndrome, ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders. Less than 4% had problems understanding English.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: School gymnasium or hall.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: Groups of 24 to 27

Tutors: 2 occasionally 3

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed abilities. Single or mixed gender. Each class had students with special needs.
<i>Setting:</i>	Students seated on paper mats on the floor, facing projector during talk time by tutors. When exploring with Dash, students were again on the floor and Dash on the mat.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	e.g. Exchange ideas and dialogue
<i>Relationships</i>	e.g. Collaborative and competitive (during races)
<i>Roles in the group</i>	e.g. role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Not applicable
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. observe the robot's behavior once programmed 2. communicate and discuss tasks set and decide on the way forward 3. create your experience on a 2 differently designed postcards(one postcard was not printed on both sides; the other, was printed on only

	one side).
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	None

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The pre-questionnaire was first carried out. This was followed by an introduction to what are robots and what isn't a robot. Advantages and disadvantages of robots in everyday life, and, how or why humans use them.

Collaboration, communication and teamwork are discussed and students are asked to reflect on what are the requisites for good teamwork (Part A, Annex 1). Examples of science careers and employments are presented to them to sustain the applicability of STEM subjects and nurture STEM in their thinking and possibly future choice of subjects. Gender is brushed upon to explain that any STEM career can be equally followed by males or females and hence to break down any stereotype images that the students might have had.

A demonstration of Dash and its functions, sensors and actions was explained to the children. The robot was then handed out and they were allowed firstly to experiment and explore freely.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use related and Social and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: communication and taking turns

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion with the students and experimentation by the students themselves.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING, GROUP REFLECTION AND INDIVIDUAL CREATION OF A POSTCARD

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Group work (groups of 2 or 3) and individual

Description: Students implement their first programs as per the puzzle sheet. No loops. The first programs moved the robot on a predefined path on the floor, made sounds, turned on/off its lights etc. They were then asked to reflect and think about the outcome of this first workshop, their

impression of teamwork and collaboration and the advantages and disadvantages of working together (Annex 1, Part B and C).

Finally, students were given a postcard - printed on one side with Dash and Dot, and empty on the other side. This was a 'free to think' and 'do as you wish' exercise where students were asked to draw and/or colour and/or describe their experience of during the workshop (Annex 2). This was done individually by each student.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use related and Social and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, taking turns, taking decisions

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: REFLECTION AND USING LOOPS

Duration: 3 hours 30 minutes

Orchestration: group work (groups of 2 or 3)

Description: Follow on from the previous session and further reflection on teamwork/collaboration.

Students try to find a way to simplify their programs by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program. They use loops with their programming blocks. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, taking turns, taking decisions

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: CREATIVITY AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and class work

Description: The students are handed out a postcard, same size and shape as the one from the first session. It is different that it is empty at the back and at the front.

In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, they also fill in an evaluation questionnaire. The teacher gets short informal open interviews from a group of students (2 - 3) who had been informed previously (during the first workshop) to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use related and Social and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, creativity and thinking

Teaching method: Discussion

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

In this section we include the worksheets they were used during the implementation of the activity both as an instrument to support the teaching and learning process and as means to assess students

WORKSHEET 1

REFLECTIVE QUESTIONS:

Before Starting Workshop No 1: (Part A)

1. What do you think is the Golden Rule to work together? {Write all the comments on a blank paper}
2. How do you feel about group work?

Before Postcard Activity No 1: (Part B)

1. Apart from working together as a group, what have you learnt today (prompt regarding programming/technology)?
2. Do you have any previous experience working together/collaborating from other projects (prompt: this could be together at school or in other circumstances outside the school where they engage together e.g. sports, dancing sessions, scouts/guides etc.)
3. How does it feel, or, what are your impressions about teamwork?

End of Workshop No 1: (Part C)

1. Now that you have worked as a group, reflect on one thing that you would like to change to work better in a group/team. Write a sentence on this and bring it with you to the next workshop.

Before Starting Workshop No 2: (Part D)

1. Discuss on points from previous activity: What would you change to work better in a team?
2. Remind them of the Golden Rules set from Workshop 1

WORKSHEET 2

Postcard cover page

ANNEX 1

QUESTIONS TO LEARNING SUPPORT ASSISTANT

Age of student/s you assist:

What are the student/s conditions/learning difficulty etc.?

Does your student/s prefer to work alone? Why?

Could working in a group (teamwork) of 2 - 3, benefit your student/s. How?

In your opinion, do you think that the use of robots would be beneficial for your student/s in particular subjects? Yes/ No? Which subjects? Why?

Engaging with robots in a fun way

AUTHOR:

Pullicino Joanna, Duca Annalise

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

These were workshops run with students whose age was between 11 - 13 years, and, at secondary level. The robots used were Dash and Dot although the practical aspects were explored with Dash. Dash is a pre-constructed robot and activities focused around programming Dash through commands and loop statements. Another objective was explaining to students that when searching for a solution programming gives you the advantage of finding multiple answers to activities, and, that some solutions are simpler and more straightforward than others.

These sessions were run between March and May 2018 and during each workshop the tutors reflected with the students about group work and collaboration; a worksheet (Annex 2) was also assigned to students to gather feedback about this. STEM careers and gender in science were topics discussed during workshops.

Another topic discussed with students was about success, failure and resilience. These factors were presented to students in an employment context where perseverance, personal initiative and drive are key factors. The students recounted their experience of how successful/unsuccessful they were during the workshop activities by describing this in a diary post (Annex 3).

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO X YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	8	0	0	0	6

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Specific tasks according to set instructions related to, technology, programming and mathematical concepts including probability and random numbers.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Drag and drop visuals
<i>Social and action related</i>	Allowed students to collaborate and share ideas with each other, and, to learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being teams/groups.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Finding multiple solutions to activities, allowing the robot to respond to external stimuli/obstacles

TIME

Duration: 2 days

Schedule: 4 hours per day

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Drag and Drop visuals
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Not applicable
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Using worksheets containing graded activities whose difficulty increased from one task to another
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Power point presentation, and, hard copy of programme for time management

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 11 - 13 years old. Some classes were same gender, girls only.
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<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Knowledge of Scratch language for a few of the students which helped with programming of Dash; very few others had attended Lego Mindstorm classes. Other students had no previous knowledge in programming or robotics.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	The majority Maltese; around 10% came from European or non-European countries
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Church schools and private schools. In church schools the population is of a diverse social status. In private schools the majority come from a high social background and there are more foreigners attending versus church schools.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Some degree of autism, dyslexia, dyscalculia, Down's syndrome

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: computer lab or school hall or school gymnasium

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: e.g. groups ranged between 15 and 26

Tutors: e.g. 2

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender or single gender
<i>Setting:</i>	e.g. Students seated on the floor, indoors, in groups of 2 or 3 sharing a tablet and a robot per group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	e.g. Exchange ideas and dialogue
<i>Relationships</i>	e.g. Collaborative and competitive (during races)
<i>Roles in the group</i>	e.g. role exchange in the group

<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate
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LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Not applicable to activities prepared
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. multiple programming solutions to the activities 2. communicate and discuss tasks set and decide on the way forward 3. write up about your experience, learn about collaborative issues).
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	None

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Presentation, experimentation and group work.

Description: The pre-questionnaire was first carried out. This was followed by an introduction to what are robots and what isn't a robot. Advantages and disadvantages of robots in everyday life, and, how or why humans use them.

Collaboration, communication and teamwork are discussed and students are asked to talk about the requisites for good teamwork (Annex 2). Examples of science careers and employments were presented to them to sustain the applicability of STEM subjects and nurture STEM in their thinking and possibly future choice of subjects. Gender in career uptake and employment is discussed to explain that any STEM career can be equally taken up by males or females and hence to break down any stereotype images that the students might have had.

A demonstration of Dash and its functions, sensors and actions was explained to the children. The robot was then handed out and they were allowed firstly to experiment and explore freely.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: communication and taking turns

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion with the students and experimentation by the students themselves.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING AND LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Group work (groups of 2 or 3) and individual

Description: Students implement their first programs as per the puzzle sheet (Annex 1). Loops, If-else, repeat-until were included in the programs constructed by the students. A key factor in these puzzles was to make students aware that a number of options and answers are possible in programming which range from a simple to a more complex solution.

Puzzle 5, as shown in Annex 1 allowed the students to come up with an activity themselves for a peer. We emphasized on creativity and to come up with an exciting task; this task was based on bringing in knowledge from the previous activities of the day but it had to be different.

At the end of this workshop, students were given a worksheet to point out characteristics relating to collaboration and group work.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, taking turns, taking decisions

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS AND ANALYSIS

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Two scenarios are presented to students where the robot assumes two personalities: as a security guard (puzzle 6) and a lottery drawer (puzzle 7). In the former situation the robot must realise where its boundaries are and walk accordingly from one end to another. As a lottery drawer the robot presents a fair and transparent scenario by drawing random numbers. In both instances there are multiple ways how to arrive to your answer and the loops came into the picture again.

Two commonly used mathematical and analytical topics were part of these activities and explained. These are the use of graphs to interpret data collected (Puzzle 6) and hence the importance of statistics, and, probability (Puzzle 7). With regards to probability students recorded the number generated by their robot. The tutors generated a random number and then listed all the numbers on the board. Later the tutor revealed the number the robot generated. The question “What is the probability that your robot generates the same number as mine?” was asked to the students.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions - not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: brainstorming, interpretation

Teaching method: instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: REFLECTION AND POST FEEDBACK

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Individual work

Description: These 2 day workshops focused on the students' abilities to come up with more than one answer to a task, and, therefore their resilience to achieve or give up. They were asked to describe and talk about their experience with being successful, unsuccessful and resilient in a diary post.

At the end of this exercise, the students were asked to give their feedback about the two day workshops which they had participated to.

An interview was carried out to 2 - 3 students who had acted as the focus group to get deeper insight of their experiences.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: personal reflection, evaluation

Teaching method: Explanation

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

Annex 1

Puzzle 1

Make Dash drive in a square.

There are 2 correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them both?

Puzzle 2

Make Dash look left and right for 5 times.

There are 2 correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them both?

Puzzle 3

Make Dash work like a traffic light. Each colour should be active for 10 seconds. Once the light turns green, Dash should move forward 1 meter.

There are 2 correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them both?

Puzzle 4

Make dash drive forward until he finds an obstacle.

There are 2 (or more) correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them?

Puzzle 5

Based on what you have learned in Puzzles 1 to 4 above, use this knowledge to come up with a puzzle for a friend your age in another class. Try it out to find out whether it works; ensure that your puzzle is solvable. Provide the answer as though you will act yourselves as the tutor.

Turn Dash into a Security Guard

Puzzle 6

Part A

Your robot has a task. He is a soldier in a war zone and everyday and at all times he has to patrol a marked territory walking from end to another without

stopping and without walking into the set boundaries marked by sacks.

Make Dash walk from one end to the other of the marked territory without bumping into the sacks.

Use cardboard boxes as sacks.

There are over 4 correct answers, how many can you find? (Use your tablet to keep a record of your results and ask the tutors to check these).

Part B

After a month, the rebels lost some of their territory. This meant that Dash had less area to patrol and the sacks were brought closer. The new distance Dash walks from one side to another has decreased. Dash's task remained the same: the robot had to persist on a daily basis to patrol the boundaries and walk from one end to another.

Think: a) The distance has changed; does your programme from Part A to Part B change too?

b) The tutors will inform you of the different solutions obtained within the class; interpret this information and present it as a bar graph

Grand Lottery

Puzzle 7

Dash is able to generate random numbers. He finds himself at the Lottery

Department and Dash is involved in the draw so that it is fair. His role is to generate 5 numbers to create a 5-digit number. This 5-digit number is the winning ticket and its owner is the winner of EUR 1,000,000!!

Get Dash to make this draw of five numbers; as a team you have to give the tutors your 5-digit number.

Annex 2

In a list share with us 3 top tips about collaboration and working with each other. The first tip must be the one which is most important to you.

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Write one more tip about collaboration and working with each other which you know from your personal experience. (If possible this should be a tip which hasn't been mentioned in today's session).

Annex 3

You were asked to find solutions to make Dash behave as a soldier and as a Lottery drawer. In arriving to these solutions you may have been successful or you may have failed (completely or partially) and we wish you to write about how this went by creating a diary post. Imagine you own a diary and you are going to share your feelings with it. Fill in the below as best as you can.

Dear Diary,

Today, at school, I was involved in workshops using Dash. This robot played two roles: being a soldier in a war zone and a Lottery Drawer at the Lottery Department.

I worked in a team. The most challenging moment in working as a team was

I learned from my team members that:

An idea I hesitated to share with my team was

This idea could be useful:

I (succeeded/failed) _____

to solve (one/both/none) _____ of these puzzles. _____

_____ (Mention the names of the puzzles if any).

When I (failed/succeeded) to find an answer or answers I felt: _____

As the friend with whom I share all my secrets, I wish to tell you that my feelings and attitude today following this workshop are:

And, (write anything else which you wish to tell your diary):

Thanks for taking care of my feelings and secrets,

Your dearest friend,

_____ (write your code number here)

Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop

AUTHORS:

ESI CEE Team: Ivaylo Gueorguiev with the support and direct contribution of Pavel Varbanov, Petar Sharkov, Prof. Galina Momcheva, Dr. George Sharkov, Prof. Maria Nisheva, Christina Todorova and Georgi Georgiev

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This workshop inspires students to think and dream about using robotics in real life. The students discuss and learn what a robot is and how robots can be used in everyday context through demonstration and creativity exercises. The activity is specially designed to develop skills as follows:

Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques.

Digital fluency: Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative use of robotics and building and programming a real robot.

Communication: While working in team students build a robot following generic instructions. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot; to correctly connect the robot electronics and to program the robot.

Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.

Robotics is intriguing and fun, which is why we believe it makes a wonderful tool to engage students in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. We know that learning by doing makes children fall in love with creativity and robotics and helps them maintain their in-born curiosity about natural life and technology.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

NO YES Subject:

While creativity through mind-mapping could significantly contribute to the students' ability to learn², structure information and memorize³, the workshop is not directly connected with the formal school curricula.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

5 10 0 10 0 0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Digital fluency: Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative use of robotics and building and programming a real robot. In particular students learn and discuss key robotics elements (technology); construct a robot (technology & engineering) , develop a visual program to control the robot and to execute tasks (technology); develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields
<i>Technology use related</i>	Digital fluency: The technology used by the students include: Arduino microcontrollers; motor drivers; ultrasonic sensors; Scratch or Snap visual programming software.
<i>Social and action related</i>	Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques. Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot to correctly

² A study conducted at Newchurch Community Primary School in Warrington showed a variety of improvements in pupils learning after Mind Mapping was introduced. This evidence includes improved concentration, staying on task for longer periods of time, improved questioning and answering during class discussions and improved independence. (

³ Toi, H (2009), ('Research on how Mind Map improves Memory'. Paper presented at the International Conference on Thinking, Kuala Lumpur, 22nd to 26th June 2009) shows that Mind Mapping can help children recall words more effectively than using lists, with improvements in memory of up to 32%. (Cain, M. E. (2001/2002), 'Using Mind Maps to raise standards in literacy, improve confidence and encourage positive attitudes towards learning'. Study conducted at Newchurch Community Primary School, Warrington.)

	connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot.
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TIME

Duration: 1-2 weeks (8 hours in total)

Schedule: 2 sessions, 4 hours per session

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Students work with Scratch or Snap visual programming software; Arduino IDE, python s2a_fm and pymata are used to connect the robot to a computer and to control it, along with visual interfaces.</p> <p>Additional: BirdBrain Robot Server is used if Finch robot is used for the programming or demonstration games and the Choregraphe suite is used to demonstrate the NAO humanoid robot.</p> <p>Students productions: (i) Scratch code that programmed the robot to go forwards, backwards and stop; (ii) Scratch code that programmed the robot to turn left and right around one of the chains and around the center.</p>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	<p>Robotic Arduino-based tank developed and specifically tailored for children's use by ESI CEE. The customized kit consists of: gearbox; chassis; chains and wheels; Arduino controller; motors driver; breadboard; wires and jump wires; ultrasonic module; Bluetooth module or USB cable; batteries and battery holders, safely designed pins suitable for children's use to avoid soldering.</p> <p>NAO and Finch robots for demonstration are optional.</p> <p>Students productions: tank robot</p>
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	<p>Visual Guide for constructing the robot; examples of Mind Maps.</p> <p>Students productions: mind-maps illustrating different creative applications of robotics.</p>
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	<p>Manual How to connect and program the robot.</p> <p>Mind-map presentation.</p>
<p>Note: the workshop artifacts are uploaded and maintained at: https://github.com/esirobot/practical-robotics-workshop-tank-with-USB-cable. The particular</p>	

workshop was conducted with the artifacts attached as a zip. File

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 8-12 years;
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required. The workshop is designed for “all students in the class”;
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Bulgarian, suitable for students of diverse cultural background, capital city and other cities
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public schools
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Students with the disabilities might need additional support by qualified personnel.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Workshops in school, either in classroom or computer room during regular school time

Physical characteristics: indoor only

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: up to 28 students

Tutors: 2-4; **School teachers:** 1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups
<i>Setting:</i>	The workshop is conducted in a school classroom equipped with at least 7 computers for students and one computer for the tutors. The tables are arranged as “islands” for each team of 4 students. Enough space is left for demonstrations of robots. Large screen and white board with markers are positioned in a way to be visible by the students

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	<p>Through creativity mind-mapping exercises students are motivated to think “out of frame” and to debate about the use of robots in everyday life. They exchange ideas and summarize them on a team level.</p> <p>While building and programming the robot students maintain dialogue about how to complete next steps. They debate and negotiate when they have doubts or have to fix any mistakes. When the robot is built and programmed students have to agree on how to play with the robot during the free time allocated for games and experiments.</p>
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<i>Relationships</i>	Tutors promote collaborative behavior within the teams and between the teams.
<i>Roles in the group</i>	The roles in the team are designer/builder – the student who builds the robot or programs the robot and team members who support the work as they directly help the builder or provide advices and check the quality of the work. The tutor requires that the students change their roles after every step of building the robot or programing it, so every student could gain experience by changing different roles within the team.
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	<p>During most of the time the tutors facilitate the activities through asking questions and maintaining debates and discussions. The tutors provide guidelines and explain definitions at the beginning of the robotics session when the key elements of the robots are taught and at the beginning of the creativity session when the key principles of mind-mapping are explained. In both cases instructions are provided after and if needed and are based on open discussions or direct questions and are followed by demonstrations and exercises.</p> <p>The principle which the tutors convey is “let’s first think how to solve the problem before asking the tutor”. When support by the tutors is essential the tutors ask questions but do not provide direct instructions.</p>

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work as a team to the tutors, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	<p>One of the creativity games includes a planned conflict, aiming to question students’ preconception of problem-solving. Students face a contradiction between the possible solution and their internal boundaries, set by themselves.</p> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-left: 20px;"> <p>The game consists of 9 dots. Students are asked to cross out all the dots with 4 straight lines. The solution requires that students should inevitably draw outside the dots (allegorically outside the box).</p> </div> </div> <p>In another exercise, the students have to generate ideas about the applications of a paper clip and the non-applications of a paper clip (what you can’t use a paper clip for). Students have to think within their team. Normally, students are thinking only about metal paper clips, which has not been stated in the task itself. With a little help from the tutor, they realize that the paper clip could be made of different materials, could be of different sizes, could be hollow, etc. and they realize that there are no “non-applications” of the paper clip. The goal of this game is to make children realize that their creativity is limitless and they should not base their ideas on mere practicality or</p>
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	preconceptions, but that it is important to train your creative thinking nevertheless.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	The focus of the workshop is to stimulate creativity, communication and collaboration while building a robotic kit. The students are encouraged to unleash their imagination and creativity and generate ideas about what a robot could do and present their ideas as Mind Maps. At the end of the workshops students have free time to play with the robots and to experiment with them.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Although the robot has a predefined design, the way that the visual guide for its construction is presented, suggests that the students have to make experiments, to discuss within their team the possible solutions and reach conclusions within the group based on communication and experimentation. The visual guide provides just pictures of different stages of the building process and no instruction on how to connect parts. The same approach is applied when programming the robot – the students have to first “discover” what the movements of the motors should be for the robot to turn left and right around the opposite chain and around the center and then program it.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

Total duration of the activities will be within 8 hours. The programming session, during which the students develop code and animate the robots is used as a buffer in case other activities took less or more time for the students to complete.

Orchestration: teams of 3-4 students per table, equipped with one computer, preferably laptop with the required software installed (see [digital artifacts](#) for more information), and one robotic kit; enough free space in the center of the room for demonstrations; demo robots such as NAO; omnidirectional models, the Finch Robot or mobile telepresence robots;

Description:

MODULE 1 INTRODUCTION AND PRE-EVALUATION (40 MINUTES)

The tutors introduce themselves, explain what they do and why they came to the school. They also explain what they find fascinating about robots and what is the task for the specific day. Next they ask from the students whether they like robots, if they have had any experience with them in order to informally introduce themselves by their interest within the topic of robotics. The purpose is to become familiar with the students get to know some names and show that they are interested to learn with whom they are going to work with.

Following that, the rules and safety instructions are explained:

Rules:

- Everybody listens to the others and respects their ideas.
- No direct competition, lets cooperate and have a fun.
- Questions and strange ideas are highly encouraged.
- We are tutors but also your friends – everybody can argue with us regarding the content but not regarding the discipline.
- The parts you are given are only for construction, not for eating.

- Handle everything with attention in order to remain safe.
- Respect other team members' opinions and let everyone work equal amount of time – we all have to learn.

Tutors try and emphasize to the students that in order to complete the task they need to collaborate with other students. The work of one person, no matter how good it is, is not going to be better than the collective work. Disagreement in a group is not a bad thing, instead it can be very productive if the group knows how to handle it.

Handling disagreement involves:

- a) asking questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do);
- b) asking questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?);
- c) being open to trying new ideas;
- d) respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate;
- e) the group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion);
- f) trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work;
- g) try to engage all group members in the task.

Students fill out Pre-Workshop Questionnaire and complete the Draw a Scientist evaluation activity.

MODULE 2 WHAT IS A ROBOT (40 MINUTES)

The tutors ask students “what is a robot” to generate ideas what are the key components of the robots. Once an idea is generated by the students the tutors encourage other student to comment and contribute.

After most of the interested students have a chance to contribute the tutors use one of the demo robots to conclude the key elements such as processors, drivers, actuators and sensors. They demonstrate those parts with the robotics kits and give a chance to the students to examine the parts. Analogy with nature is provoked. E.g. the tutors explain how the ultrasonic sensor works and ask students to name an animal that uses the same principles (bat; dolphin, etc.). Finally, the origin of

“robot” terms is explained.

The tutors ask student if they have a robot at home and to guess different types of robots. Once a student explains his/her ideas the tutors encourage other students to comment and contribute. The tutor structures the students’ ideas to main categories such as industrial robots; home robots; humanoids; drones; toys and others. Then tutors ask student to further elaborate how their home appliances (automatic washing machine, autonomous vacuum cleaner, etc.) are similar to the robots. At the end the tutors ask students to further elaborate ho the robots will change when they grow up.

MODULE 3 CONSTRUCT A ROBOT (120 MINUTES)

The tutors remind the students about the **safety instructions**:

- Do not put the parts in your mouth – this can cause serious injury;
- Do not try to connect batteries before the instructors check the model for short circuits – the robot can cause fire.
- Be careful when using the jump wires and the pins – you can hurt yourself.

Students are once again encouraged to:

- learn from their experience and mistakes;
- have fun and play;
- discuss and respect the ideas of the others;
- shift their roles within the team after each step;
- contribute constructively to the team
- be helpful and make necessary compromises to accomplish the task
- solve the problems by themselves and to ask for tutors support only after they did their best to find a solution.

Students are introduced to the robotic kit. Tutors say a few words about the parts and what are the parts used for. They show an example of the built robot, so as to motivate the students and give them an idea towards what they are working on. Tutors give recommendations for work, including, to put

the small parts in the lid of the box in which the kits come. The application of some tricky parts is demonstrated by the tutors – for instance the Patafix glue and the pins.

Students build the robot using visual guides on printed cards or slideshow on computers. Instead of employing direct instruction to introduce a concept or explain an example, constructionist methodology is applied to provide students with an example and ask them to test it and observe.

MODULE 4 ROBOT'S TOUCH (40 MINUTES)

Once the models are built the researchers demonstrate in action different type of robots such as NAO, VGo, omnidirectional robots or maybe the Finch robot and facilitate a Q&A session. When a student has a question the tutors first ask other students if they can answer the question and then elaborate based on the discussion.

During or after this and the previous module, students are asked in groups questions on what was most difficult for them during this session or what they consider to be their biggest achievement. They are asked questions about teamwork as well.

MODULE 5 LET'S IMAGINE (120 MINUTES)

The tutors ask students to discuss what is creativity and how important is it in the real life. They are using the predefined games and demos to demonstrate different aspects of creativity. Furthermore, tutors ask questions about the difference between a robot and a person ultimately reaching the conclusion that a person's brain and the person's heart is what ultimately makes a difference. Children are led to reach the consensus that the brain is that thing that helps us remember and help us make associations between different concepts. The heart on the other hand is what leads us to be imagine things and to apply our imagination to ultimately invent new things and new applications of things. Combined with the brain, they are what makes us creative.

Using games to illustrate the functions of the brain and the heart, children reach the point of creating a Mind Map on the applications of robotics in different aspects of their life. Different games include:

The intimidation of what seems impossible:

A memory game in which students try to remember 15 numbers in the order they were said by the lecturer. The game aims to show children that although a regular person is usually not able to remember this by hearing it only once, when you come to exercise your brain's creativity and memory potential every day you build the capacity to do that. This exercise also aims to show that the brain's potential is somewhat limitless and by making a conscious effort your brain's ability becomes limitless.

Thinking "out of the frame" while generating and constructing new ideas:

The game consists of 9 dots. Students are asked to cross out all the dots with only 4 straight lines. The solution requires that students should inevitably draw outside the dots (allegorically outside the box). This game aims to convey the idea that the only thing that puts borders to our capacity to solve problems is our brain itself. Listening carefully and thinking creatively is what helps us to find solutions as much as the knowledge we already have accumulated.

The paper clip

Students have to generate ideas about the applications of a paper clip and the non-applications of a paper clip (what you can't use a paper clip for). Students have to think within their team. Normally, students are thinking only about metal paper clips, which has not been stated in the task itself. With a little help from the tutor, they realize that the paper clip could be made of different materials, could be of different sizes, could be hollow, etc. and they realize that there are no "non-applications" of the paper clip. The goal of this game is to make children realize that their creativity is limitless and they should not base their ideas on mere practicality or preconceptions, but that it is important to train your creative thinking nevertheless.

Using the mind-mapping technique to generate ideas: Students are shown as a conclusion from the games that it is easier for us to remember things and to generate new things by stimulating our brains with structure and color. Based on the conclusion from the games the tutors conclude and demonstrate the key principles of the Mind Mapping technique. Then the students construct their first simple mind map.

Create a Mind Map about the applications of robotics in everyday life: students are asked to generate ideas about use of robots and to present them as Mind Maps. They are encouraged to use drawings and colors to put emphasis on their ideas and to differentiate branches of ideas, exercising the importance of structure. Students work individually but are encouraged to share their ideas within a team and help each other to come up with ideas, exercising their collaboration skills in terms of an individual task.

MODULE 6 PROGRAM THE ROBOT (90 MINUTES)

The tutors remind the students the safety instructions and the workshop approach from Module 3. This is very important in case that the Module 3 was conducted in different day.

The tutors explain to the students the basics of programming with Scratch and how specific blocks are used to control the motors and the sensor.

Each team uses the “set up” block to switch on the robot. The teams are left to play with the ultrasonic sensor and to measure distance between the sensor and obstacles.

The rationale of this activity is to familiarize students with the functioning of the robots and the importance of sensors. This activity is performed by every group. Then the tutors demonstrate how to use events (key boards push) to create simple program – a robot moving forward. Students are left to construct and program concepts how to control the motors to move the robot backward and to stop it. Once students complete this task, they are asked to “discover” how to control the motors in order the robot to turn left and right, to go backwards (using negative numbers), to turn around the opposite chain and around the robot’s center and create a separate program for each of these activities.

Instead of employing direct instruction to introduce a concept or explain an example, following the constructionist methodology, the tutors focus on providing students with an example and ask them to test it and observe the behavior of the robot with the aim of identifying the role of specific programming concepts and structures such as logical thinking and functions. This is a teaching and learning process which makes use of the affordances of digital constructionist environments where the observation of the generated behavior (i.e. feedback) its analysis provide the grounds for the formulation of a hypothesis about how the robot works. The students are expected to generate ideas, based on the examples they are provided, how the robot can move in different directions by exercising logical and proportional thinking.

Based on the planned length of the module students might be asked also to complete other tasks such as: use sequence of commands to program the robot to go through predefined route; practice cycles

to make the robot “dancing”, program the robot to turn on predefined angle or to go to predefined distance, etc.

Finally, the students are left to play with the robot or to experiment with the variety of comments that they have created or even generate new once to fit their ideas and goals. Tutors are working with groups, asking them questions to guide them towards solutions.

Some groups even find solutions to quite everyday problems, such as back pain, as illustrated below. Students stated that they created the first robot that cures back pain and were willing to showcase their robot in action. This is an example of how children’s creativity not only helps them find a new outlook on things, but also motivates and inspires them to create and maintain their interest in inventing.

MODULE 7 FINAL EVALUATION (30 MINUTES)

Evaluation session is held for students to present their achievements and evaluate their experience.

Group and/or individual interviews are conducted and students fill out Post-Workshops Questionnaires.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

REGARDING DIRECT WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES

<i>Objective</i>	Activities to achieve the objective	Assessment (evaluation) procedures
<i>Subject related – technology, engineering, science</i>	Digital fluency: Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative use of robotics and building and programming a real robot. In particular students learn and discuss key robotics elements (technology); construct a robot (technology & engineering), develop a visual program to control the robot and to execute tasks (technology and mathematics); develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields	Opinions about STEM as well as preconceptions about scientists, scientists and robotics are measured by the pre and post workshop questionnaires as well as visualized through the draw a scientist exercise. Mind Maps are used as tools to boost and visualize creativity, skills. Group interviews assess and record concepts regarding collaboration and digital fluency. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Digital fluency: The technology used by the students include: Arduino microcontrollers; motor drivers; ultrasonic sensors; Scratch or Snap visual programming software.	Photos and videos of successfully constructed and programmed robots. Attention to detail and peer review during those processes is a possible mechanism of evaluating the success of a team. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
<i>Social and action related</i>	Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques. Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.	Group discussions/interviews and focus group interviews are used as a tool to record students' progress, opinions and changing attitudes, along the with questionnaires. Attitudes towards team work are recorded and measured with the questionnaires as well. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how	Group discussions and interviews, alongside with photos and videos are used to record children's attitude and

	to construct the body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are aware made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot.	productions. All forms of evaluation, applied within the ER4STEM projects are further relevant for measuring this objective. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
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REGARDING RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND TOOL FOR ASSESSMENT

Research Question	Assessment Method or Tool
Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Draw a scientist ● Pre-Questionnaire ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections ● Tutor Observations & Reflections
Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections
<p>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</p> <p>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learners' experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-Questionnaire ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections
Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections ● Tutor Observations & Reflections

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-3a

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 19.02.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 26.02.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

No significant incidents were observed.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

No significant incidents were observed.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;

Students performed iterations and similarity to derived the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to complete their second mind map on applications of robotics in the future. Some students didn't manage to finish or even start their second mind map.
- Maybe in a longer workshop with a similar activity plan we could implement more games with the ultrasonic sensors and sequences of actions to show students more advanced programming concepts, along with sensor work.

- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Communicate breaks beforehand.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-3b

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 07.03.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 12.03.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

No significant incidents were observed.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

No significant incidents were observed.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;

Students performed iterations and similarity to derived the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to complete their second mind map on applications of robotics in the future. Some students didn't manage to finish or even start their second mind map.
- Maybe in a longer workshop with a similar activity plan we could implement more games with the ultrasonic sensors and sequences of actions to show students more advanced programming concepts, along with sensor work.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Attend a parents meeting or talk directly to parents, who are not familiar with the robotics activity prior to the workshop, so as to relieve some of their worries about the research and leave them with a more positive outlook towards the robotics activities.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 1

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-3d

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 20.03.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 27.03.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

This class had a generally negative attitude towards the educational robotics workshop. Most of the parents didn't allow us to even take photos of their children, which resulted in us making very few photos only in selected groups. We also didn't do any interviews with this class.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

There was not much that could be done during the workshop itself. We did manage to win the children over to "our side" and they appreciated the activity a lot. However, we were still not able to collect the amount of evaluation data that we normally would.

I think a great solution would have been prevention – in the sense that we take the time to attend parent meetings or just generally communicate the activity more efficiently to the parents and the teachers.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;

- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;

Students performed iterations and similarity to derived the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to complete their second mind map on applications of robotics in the future. Some students didn't manage to finish or even start their second mind map.
- Maybe in a longer workshop with a similar activity plan we could implement more games with the ultrasonic sensors and sequences of actions to show students more advanced programming concepts, along with sensor work.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Attend a parents meeting or talk directly to parents, who are not familiar with the robotics activity prior to the workshop, so as to relieve some of their worries about the research and leave them with a more positive outlook towards the robotics activities.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 2

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-3e

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 19.03.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 26.03.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

There were two unexpected notable incidents that occurred during this workshop. The first was that generally, this class had a relatively negative initial attitude towards the activities. They allowed

photos only in certain groups and did not allow interviews at all. This is not the only workshop where this happened this year, but no satisfying explanation on why it was like that was received.

The other interesting thing that has happened only a few times before, is that during the second session, one of the students brought his own robot, that he built himself at home to show in front of the class. The robot was a humanoid LEGO robot that could move, shoot balls and talk. Students were very impressed, and it turns out that most of them didn't know that their classmate was interested in robotics or technology at all. They asked him questions about what and how he did to achieve that and a very natural discussion arose, which was very productive, and I feel motivating for the other students.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

At one point during the workshop, this student came and told me that he has built a robot before and that he actually brought it with him today at school just to show it to us. I asked him if he would like to demonstrate what he did in front of the class and he eventually agreed.

We gave this class less time to program the tanks and fill in their questionnaires, just so this student could demonstrate his robot. However, it turned out to be a good thing, as students themselves started asking this boy questions and became interested in how he did what he did.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;

Students performed iterations and similarity to derived the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to complete their second mind map on applications of robotics in the future. Some students didn't manage to finish or even start their second mind map.
- Maybe in a longer workshop with a similar activity plan we could implement more games with the ultrasonic sensors and sequences of actions to show students more advanced programming concepts, along with sensor work.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Attend a parents meeting or talk directly to parents, who are not familiar with the robotics activity prior to the workshop, so as to relieve some of their worries about the research and leave them with a more positive outlook towards the robotics activities.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 3

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-3g

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 06.03.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 12.03.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

This class was very difficult to work with because of two reasons. The class teacher and the English teacher of this class openly disapproved of our activities. Reportedly, they disliked the fact that our workshops were carried out within regular school time, in two 4-hour sessions, causing them to have to rush through the material to compensate for the time lost. They considered our activity as useless and never missed a chance to say this to the students, even in front of us. The English teacher was very passive aggressive during the short period of time when she was attending the workshop. She made fun of our speech, repeating it mockingly, she also made comments such as “This is bullshit, and I don't see why you waste the students' time to talk to them about this, they will never use this in their life ever” (regarding the mind-mapping session) or “What they are saying is that they are here because they have to report a project, not because they want to teach you robotics” (when we explained about the evaluation process). She was constantly paying attention if we were making photos – at one moment I looked at my phone to see about a message I received and she asked “Did you just secretly take a picture?”. At the beginning of the workshop the class teacher showed us a written request by several parents to not take any photos or videos during the workshop, so no photos, videos or interviews were made. In the whole class only 3 or 4 children were allowed by their parents to be filmed.

The second thing that made the workshop really difficult was the parents of the students' attitude towards the workshop. They were calling us on the phone saying that they refuse their child to participate in the workshop and they are doubting if they should even send their children at school this day. They were obviously influenced by those two teachers' opinion as they used sentences like “this activity is useless, those children should be studying their regular school material during this time”. Most of the parents who called were fathers of daughters – I don't know if this is important in any way but it was noticeable.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

Regarding the parents, some of them called me on the phone I left for contact – when I spoke to them I did manage to calm them down and reason with them or at least with those who had privacy concerns regarding the research. The parents who claimed this activity as useless and that it shouldn't be allowed during school hours were not allowing to be convinced. I facilitated this incident by telling them that these activities are within their school's development strategy and that I am certain that the school is protecting the interests of its students. Furthermore, if I was given the chance to, I would say that this is the third consecutive year in which we carry out such activities within the school and that most children are happy to participate within the workshop, and that participating in the research has nothing to do with participating within the workshop.

It was generally easier to reason with the parents, especially after the first session when some of them called to apologize, saying that their children returned home very happy and inspired, rather than the teachers.

Maybe a good idea for future activity plans would be to include strategies for pre-workshop communication with the teachers and the parents, as well as conducting interviews with some teachers in order to obtain a more clear feedback on their opinion on the workshop.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;

Students performed iterations and similarity to derived the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to complete their second mind map on applications of robotics in the future. Some students didn't manage to finish or even start their second mind map.
- Maybe in a longer workshop with a similar activity plan we could implement more games with the ultrasonic sensors and sequences of actions to show students more advanced programming concepts, along with sensor work.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Attend a parents meeting or talk directly to parents, who are not familiar with the robotics activity prior to the workshop, so as to relieve some of their worries about the research and leave them with a more positive outlook towards the robotics activities.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT 4

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-3v

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 20.02.2018

Workshop end date (second session): 27.02.2018

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

Maybe because this was one of our first workshops with this activity plan for this set of workshops, we didn't manage our time quite too well. Not enough time was left for the students to begin their applications of robotics in the future mind maps and they ended up having only mind maps on the associations with colors.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

We collected the mind-maps that related to associations with different colors and we ended up giving more time than usual to these mind maps, so they became very elaborate and pretty. Students were, however, a bit disappointed, as initially, we promised them that they would keep those mind maps and will be able to work on them further at home and we ended up collecting them.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;

Students performed iterations and similarity to derived the desired result.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to complete their second mind map on applications of robotics in the future. In this workshop we didn't manage to reach the mind mapping on the topic of applications of robotics as we had little time left.
- Maybe in a longer workshop with a similar activity plan we could implement more games with the ultrasonic sensors and sequences of actions to show students more advanced programming concepts, along with sensor work.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.

Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot

AUTHORS

ESI CEE Team: Christina Todorova and Petar Sharkov with the support and direct contribution of Ivaylo Gueorguiev, Pavel Varbanov, Dr. George Sharkov, Prof. Galina Momcheva and Prof. Mariya Nisheva

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

The goal of this workshop is to introduce and exercise mathematical concepts, which are covered in the national school curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade in Bulgarian schools, using programming and robotics.

Participants play 5 different games with the robot. Every game builds on the previous one and is broken down into quests, through which they exercise their knowledge on mathematics and adopt new mathematical concepts by exercising them. Children program to make the robot move and they make the robot move to solve a mathematical problem.

In addition, and of equal importance to the subject of mathematics, this workshop is specifically designed to support and encourage the development of the following skills:

1. Problem solving skills are stimulated by encouraging students to solve different kind of problems in conventional ways, but also to seek innovative ways to find solutions. Children are stimulated to identify and ask significant questions that clarify various points of views and lead to better solutions.
2. Communication is important for the successful outcome of the games. This includes the ability to articulate thoughts and ideas effectively in a group. Groups consist of student of diverse points of view, knowledge and abilities, which requires a certain ability to communicate complex ideas clearly, effectively and patiently.
3. Flexibility and adaptability is a skill which is greatly incorporated on many levels. Students have to be flexible in order to incorporate feedback from other team members and tutors effectively, and furthermore to understand, negotiate and balance diverse views and beliefs to reach workable solutions.

Within the sessions, students are required to shift roles within their group, which consist of different responsibilities, aiming to ensure that flexibility and adaptability skills are fostered. During the second session, students are not reminded to shift roles, which encourages communication, as well as provides students the chance to fall back into the most comfortable role within their team.

Robotics is intriguing and fun, which is why we believe it makes a wonderful tool, in addition to the general school curriculum, for learning mathematics. We know that learning by doing makes children fall in love with mathematics and robotics is the way we visualize mathematics.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Mathematics

This workshop is aligned to and specifically designed in support to the Bulgarian national curriculum on Mathematics for the fourth grade.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	5	0	0	0	10

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	<p>Mathematics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn about and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors; Engage students in brief discussions on different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another; Exercise the use of measuring tools such as ruler and protractor; Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory; Showcase the difference between whole numbers and decimal numbers without going into theory; <p>Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; Students understand that robots are programmable; Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot. Students gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors; Students understand that different sensors serve different purpose; Students understand that sensors are controllable and programmable;
Technology use related	Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch.
Social and action related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability; Foster collaboration skills;
Argumentation and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and

fostering of maker culture:	<p>expressing ideas.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage curiosity, tinkering and experimentation; • The games require the decision-making within a team; • Identifying and solving problems; • Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. • Exercise logical thinking;
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TIME

Duration: 1-2 weeks 6 hours in total)

Schedule: 2 sessions, 3 hours per session

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Desktop version of Scratch visual programming software.</p> <p>A digital artifact of learning will be Scratch project files from teams. Students work only with the desktop version of Scratch in order to avoid connectivity issues.</p>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	<p>The Finch robot by Birdbrain Technologies programmable using Scratch visual programming language.</p> <p>Children program a pre-constructed robot with USB cable and do not build one themselves.</p>
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	<p>Handouts with the game tasks of gradual complexity, featuring example code in case of trouble getting started, as well as bonus games for the fastest teams.</p> <p>Additional materials necessary: markers, color pens, pencils, plain paper of different sizes (A4, A3), protractors, rulers, masking tape.</p>
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	<p>Activity plan, workshop checklists, copy of student handouts, source code, evaluation protocol, interview questions.</p>

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

Sex and Age:	boys & girls, 9-11 years old (fourth grade students)
Prior knowledge:	<p>The workshop is developed as a continuation of the "Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop" for students, so it is expected or recommended for the students to know the very basics of Scratch programming and robotics elements.</p> <p>The workshop is developed taking into account the national curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade. Students should be familiar with third grade level mathematics.</p>

Nationality and cultural background	Bulgarian and Bulgaria-based and Bulgarian-speaking minorities;
Social status and social environment	Mainstream, general education public schools;
Special needs and abilities	Children with physical disabilities or mental disorders might need additional help from specialized personnel according to their special education needs and obstructions, if any. Fluency in Bulgarian language is necessary as game tasks are written in Bulgarian and team communication would most likely be happening in Bulgarian.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school, equipped with a spacious hall with sufficient power outlets, with one computer and one empty table per team with enough chairs for all team members, a whiteboard.

Useful but not required are projector or smart TV screen & internet access.

Physical characteristics: Indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: up to 28

Tutors: e.g. 1-2; **Assistants:** 1 (school teacher)

GROUPING

Grouping criteria	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups based on pre-established friendships or due to disciplinary reasons. However, as this is a workshop intended for recurring participants of the ER4STEM project, students are encouraged to remain in the groups with which they were during the previous workshop.
<i>Grouping criteria</i>	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups based on pre-established friendships or due to disciplinary reasons. However, as this is a workshop intended for recurring participants of the ER4STEM project, students are encouraged to remain in the groups with which they were during the previous workshop.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, engage in dialogues, negotiations, debates; Program, calculate, measure; Test out concepts and ideas; Learning by experiencing;
Relationships	Collaborative;
Roles in the group	Role exchange in the group;
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, monitor, facilitate, encourage;

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in effective communication within their team, with other teams and tutors in order to successfully complete their quests. A problem solving attitude is expected in order to experiment with new ideas to solve problems and observe results in order to improve or change strategy, as well as to maybe accept help and advice from other teams. Students are expected to be flexible and adapt to different roles in terms of responsibility within a team, and to be tolerant and patient with their classmates and the tutors.

Students are supposed to verbally and visually present their solutions to tutors and optionally to demonstrate their work in front of other teams, which requires them to communicate their learning curve and solution in an understandable and clear manner.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	The only designed conflict is to put students in a situation, which contradicts their probable attitude that some roles are more important in a team than others. By promoting flexibility and adaptability within a team, children are encouraged to find a way to show their abilities and be useful for the team in different contexts in terms of role.
Learning processes emphasized:	Emphasis on experimenting with different values and approaches to reach a goal, as well as on analyzing robot results in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this result.
Expected relevance of alternative knowledge	Alternative knowledge will be encouraged as the activity requires logical thinking, interpretation and creativity. Children might apply knowledge from other domains apart from mathematics, such as arts, Mind Mapping and ICT.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

The workshop is divided into 2 sessions of 3 hours each. In each session, students have to complete a given number of games with gradual complexity.

The ultimate goal of the games with gradual complexity is to introduce students to a complex concept or construct. The idea is to start with simple procedures or physical constructions and in consecutive steps add new and new elements in the process.

The duration of the phases described below is estimated by including a total of 30 minutes of breaks between the phases, as required by schools.

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION & PRE-WORKSHOP EVALUATION

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: The tutors introduce themselves, explain what they do and why they came to the school. They also explain what is the task for the specific day and how this is going to build on the Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop, in case children have went through it. Next, they ask from the

students what they remember from the Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop and if they have had any robotics and/or programming experience since then in order to break the ice and put children in the mood for sharing and thinking about robotics, but also to refresh their memory. Children are also asked about their **attitude on mathematics**, whether they like it and whether they think robots are useful for teaching mathematics. The purpose is to become familiar with the audience and vice versa and to explore their existing attitudes.

The researchers introduce themselves as **robot enthusiasts and math-lovers** and explain that in this workshop they will play and work together with the student teams in order to solve several mathematical games using the Finch robot. Tutors explain again the importance of feedback and student contributions which will be used to design even more interesting educational workshops.

Following this, children fill out the **Pre-Workshop Questionnaire** evaluation activity. In case this is the first acquaintance with these students, they are asked to complete the Draw a Scientist evaluation activity. Children are provided with instructions on how to fill out the questionnaires.

After the evaluation, the tutors continue the discussion about robots and ask questions about the parts of the robot. They introduce the Finch robot and ask children to fill out the **“Parts of my Robot handout”** together as a team.

Following that, they are presented with the **workshop rules in the form of a Mind Map**, to refresh their memory from the previous year, in the instance of recurring participants. Every group is handed out a Mind Map with the workshop rules.

The rules are explained and a focus is put on the importance of recording results, on protecting the robot and on switching roles within the team. Tutors try and emphasize to the students that in order to complete the task they need to collaborate with other students. The work of one person, no matter how good it is, is not going to be better than the collective work. Switching roles is of utmost experience to the success of the group and that everyone has to gain experience.

Please note that this is a translation of the Mind Map with the Workshop rules, not the original handout!

Children are encouraged by tutors to find a way to work past possible differences and disagreement within a team, by supporting them on occasions with advice to:

- ask questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do);
- ask questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?);
- be open to trying new ideas;
- respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate;
- the group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion);
- trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work;
- try to engage all group members in the task.

Workshop objectives supported: Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students are aware that different sensors serve different purpose; Foster communication and collaboration skills; practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas; decision-making within a team;

Expected student constructions: Completed pre-workshop evaluation forms, completed introduction handouts.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration, discussion;

Teaching method: Evaluation activities – Instruction; Introduction activities – Discussion and collaboration;

PHASE 2: MOVING OUR ROBOT

Description: Students implement their first programs that consist of sets of programming blocks. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot forwards. The robot is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming, debugging their own programs, getting. After a successful first program, they are asked to write additional code, so as to program

their robots to move backwards, left, right, around its center (left and right) and implement a stop function. For the bonus game, one of the tutors draws on a bigger sheet of paper a route. Every group member is supposed to go through the route, using the robot, with the navigation of the other team members.

Workshop objectives supported: Students are programming the Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch. They are further showcased the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory, as programming the Finch to move backwards requires the input of a negative value for the motors. Students understand that robots are programmable;

This game develops problem solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

This game requires the decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: COLORS

Duration: 70 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary for some reason 5 people is the maximum and 2 is the minimum number of participants.

Description: As the students already know from the introductory activities that the Finch robot has LEDs in his nose, which allows him to shine in different colors. They use a custom block in Scratch to mix colors and thus produce new colors or change the current color. The custom block, is programmable by inserting three variables (for red, green and blue) to, respectively, produce a color.

Students have to produce, along with red green and blue, purple and yellow(-ish), which require them to apply knowledge of color combination or to perform simple experiments. Students know that the higher value they put for one of the three colors, the intensity of the color, produced by the LED light, will change, so they carefully plan out the formation of colors, such as yellow. The bonus games include having to add different colors to different movements – for instance adding red to the set of blocks that program the robot to move forward, thus every time the robot would move forward, its

nose would emit red light. Another option, for groups that are very fast, is to introduce them to the “wait” block, and suggest they put waiting time between different colors to make a “traffic light”.

Workshop objectives supported: With this exercise, students control the LEDs of the robot, by producing and mixing colors of different intensity. Apart from exercising their knowledge in color combination, this game, as the previous one provides them with direct feedback for their actions, namely, every change in the code, results in different colors. This gives them space for experimentation and discovery and students generally enjoy adding colors to their robot as this way it enables them to personalize it to a degree.

This game develops problem-solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, and encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Discussion, experimentation, hypothesizing

PHASE 4: WAIT! AND DO A SEQUENCE OF ACTIONS

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary for some reason 5 people is the maximum and 2 is the minimum number of participants.

Description: Students build on the knowledge, gained during the previous games in order to make a longer sequence of actions with the use of the “wait” blocks in Scratch, in order to gain a smarter command of the robot. In this game, the robot has to complete a series of tasks upon pressing a single keyboard key.

Workshop objectives supported: Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot. Students are applying the skills and principles related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives, similarly to Phase 2.

This game develops problem solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

This game requires a decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation. Teachers refrain from instruction, leaving students at a position where they have to experiment with different ideas and observe results to achieve the desired result.

PHASE 5: MATHEMATICAL GAMES – MEASURING LINES

Duration: 50 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary for some reason 5 people is the maximum and 2 is the minimum number of participants.

Description: Students attach a pencil to their robots using masking tape. With a pencil, they have to draw, by pressing only one button, lines of different lengths. They have to work with a ruler to make the measurements and have to do some precise coding to achieve their goal. This game requires students to discover fractions to achieve precise results.

This game exercises proportional thinking and encourages experimentation.

The last part of the game is devoted to applying this knowledge in a sequence of actions by doing preliminary measurements and experimentation in order to include lines of certain length being drawn by the robot in a complex sequence of actions.

Workshop objectives supported: Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot and exercise proportional reasoning to transfer ideas from a digital space to the analogue world. They use measuring tools to complete the game (ruler) and test out in practice work with whole numbers and decimal numbers (without going into theory) by having to program the “wait time” to achieve precision with their results;

Students are applying the skills and principles related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Experimentation, discussion. Teachers refrain from instructions at this point, leaving students at a position where they have to experiment with different ideas and observe results to achieve the desired result.

PHASE 6: MATHEMATICAL GAMES - MEASURING ANGLES

Duration: 60 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: Tutors engage the students in brief discussions about different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another.

Building on their knowledge about angles, children are briefed on how to measure angles if they don't know already. This is explained by one of the tutors with student volunteers on the whiteboard and to

reinforce the knowledge of the students, a handout with various figures is given out to the children to complete in groups.

After making sure that each group feels comfortable measuring angles, we continue with a game, aiming to make children exercise what they know about angles.

This game is adapted from the www.finchrobot.com and could be viewed here.

For this activity, children are given paper, pencils, colored markers and a protractor. They have to make the Finch turn around one wheel at speed 30. Students measure how far the Finch turns for different wait times, and they use this information to figure out how to calculate the wait time for a particular angle, which is included in the bonus games.

Workshop objectives supported: Students learn more and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors. They are also discussing the different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another;

They use measuring tools to complete the game (protractor and ruler) and test out in practice work with whole numbers and decimal numbers (without going into theory) by having to program the “wait time” to align with the requirements of the game task;

Students are applying the skills and principles related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation.

PHASE 7: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION, FINAL GAMES AND CONCLUSIONS

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: In addition to the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience. Children are asked about their recommendations and their favorite games from both sessions.

Tutors give instructions on how to complete the evaluation papers and thanks children for participating in the workshop.

Workshop objectives supported: Ultimately, students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students are aware that different sensors serve different purpose; They have already worked on the subjects of mathematics and informatics and have covered a lot of subject related material.

The final games are informal and serve as a conclusion to the workshop. They support the objectives related to fostering curiosity, experimentation and collaboration.

Expected student constructions: Code, Post-Workshop Questionnaire, Focus group interview

Teaching method: Evaluation activities – Instruction;

Other activities – Discussion;

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

REGARDING DIRECT WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES

Objective	Activities to achieve the objective	Assessment (evaluation) procedures
Subject related – technology, engineering, science	<p>Mathematics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors; • Engage students in brief discussions on different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another; • Exercise the use of measuring tools such as ruler and protractor; • Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory; • Showcase the difference between whole numbers and decimal numbers without going into theory; <p>Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; • Students understand that robots are programmable; • Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot. • Students gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; 	<p>Opinions about STEM as well as preconceptions about scientists, scientists and robotics are measured by the pre and post workshop questionnaires as well as visualized through the draw a scientist exercise, if applicable. Mind Maps are used as tools to boost creativity and remember rules. Group interviews assess and record concepts regarding collaboration and digital fluency. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors; 	
Technology use related	Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch.	Photos and videos of successfully performed tasks. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
Social and action related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability; Foster collaboration skills; 	Group discussions/interviews and focus group interviews are used as a tool to record students' progress, opinions and changing attitudes, along the with questionnaires. Attitudes towards team work are recorded and measured with the questionnaires as well. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity, tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; 	Group discussions and interviews, alongside with photos and videos are used to record children's attitude and productions. All forms of evaluation, applied within the ER4STEM projects are further relevant for measuring those objectives. Tutor reflections and observations come in support to the assessment of these objectives.

REGARDING RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND TOOL FOR ASSESSMENT

Research Question	Assessment Method or Tool
Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Draw a scientist (if not with a group of recurring participants) Pre-Questionnaire Post-Questionnaire Interviews Team Reflections Tutor Observations & Reflections

Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections
<p>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</p> <p>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learners' experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-Questionnaire ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections
Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections ● Tutor Observations & Reflections

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-4a

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 02.10.2017

Workshop end date (second session): 09.10.2017

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

During the second session of the workshop, a informatics teacher came to join one group of students. The background of this is that in Bulgaria, starting from school year 2018/2019, every school is obliged to teach in the third or fourth grade a new subject, called computer modelling, most commonly taught with Scratch. Most schools envisage that the informatics teachers would be the one to teach computer modelling, but many teachers find themselves unprepared for this.

This teacher has never worked with Scratch before and she found herself having to teach it an year from now, so when she found out that we do a robotics workshop with Scratch, she asked to join us. She sat, however, with the regular class teacher in one of the groups where only 2 boys were present for the current session. The informatics teacher was constantly distracting them, asking them how they know how to do that and what textbook have they used to learn it. She was also telling them what to do and was generally confusing them, which resulted in the team not performing to their own expectations and frustrating them. By far, they managed to solve all problems in all games,

including the bonus games and were very quick, but here they managed to solve only one or two problems within games 3 and 4.

I think this is interesting as the teacher who sat with the group came forward with an instructionist approach and I think she felt that we didn't explain enough to the students (as the group she sat with started to underperform) and that we didn't pay much attention to them.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

One of the tutors went to and ask the teacher to please refrain from telling them what to do and to ask us questions if she had any. We also promised to send her our activity plan and relevant Scratch programming resources, as well as we promised to remain available for further questions and discussions.

We told her that the pedagogical approach we apply in these workshop envisages student experimentation and discussion rather than instruction, and that generally, students are really intuitive and motivated in terms of their programming.

I encouraged her to observe a bit the other groups and see how they are performing. I feel as if she was generally very insecure and uncertain about how she's going to teach this sort of activity to the children and she was overdoing it by distracting the students.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students exercised their knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors;
- They used measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;
- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students applied sequences of actions to program their robot;
- Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students exercised their proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. This way, they also exercised their logical thinking and their understanding of similarity;

Students performed iterations to approach the required results.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity

- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to experiment, have more fun and be able to discover various solutions of the tasks.
- A game with some of the sensors would be nice in future iterations of this activity plan in order to improve the digital fluency of the students and better showcase the function of the various types of sensors along with their programmability.
- Refine the modules and the tasks in order to facilitate a better understanding by third parties.
- Provide the activity plan for further review from teachers.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Communicate breaks in the activity plan.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-4b

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 03.10.2017

Workshop end date (second session): 10.10.2017

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

No significant incidents were observed.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

No significant incidents were observed.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students exercised their knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors;
- They used measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;
- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;

- Students applied sequences of actions to program their robot;
- Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students exercised their proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. This way, they also exercised their logical thinking and their understanding of similarity;

Students performed iterations to approach the required results.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to experiment, have more fun and be able to discover various solutions of the tasks.
- A game with some of the sensors would be nice in future iterations of this activity plan in order to improve the digital fluency of the students and better showcase the function of the various types of sensors along with their programmability.
- Refine the modules and the tasks in order to facilitate a better understanding by third parties.
- Provide the activity plan for further review from teachers.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Communicate breaks in the activity plan.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-4d

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 13.11.2017

Workshop end date (second session): 20.11.2017

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

The groups within this class were generally very friendly and not too competitive with each other. I encouraged teams to invite guests from other groups so that they could show them their progress and how they did what they did, or maybe give advice to others. This worked surprisingly well, especially with the angle measurement. It turns out that this class was not familiar prior to the second session of this workshop, how to measure angles. What we did was, if a group had two or more members who knew how to measure angles, we would send them as mentors to teach the students in other groups.

What was interesting to me was that after the introduction to how angles were measured, when the actual angle measurement game with the robot has started, the “mentors” sometimes returned to the teams they mentored to see how they were doing and give them tips.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

This “incident” was facilitated by encouraging more of it. The tutors were encouraging students who asked how something was done to go to a group that already did that and ask them what how they did what they did.

We tried to convince the students that the groups that perform better are the ones that are open to suggestions and that this is not a competition but a game where every group could support the other groups.

I think the current activity plan could be modified in order to include more guidelines on encouraging this behavior.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students exercised their knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors;
- They used measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;
- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students applied sequences of actions to program their robot;
- Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students exercised their proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. This way, they also exercised their logical thinking and their understanding of similarity;

Students performed iterations to approach the required results.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion

- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to experiment, have more fun and be able to discover various solutions of the tasks.
- A game with some of the sensors would be nice in future iterations of this activity plan in order to improve the digital fluency of the students and better showcase the function of the various types of sensors along with their programmability.
- Refine the modules and the tasks in order to facilitate a better understanding by third parties.
- Provide the activity plan for further review from teachers.
- Make the activity plan shorter – formulate sentences briefly, remove unnecessary parts. This would be necessary in order for this activity plan to be meaningful in the ER4STEM repository.
- Communicate breaks in the activity plan.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-4e

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 14.11.2017

Workshop end date (second session): 21.11.2017

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

Group 7 consisted of 4 boys – two of them had learning difficulties, one of them was Ukrainian and had difficulties understanding spoken Bulgarian language and the third of them had previous experience with robotics. This group seemed clueless most of the time with every student doing their own thing. One of the boys with the learning difficulties was constantly visiting other groups. The other student with difficulties was having trouble concentrating and was mostly doing his own thing. The Ukrainian boy was not understanding programming the robot mostly but not following the written game – he was observing what the robots of the other groups were doing and trying to copy it (he said that it is not because of the games being written in Bulgarian, he could read and understand them). The boy with the previous experience, contrary to my expectations, was not participating that much, he was assisting, but he was more fascinated by the robot itself, rather than the problems that the robot was supposed to solve or the programming of the robot.

I consider this interesting, as it was very noticeable – all children in this group looked very preoccupied with their own thing. When I looked at them, a few times I felt as if they were strangers sat around a dinner table at a restaurant.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

One of the things that we did was for the second session we prepared a copy of the games in Russian for the Ukrainian boy – he did prefer reading them instead of the Bulgarian text, but he did not change his tactics. Regarding the boys with the learning difficulties, I did consult with their resource teacher on how they could be included more efficiently in the game. The teacher went to talk to them and stayed with them for a small portion of the session, but not much changed.

About the boy who was interested in the robot, I did not do anything to facilitate his behavior as I think that when the more geometry related tasks started coming up within the second session, he became more involved with the programming, while the Ukrainian boy remained focused on the problem-solving and he was doing the measuring.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students exercised their knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors;
- They used measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;
- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
- Students gained some knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
- Students understand that robots are programmable;
- Students applied sequences of actions to program their robot;
- Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colors and sequence of colors;
- Students practiced their communication skills in order to formulate and express ideas.
- Students identified and solved problems;
- Students exercised their proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. This way, they also exercised their logical thinking and their understanding of similarity;

Students performed iterations to approach the required results.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Among the possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation made in the classroom, the most prominent are:

- More time is required for the students to experiment, have more fun and be able to discover various solutions of the tasks.
- A game with some of the sensors would be nice in future iterations of this activity plan in order to improve the digital fluency of the students and better showcase the function of the various types of sensors along with their programmability.
- Refine the modules and the tasks in order to facilitate a better understanding by third parties.
- Provide the activity plan for further review from teachers.
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- Communicate breaks in the activity plan.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-4g

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria

Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova

Number of Sessions: 2

Workshop start date (first session): 17.10.2017

Workshop end date (second session): 24.10.2017

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

When there is a group with a student who is not engaging much with the activity, I usually distract them by giving them the camera to record the team's progress. It usually distracts the whole group a bit, but in this workshop, the target group not only did get distracted but also got into a fight over who will use the camera. Target group 1 consisted of four girls and they fought all along the course of the workshop, mainly for taking turns and changing roles. After one of these fights, one of the students refused to participate for longer than usual in my experience, so I decided to distract her with the camera. It turned out that most of the girls found the work with the camera generally more interesting than the work with the robot and wanted to have a go with the camera as well.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

What we did was include the “camera person” within the roles in the group. They had to exchange roles as they usually would, but the person who was responsible for reading and interpreting the problem to the others, as well as checking if they follow the general rules of the workshop was now responsible for recording on video their progress as well.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

- Students exercised their knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors;
- They used measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;

- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts;
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Students performed iterations to approach the required results.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
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- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

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POST ACTIVITY REPORT

Workshop Code: PRW2-3-125-4v

Partner Organization: ESI CEE

Country: Bulgaria
Post activity report completed by: Christina Todorova
Number of Sessions: 2
Workshop start date (first session): 16.10.2017
Workshop end date (second session): 23.10.2017

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

One thing that I considered interesting and worth reporting, is that in this class particularly within the target group, one of the girls started attending programming courses. All of those students are recurring students of ours and we are always happy to see their Scratch projects, which they show to us and hear about what they have been doing. This girl in particular advanced quite a lot, and has recently switched from Scratch programming to JavaScript. She said that she became interested in programming after attending our previous workshop and decided to work with technology when she grows up.

Her attitude changed a lot also. During the previous year, she was a bit bossy, she was overtaking the activity and doing most of the work herself. This year, however, she mostly supported the others and the physical problem-solving. She said that the other children needed also to learn and she already knows how to do most of these things in terms of programming, so she supported with advice and mostly stuck with the roles requiring work with measuring tools, and generally the physical implementation of the program.

In another student group there was one girl who changed groups quite a lot and generally sat wherever there was free space, not engaging much. However, during the previous year she seemed not engaged with the project, she seemed more into this year's activities. She claimed it looked friendlier. The others from the group were entertaining her in between tasks by making color combinations and sequences of color change with the LED lights in the robot's nose.

There was no critical incidents or something that happened that really took us by surprise however. This workshop went really according to the activity plan with very few significant deviations (apart from time taken for certain games).

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

We didn't do much to facilitate the activity. We did speak with the resource teacher who was working with the girl who wasn't participating much, but generally the girl looked involved and happy with all the groups she went to, so we didn't really mind that she would switch groups.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

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Students performed iterations to approach the required results.

From the following concepts, within both sessions of this workshop, students exercised:

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- Communicate breaks in the activity plan.

Design thinking and robotics workshop

AUTHOR:

PRIA

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity is designed for children who have never been in touch with robotics and/or programming. There is no prior knowledge required and it is suitable for children aged 9 and up.

It consists of two main sessions held by the workshop tutors with several activities done by the handicraft teacher in between. The first session focuses on giving them a head start into design thinking and focuses on what kind of robot they want to do. Then the students will build a kind of case for the robot in between the sessions. They will have some support with 3D-Printing and makers. The case for the robot should be built in a way which allows the controller to be mounted on this case. In a basic version, it consists of a plastic plate with wheels and electric motors mounted. The second session explains the basics of programming. The goal is to make the robot drive.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
3	6	0	10	3	0

<input type="checkbox"/> Societal Issues	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life skills	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify).....
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
2	8	0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	No subject
------------------------	-------------------

	<p>Engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand that the product design process starts with a basic idea which must be refined subsequently • Gain some resilience against making errors • Use what is available <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what a robot is and of what parts it consists (motors, sensors, controller) • Understand basic programming concepts, like sequences <p>Art:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Express your ideas through built artifacts which have a beauty of their own <p>Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss your ideas and get feedback from your peers • Observe your robot and adjust your program based on your observations <p>Societal Issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on “How robots can make the world a better place” and in course of thematizing current societal issues <p>Life skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem solving • Working in Teams • Presenting
<p><i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i></p>	
<p><i>Technology use related</i></p>	<p>Hedgehog Educational Robotics Controller</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p>
<p><i>Social and action related</i></p>	<p>Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p>
<p><i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i></p>	<p>practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution</p>
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	A Visual or Python program for the hedgehog controller
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A simple vehicle built by the students with the help of their handicraft teacher

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE**TIME**

Duration: 8 hours

Schedule: 2 sessions with 4 hours each (with other activities in between)

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 8-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Basic reading skills and understanding of numeric values; basic knowledge of working with computers is advantageous
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Not relevant
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Not specifically designed It is used in schools with low social economics level
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Not specifically designed <i>A large percentage of the students have german as their second language and the workshop is held in german</i>

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Open space for testing and building the robots, notebooks or computers, projector

Environment: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION**POPULATION**

Students	Tutors	Assistants
Up to 12	1	0
Up to 16	1	1
Up to 20	2	0
Up to 25	2	1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No criteria
Setting (Style of room):	students in front of computers with one robotic kit available for each group, with view of the blackboard (projector)

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash & Dot
 mBot
 Other Hedgehog

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

observe, communicate, create (design artifacts, code, robot), discuss their ideas with a classmate, present their work in front of their colleague.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	<p>It is possible to not make errors</p> <p>In the first game the students will eventually make an error and experience that it is ok to not be perfect</p> <p>Leave out the sleep() function and show the students that the robot will not drive without it</p>
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	<p>first part: I can be creative build something in a small amount of time</p> <p>second part: trying out their code and adapting it to the task</p>
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Not relevant

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

ACTIVITY 1: INTRODUCTION ON THE LEGO MINDSTORMS EV3 SET

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: plenum discussion

Description: A short introduction of the tutor and all of the students (Name, Age, Knowledge about robots etc.).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: Instruction, Discussion

ACTIVITY 2: CLAPPING GAME – ERRORS HAPPEN

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 10-15 minutes

Orchestration: work in pairs and classwork

Description: First the students form pairs and stand next to each other facing the partner. Afterwards the game is explained. The game itself consists of three movements, which the students need to remember (it was also projected). The movements are to first, slap one's thighs, second, to clap, third, to stamp. This three movements must be done recurrently by the pair while alternating between the two students. After student 1 slaps his/her thighs, student 2 claps; then student 1 stamps and next student 2 slaps his/her thighs; after which student 1 claps and then student 2 stamps; and so on.

To complicate the task and to attain more mistakes, the game rules are changed after some time. The time until the change is decided by the trainer and depends on how difficult the activity is for the students. The new rule changes only the second movement, from clapping, to instead saying the number "two". The aim of the activity is to give the students the feeling, that making mistakes is not bad but rather something which is ok to happen to promote a more freely idea development process. Thus, the students are told to start laughing or cheer when errors occur to promote this. During the activity, the trainers try to emphasize that making mistakes is more than welcome during the task and in general.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Life skills

Teaching method: Demonstration with exercise

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: cheering, laughing

ACTIVITY 3: DESIGN AND MAKE GLASSES FOR A SCIENTIST

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 50-60 minutes

Orchestration: work alone, share your ideas in pairs

Description: The students are asked about what they know about scientists and what characteristics a scientist needs to have. Afterwards the students get boxes with different materials like wrapping paper, drinking straws, paper plates, pipe cleaners, sticky tape ... and the task to create a pair of glasses in 2 minutes. The time restriction should help them in trying out the first ideas which came to their mind. The time can be extended to 5 mins which is advisable for younger kids. After they built the glasses they are asked to improve their glasses to be suitable for a scientist with the same time restriction as before. Finally, the students are asked to explain their creation to their partner from the previous task. If the students had ideas they were not able to build they are also encouraged to explain these parts to their partners.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Art, Life skills

Expected student constructions: a pair of glasses suitable for a scientist made of the given materials

Expected forms of student dialogue: reciprocal explanation and exchange of their ideas (in pairs)

Teaching method: problem based

ACTIVITY 4: DESIGN A ROBOT WITH SOME RESTRICTIONS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 20 minutes

Orchestration: work in pairs

Description: The students are asked to form pairs and are then presented with three stacks of cards. Each student pair must draw a card from each stack. The stacks represent three attributes of a robot they must design.

The first stack of cards consists of locations where the robot should operate. The locations we used were: underwater, in a bus, in a dark forest, on an airplane, on holiday, in school, at home, in the shopping mall, in the bathroom, going to bed, at the rubbish dump, in the cinema, in the garden, by a birthday party, in the kitchen, in the hospital, in a swimming pool, in space.

The second stack of cards consists of persons or roles the robot should assist. We used the following roles: superhero/superheroine, grandma/grandpa, superstar, teacher (m/f), brother/sister, baby, doctor (m/f), pet, yourself, astronaut (m/f), president (m/f), police officer (m/f), fire fighter (m/f), ballet dancer (m/f).

The third stack of cards consists of restrictions the robot has. We used the following restrictions: it must be so small, that it fits into your trouser pockets, his/her mother must hate it, his/her mother must love it, it must be as cheap as possible, it must be as expensive as possible, it must have sleeves, it must fit under your bed, you must be able to hide it from your parents, it must be movable, it must be the favorite color from your person, it must be able to be carried around, it must have three legs, it must have wheels, it must be fluffy

The aim of the cards is to get the students to think in about what different shapes and tasks a robot could have. Again, they have a limited time to design and build their robot with the different materials they were given.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Art, Life skills

Expected student constructions: a prototype of a robot

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and exchange of ideas

Teaching method: problem based

ACTIVITY 5: PRESENT YOUR IDEAS

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: classroom presentation

Description: The students should present their robot for the whole class. Each team gets 2 to 3 minutes time for their talk. Everything they weren't able to build could be explained.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Science, Life skills

Teaching method: Instruction, experimentation, problem based

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

ACTIVITY 6: WHAT IS A ROBOT – A 3 STEP PLAN

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: classwork

Description: The tutor presents what engineers think a robot is and the three core steps in designing a robot:

- functionality: which problems should the robot solve? Where can you use a robot assistant?
- design: how does the robot looks like? How big is it? Which materials should be used?
- communication: how can you tell the robot what you want? What are the possibilities?

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: instruction with discussion

ACTIVITY 7: WHAT ROBOT DO YOU WANT TO BUILD IN THE LAB

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 60 minutes

Orchestration: individual work and class work

Description: The tutor explains what parts are available to build a robot in the lab. Then the students should imagine a robot they want to built according to the 3 core steps:

- functionality
- design
- communication

To guide the process the students get a worksheet with 3 questions representing the core steps and a room for a drawing at the bottom. After that they need to present what they want to do

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Life skills

Expected student constructions: the drawing of their dream robot

Expected forms of student dialogue: presentation to their fellow students

Teaching method:

ACTIVITY 8: HEDGEHOG DEMO ROBOT AND PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENT

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 40 minutes to 1 hour

Orchestration: work in groups and classwork

Description: During this phase, the students are introduced to various definitions associated with programming, robotic and the hedgehog controller. First the term “programming” is explained and afterwards the terms “Hedgehog Controller” and “Programming Environment” are discussed. Furthermore, the students learn how to work with the Hedgehog demonstration robot and how to program the controller step by step.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Technology

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: instruction, demonstration by example, experimentation

ACTIVITY 9: DRIVING ACTIVITIES

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: 2-3 hours

Orchestration: work in groups and classwork

Description: During this phase, the students had to solve different driving tasks. The first tasks were solved together in classwork until the trainer got the impression that the students could finish the given activities on their own. The number of tasks done together depends on the learning speed of the children. During free work, the students must present each finished task to one of the PRIA trainers or one of the class teachers.

- The robot must drive forward for 5 seconds.
- The robot must drive forward for 2 seconds and afterwards drive backward for 2 seconds.
- The robot should drive forward for two seconds, wait for 2 seconds, and finally drive backwards for 4 seconds.
- The robot must drive a specific distance. The distance the robot should drive is marked on the floor.
- The robot must dance.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Engineering, Technology, Life skills

Expected student constructions: programs which fulfill the given tasks

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion and collaboration within the group

Teaching method: instruction, demonstration by example, experimentation

ACTIVITY 10: ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Duration: Depending on the pacing of the students, approximately 0 - 2 hour

Orchestration: work in groups and classwork

Description: Depending on the pace of learning of the students, additional exercises are possible to be done by the different groups. Which activities as well as the number of executed activities are decided by the PRIA tutors.

- **Square and “for“-loops:**
First the students get told to let the robot drive a square with the until now learned knowledge. Afterwards the concept of “for“-loops is explained and applied to the previous task.
- **Digital sensors and “while“-loops:**
During this exercise the students learned the usage of programming a tactile sensor using the programming concept of “while“-loops.

- **Save the world:**

The students had to think about a robot capable of making the world a better place. Afterwards they had to modify the construction and the software of the robot to fit their concept. After completing their robot, the students presented their work in front of the class.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Depending und the individual task - Engineering, Technology, Societal issues

Expected student constructions: programs which fulfill the given tasks

Expected forms of student dialogue: presentation to their fellow students

Teaching method: instruction, demonstration by example, experimentation

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	no
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Slide set

Assessment of the worksheet in Error! Reference source not found.

Presentation of the task to the teacher

Presentation of their robot and their program to the whole class in Activity 9: Driving activities or Activity 10: Additional activities

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Interest of older students

To us it was unexpected, that even older students seemed to have fun making things out of the given handicraft materials (activities "**Design and make glasses for a scientist**" and "**Design a robot with some restrictions**"). This was unexpected, since we were afraid that some students might think that the activities are for younger children and that they are too old for something like this, since similar things already happened when older students had to fill out the form "Draw a Scientist".

Relative dry theory during session 2

During the second session the students seemed less concentrated compared to the first session. We believe that the reason for this might be that this session included large theory sections.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Interest of older students

Since our fears did not come true, the tasks never became critical and thus did not influence the class. There was also no need for the class teachers or the PRIA trainers to intervene.

Relative dry theory during session 2

During the second session the students seemed less concentrated compared to the first session, we suggest to change some of the driving activities to more creative approaches such as the “Save the word” task or the “Robotic theater” which was currently only done when student groups finished early.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Sense of time

During the activities “**Design and make glasses for a scientist**” and “**Design a robot with some restrictions**” we noticed that the primary school students seemed to have problems estimating how much time has already passed and how much time they had still left for finishing the task. To us this was very interesting, because we did not expect the students to be surprised when the time ran out.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Sense of time

Due to the missing sense of time, we reminded the students repeatedly of the remaining time.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

During the first session the focus lied on the concept of “Design thinking”. They learned about the following topics:

- Handling of mishaps (CLAPPING GAME – Errors Happen)
- Design and prototyping of given problems under time and material restrictions
- Presenting
- 3 step plan for designing robots

The students learned to work with the Hedgehog demo bots and in course of this the programming with the graphical or textual programming environment. They learned things about the following topics:

- Introduction to the programming environment
- Programming the robot to solve different driving tasks

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

- Shorten the phase “Driving activities” to provide more time for more creative approaches, where the groups need to work on their own
- Prepare sheets with additional tasks and topics for faster students and students with prior knowledge

Exploring planet Ektonis

AUTHOR:

Mavrantzas Nikolaos

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Activity is an introduction to robotics. Students will learn how to create a robot with LEGO WeDo 2.0 kit and how to control-program it with Scratch.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Robotics

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
6 7 0 10 2 3

Societal Issues Life skills Other (please specify).....

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10)
6 10 0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Making a LEGO robot and program it using Scratch to make it move. Understand how motors and distance sensor are working and how students can use them with scratch instructions.
<i>Technology use related</i>	a) LEGO WeDo 2.0. kit b) Programming in scratch environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips. Using a blog to interact with other groups and group answer to teacher questions.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given. Programming a robot is something that a student can do and do it well. Use both Test and try and spiral methodologies. Students must follow guidelines.

TIME

Duration: 2 weeks**Schedule:** 4 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Scratch programming language
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A LEGO WeDo 2.0, six wheel, of road exploration vehicle with a free to move arm (adjustment by hand). It uses a motor, a multi color led and a proximity sensor.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Online, step-by-step instructions for construct a robot with lego parts and programming it with scratch. Given examples with small programs.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's instructions are online and public on teacher's blog http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2263

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 10-11 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Basic knowledge of programming concepts with Scratch (Sequential instructions, if-then, wait-until)
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	1 pupil is from Albania and 12 from Greece.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	-

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: in school at the Computer laboratory**Physical characteristics:** indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 13**Tutors:** 1; **Assistants:**0

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Random order
<i>Setting:</i>	3 or 4 students per group. Four groups total. One computer and one lego WeDo kit available for each group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiate.
Relationships	Collaborative (in group), competitive in loose form (with other groups), collaborative in loose form with other groups.
Roles in the group	<i>Not strict</i> roles. If needed a student has to take the role of the team leader.
Support by the tutor(s)	Support, intervene, monitor, facilitate, explain. Scaffolding methodology. For the last and more complicated, activity there is an online page, protected with code, where the students can find the target program in case a team can't finish the activity in time.

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: follow instructions, construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, read others group ideas, and exchange ideas, use teacher blog.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	<p>Students should answer some questions like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) What is a robot; Is A drone a robot; b) Is it possible for 2 different programs to have the same result; c) What is more essential, the construction of the robot or the programming of it; <p>The first impression for making a robot is "OK, we want to do it. But it must be very difficult...". Is it;</p>
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	<p>Emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior.</p> <p>From sequential programming a robot to do the same thing again and again, to programming robot using sensors in order to interact with unknown environment.</p>
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	<p>Physics and especially the result of speed and moving time to the distance traveled.</p> <p>Students are expected to investigate the program of their robot vehicle to achieve the necessary accuracy.</p> <p>They'll realize that in order to work a robot in a proper way a lot of things must be arranged right: distance, speed, background, position and orientation of sensor and dimensions of other constructions.</p>

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 4 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: 2 Introduction videos are shown to students. Childrens are engaged in discussion about “what is a robot” and “why or not they like robots”. They must give their answers as comments to teacher’s blog alongside with a 3rd question: “If you could have a whole room full of lego parts, what kind of robot would you like to make? And why ”.

The LEGO WeDo kit is shown to students and they are introduced to available parts, hub, sensors, motors. They should ask some questions about robots. They must login to the online lessons platform (users.sch.gr/nikmavr) and answer the questions using comments.

Introduction to lego kit parts and their names. Simple presentation how to use the main lego parts (gears, pulleys, axles, wheels etc).

The students must connect their lego wedo hub to their PC via bluetooth. Then they should test the motor and the proximity sensor using the s2bot connection software.

An online scenario (story) is presented to the class. The teams must finish 2 missions with their robots. The robot is going to be used to the planet Ektonis. At this phase the first mission begins.

Students must follow online instructions (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2281) for constructing their exploration 6 wheels vehicle.

The team must answer the questions:

- what was the most challenging part of making the robot
- What name they gave to their robot.
- What improvements would you like to do in order to make your robot better than the other groups robots? After reading the answers of the other groups write your opinion about their answers.

After making our robot we must program it.

Students implement their first program using programming blocks in a row. Now they must be able to connect the lego hub to their pc, test the connection, the motor and that Scratch can be used to control the robot. No loops or selection structures are needed.

Picture: Paper strip 100cmx7cm with two straight routes.

The first program should move the robot on a straight predefined line (red arrows) at the above paper strip. One paper strip is given to each group. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program and ensure that the robot returns to the initial position.

Final the robot must start from (APXH) and move forward. It must stop exactly to the 1st stop (1), wait 3 seconds and then return back to start (APXH). They must test different values for the motor power and the time that motor is on (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2294).

Final the teams must answer (online) to some questions about the 1st mission. (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2357)

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

The students should be able to know what is a robot, how they can make a simple robot with lego parts, how connect it to a pc via bluetooth and program it using Scratch.

Expected student constructions

They should be able to make a robot with lego parts following the step by step instructions.

They must find out how to transfer the rotation from the motor to the wheel.

The students must test the motor axle, the pulley and the back wheels. The front wheels should be able to move over path-holes. The teams should be able to use the program blocks for changing the motor power and configure the duration of the movement in order to send the robot forth and back to a specific point of the straight path.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Group discussion, groups interactions.

PHASE 2: USING VARIABLES AND TIMERS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: After examining the answers of the teams and the programs they made, some explanations must be given and all the misconceptions must be cleared (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2473).

These subjects must be cleared to the students:

- The sequential execution of Scratch block is from top to down.
- The equivalence of programs, even if they have different instructions and that a problem can be solved with different solutions.
- The use of variables.
- The use of timers.

For this reason the groups should:

- answer some questions with given small Scratch programs.
- create a small game using the Scratch timer.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

-Clear misconceptions

- Use timer and variables.

Expected student constructions:

The students are using the robot that they already made. They learn how to change the color of the lego hub led.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: GIVING “SMART” BEHAVIOR: THE USAGE OF SENSORS AND THE “WAIT-UNTIL” INSTRUCTION BLOCK

Duration: 3-4 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A lego arm must be added to the robot in order to support and orientate proximity sensor (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2464).

The students have to:

- make the some obstacles using legos
- program the robot to change the color of hub led if something is in front of proximity sensor
- make the robot to stop using proximity sensor
- make the robot measure the traveling time
- use a time variable in order to return to the start point.

At this phase the students must complete two missions.

1st mission:

- Position the robot in parallel with the paper strip (picture above) at point (APXH).
- Position a Lego obstacle randomly between (APXH) and (3). For our scenario, the Lego obstacle is a energy generator that the robot must sense and turn on by standing near it for 3 seconds.
- Program the robot to start moving till it senses the obstacle using the proximity sensor. Then stop and store the timer value (the moving time) to a variable. Then wait for 3 sec. Use the time variable to return to the starting point.

With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure (wait...until) and also the role of the proximity sensor. In order to check if the program is OK they must change the position of the lego obstacle (generator) and then test that the robot stops, wait for 3 sec in front of it and then return back to start (APXH).

2nd mission:

Students must program a more complex behaviour. The robot must start from (APXH), find and stop at (A), (B) and (Γ) using the proximity sensor. At (A), (B) and (Γ) are positioned 3 generators (lego obstacles) that are standing near the movement path (paper strip). The robot should wait 3 seconds near each generator to turn it on. Then the robot finishes its mission and returns back. With teacher assistance, they recognize the need of using variables. The students must understand how to add values to a variable in order to find the total traveling time (excluding the three stop periods of 3 seconds each) . In order to check if the program is OK they must change the position of the 3 lego columns and test that the robot stops in front of all of them and then return back to start (APXH).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:

The students should learn how to use proximity sensor, variables, wait-until block and how to adjust (by hand) the position of the sensor.

Expected student constructions:

Expand their robot with an arm and a proximity sensor on it.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 5: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step.

- The session is ending with answering on teachers blog the questions: If planet Ektonis is going to be populated, what kind of robots you should make in order to help this process; Some more data for the planet are that it hasn't any oxygen, it has 2 moons and 3 nearby planets.
- What do you think for the other groups answers;
- Which answer do you think is the best and why;

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

For the assessment procedure:

- we took photos and videos of the each robot and how each group program their robotics
- we video recorded the whole class and the focus group
- all the answers of the groups and all the teaching material are online at teachers blog

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

Please describe unexpected and/ or interesting incidents that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

a) At the 2nd session a student (that I knew that it was very good with Lego) of the 1st group didn't come because he was ill. His group was the focus group. I move the camera of the focus group to the 4th group. At the end of the session the 2 to students of group 1 made surprisingly excellent work!

b) At the 3rd and last session which was the last day before Easter holidays, 6 students didn't come to the lab for our last session in robotics. They haven't said anything to me at the previous day when they had one hour lesson in my classroom.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical incident you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

For the b) incident of the previous paragraph:

I phoned to their parents and waited for almost one hour and a half for 2 of them to come to the lab in order to finish our last day activities.

After the Easter holidays I discussed with them and i realised that they didn't wanted to come because they were tired (lot of mind work...) with the 2nd session...

We were late for about 1.5 h so I finished the session without doing the 2nd Mission of 3rd phase.

Evidence of student learning

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

Please indicate specifically what your students learned regarding STEM choosing from the concepts listed below

Iteration

Proportion

Variables

Rate of change

Similarity

Symmetry

Periodicity

Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

- More steps.
- Add the usage of the tilt sensor.
- Use gears instead of pulleys.
- Combine all the robots of all groups to a final mission in order to make all groups collaborate to the same mission.

Building a robot and making it smart

AUTHOR (ACTIVITY RESEARCHER): Marios xenos (UOA)

DISCUSSION RESEACHER: Evrikleia Panagiotou (UOA)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Make an autonomous system (vehicle) that disposes garbage at a dump

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science (0-10) 0 Technology (0-10) 10 Business (0-10) 0 Engineering (0-10) 6 Arts (0-10) 2 Mathematics (0-10) 2

Societal Issues (0-10) 5 Life skills (0-10) 10 Other (please specify)..... (0-10) 0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Introducing basic robotic characteristics and build an autonomous vehicle.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in LEGO programming environment, assembling LEGO sensor and motors
<i>Social and action related</i>	Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other "makers".

TIME

Duration: 3 sessions

Schedule: 2 1/2 hours per session

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego programming environment.
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	a simple vehicle with LEGO Mindstorms NXT
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Electronic manual with step-by-step instructions for the construction, Lego electronic manual,
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 10-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge of programming concepts. One student has basic previous experience on LEGO robotics
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Voluntary activity at non-profit organization "ARTFYGIO" (Ilion – Athens) that organizes educational activities. Participants come from local primary and middle schools.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 16

Tutors: 2

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Students that known each other before the workshop, chose their partners. In other cases the groups consisted of same-aged members trying to keep mixed-sex groups
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<i>Setting:</i>	Students in front of computers with one lego NXT kit available for each group and online platform for discussion
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INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	pre-defined roles defined by students, emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate, intervene, monitor

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct the robot, observe its behavior, communicate inside and outside their group, exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	misconceptions about what a robot can “understand”, misconceptions about robot “intelligence”
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis a) on how different programming structures affect the robot behavior b) on how a robot acting in real world in contrast with what is expected to do
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Physics laws can affect the result of robot behavior

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION, ASSEMBLAGE, EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 ½ hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about robotics and how a robot could help to deal with environmental issues e.g. in a recycle facility. Students are introduced to available parts and motors. They are assembling a vehicle - robot following online instructions. They are writing their first program bringing the vehicle into life and make it to move on a virtual rectangular on the floor. The length of each side is 1 meter and students trying to keep the robot in the desired length. The aim here is to get familiar with basic programming structures and in particular with “sequential programming”. They are facing two real issues: a) How the real distance on the floor is related to distance parameter on the program b) How a robot can turn 90 degrees as it cannot understand “degrees” by default.

Objectives:

Thinking and discussing about robotics. Assembling a robotic vehicle

Expected student constructions:

A robotic vehicle

Expected forms of student dialogue:

“non-technical” vocabulary, disagreements, dialogue about assumptions

Teaching method:

Discussion, Instructions, experimentation

PHASE 2: COMMUNICATION WITH REAL WORLD (INTRODUTING SENSORS)

Duration: 2 ½ hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students are engaged in discussion about impressions, expectations and difficulties they faced so far. They are asked to put a colored marker on the vehicle in a way that marks the route on the floor. The marked shape on the floor challenges the students to improve the movement of the robot. They also have to solve a construction issue in order to have the marker stable and functional. Subsequently, they discuss how a marked path could be useful for a real robot in environmental issues. Then, they are asked to assemble and connect an ultrasonic sensor on the robot in a way it can detect objects in front of it. Tutor gives them a predefined program with a simple loop. The program includes one “move” block that makes robot moves until it detects an object. They have to modify the program in such a way that the robot moves until detect an obstacle at 20cm away and then it turns and moves away. In this phase, students are facing two new issues: a) Robot detects the obstacle in different distances each time it runs the program. It is needed to find the reason for this “malfunction” b) How can they measure or calculate the distance that robot covers and set the proper parameters on the program?

Objectives: Assembling a sensor, programming the robot

Expected student constructions: Marker placement, assemblage of ultrasonic sensor

Expected forms of student dialogue: “more technical” vocabulary, discussion and debate in the group

Teaching method: Introduction to sensors by demonstration, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: ENHANCING THE “SMARTNESS” OF THE ROBOT

Duration: 2 ½ hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students upgrade their programs in order the vehicle avoid any obstacle by turning the vehicle and continue in different direction. Then, they place again markers on the robot and try to paint on the floor using their hands or bodies as an obstacle. Subsequently, they asked to build an additional frame in order to hold a ball as the vehicle moves around. Then they have to program the robot to move forward for specific distance, then turn and climb on a ramp until the ball falls down on a basket at the end of the ramp. In this final phase they are asked to make their robots really “smart”; not just avoid an obstacle and stop. Now they have to use their experience to program the robot to

move with precision and stop. At the end of the ramp there is a wall in order students themselves take the final decision how to make the robot stop at the correct spot. They can program the distance or they can use ultrasonic sensor to detect the wall. In this phase, students work in their groups, discuss the available solutions and decide which one should follow. They may have to improve the construction in order the sensor not to interfere with the movement and sense the ramp wall correctly.

At the end of this phase students discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in the evaluation questionnaire and tutor interviews the focus group.

Objectives: make the robot autonomous, sense the environment, programming the sensor

Expected student constructions: Improved vehicle with sensor

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

The activity is designed in a way to provide a continuous self-assessment procedure. In every part of activity, in each single task the result indicates the outcome and the success of students' actions. In order to keep the participants' interest high and to avoid possible disappointment in case of failure, the tutor provides additional help and challenges if it is needed. In other words, the main goal of the activity is to introduce robotics and programming issues through social engagement and creative tasks. Tutor and students are able to identify the progress and outcomes in each phase without explicit assessment procedures.

POST ACTIVITY REPORT

UNEXPECTED AND/OR INTERESTING INCIDENTS

In one group a student has previous experience in educational robotics. So in many cases he was trying to find the more “mathematical” and complicated solution to the given task. His behavior, combined with his reticent character made him take full control and marginalize the other group members.

HOW DID YOU FACILITATE THE EMERGENCE OF CRITICAL INCIDENTS?

Tutor was reminding group members, frequently, that they should talk each other and discuss the task in order to be more successful. Additionally, the experienced student was encouraged to explain and discuss his thoughts to his group partners. In some cases the tutor spent more time on the group by asking for more information or better explanation of the promoted solution.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

Students became familiar with technical vocabulary and parts. They learned to recognize the different role of robot parts (motors, sensor). The different settings they applied and the solutions they gave to each task indicates that they understood the way a robot get “smart”, in other words the way the robot can be programmed. Eventually, the discussions they had inside each group and with other groups are strong evidence their engagement with technology and STEM issues.

Figure 1. Ultrasonic sensor on board

Figure 2. Obstacle avoidance

Figure 3. Phase 3 - One solution

Figure 4. Phase 3 - Testing

Figure 5. Phase 2 - experimenting with the distance

Figure 6. The "artistic" task

Please indicate specifically what your students learned regarding STEM choosing from the concepts listed below

- Iteration
- Proportion
- Variables
- Rate of change
- Similarity
- Symmetry
- Periodicity
- Volume

IDEAS FOR EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

- The “artistic” part of the activity seemed to be very interesting. So, a more dedicated and longer in duration task with markers’ construction and painting could be more creative
- A extended task in which all robots should cooperate e.g. one robot follow another.

Robotic Insect

AUTHOR: Agni Pachouli

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Provide a short description of the activity so that it becomes clear the theme of the activity, the rationale behind its design and the final products students will construct.

Students are challenged to design/construct and program their own robotic insect using an Arduino platform, electronic components and every day affordable materials. A servo motor will generate the movement of the legs, allowing their robot to move autonomously.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

STEP 2. Domains

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select **NO** if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and **YES** if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Technology - Programming

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science
 Technology
 Business
 Engineering
 Arts
 Mathematics

(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
8	8	0	8	4	0

Societal Issues
 Life skills
 Other (please specify) Programming

(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	0	8

STEP 3. Learning outcomes

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Build the circuits of LED & Sonar. 2. Amend the given program so that obstacles are detected and led is turned on. 3. Build the circuit of Servo motor 4. Amend the given program so that the motor moves (variation of speed). 5. Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robotic insect to be autonomous and move. 6. Create the desired functionalities and characteristics of a robotic insect.
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	Design with Arduino Uno board, a mini breadboard, some electronic parts (resistances, led, sonar sensor, servo motor) and programming

	with open-source Arduino Software (IDE)
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership</p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, exchange ideas, take roles within groups.
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Critical Thinking <input type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership</p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Identify an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution
	<p>Skills to be fostered:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership</p>

STEP 4. Interaction during the activity

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, facilitate, support

STEP 5. Artifacts

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming with open-source Arduino Software (IDE)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Using the Arduino technology in order to build a moving robot which is formed as 'an insect'.

STEP 6. Who? Where? How long?

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 4 weeks (group_1) – 5 weeks (group_2)

Schedule: 2 hours per week

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	Boys and girls, 14-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - little knowledge of Arduino and electronic parts (resistances, led). Before this project students were involved in activities in order to get familiar with electronic circuits and Arduino board - Good knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts) in Scratch environment
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	29 students from Greece and 1 student from Thailand
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	All students have good English knowledge

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: in the Computer Lab during computer science and technology lessons.

Environment: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 30 (15students/group) **Tutors:** 1 **Assistants:** 0

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	mixed ability, mixed gender where possible
<i>Setting (Style of room):</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • workshops took place in a computer lab, • one Arduino Uno microcontroller, electronic parts and a desktop computer available for each group, • each group is seated in their own workbench, • all every-day affordable materials for the construction were placed on a table in the middle of the room

TECHNOLOGY

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash & Dot

mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

During the activity students are expected to engage in the following actions: design, construct, observe, program, communicate, exchange ideas, present their work in the classroom and participate in an educational social media platform (e-me).

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	I will bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions on programming documented in educational research and the students have to find out, discover the solution
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on studying robot behaviour as a result of its design and the executed program (i.e. use behaviour as feedback on programming and robot design)
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot emphasis on mathematical thinking and physical laws, the construction of the insect's legs depends on a specific geometry pattern in order for the zoomorphic robot to move

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1- INTRODUCTION & EXPERIMENTATION WITH CIRCUITS, SONAR & MOTOR

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: discussion, demonstration, group work, assembly, experimentation

Duration: 90 minutes (10 minutes demonstration, 80 minutes group work)

Summary (Description): At the beginning of the workshop, the teacher presents the overall aim, the objectives of the workshop, the training methodology and the expected training results. A brief demonstration of the electronic parts (resistance, led), sonar sensor and motor is being held. Before students start acting, groups are asked to choose a name for their team.

Teams start implementing the worksheet activities, which support their involvement equally in programming, engineering and electronics. First, they design the electronic circuit that detects obstacles with the help of the sonar sensor. Whenever the sensor detects an obstacle, a led is turned on. Furthermore, students get familiar with the servo motor, as they have to figure out how it is

connected on the Arduino board and how to program it. Students are prompt to tinker with the programming, since the initial code is provided (files sonar_ionidios_v3.ino & servo_motion_v3.ino), but modifications are needed. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results on the servo's motion.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 1, 2, 3, 4

Teaching method: Experimentation

Expected student constructions: the initial electronic circuits with led, sonar sensor and motor

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 2- CONSTRUCTING THE SKELETON OF A ROBOTIC INSECT

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 90 minutes

Summary (Description): Students get involved in constructing a robotic insect by using every day and affordable materials (paperclips, wooden sticks, rope, glue etc). No specific pattern or instructions are provided, instead students use their imagination and creativity to choose and combine the materials. During the construction process, students exchange ideas, disagree, negotiate, experiment, try different ideas, collaborate and improve their construction. At the end of the session, each team will have constructed part of a unique robotic insect.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 5, 6

Teaching method: Exploration

Expected student constructions: part of a unique robotic insect (the main skeleton)

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 3- DESIGNING ROBOTIC LEGS

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 90 minutes

Summary (Description): It's time to make the robotic insect move. Once they understand the programming part, they are challenged to find a proper position for the servo motor, as well for the

legs, in order to make a functional autonomous robotic insect. Many questions arise at this point, especially regarding the shape of the legs, the position of the robotic legs and the position of the servo motor on the already-made robotic skeleton.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 5, 6

Teaching method: Exploration

Expected student constructions: the robotic legs

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 4- MAKING THE ROBOTIC INSECT MOVE

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 90 minutes

Summary (Description): When they manage to complete the construction, students focus on programming and debugging the code in order to achieve their goal and make their robotic insect move.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 5, 6

Teaching method: Exploration

Expected student constructions: an autonomous moving robotic insect

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 5 – PRESENTING THE ROBOTIC INSECTS - FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 90 minutes

Summary (Description): In addition with the activity sheets, students after completing all the activity phases, they present their robotic insect in classroom, discuss the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step and suggest improvements. They also fill in an electronic evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:-

Teaching method: Discussion, Presentation

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Step 9 Attachments / Supporting Material

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheet with instructions for the electronic parts (leds, resistances, sonar and servo motor), initial code for modification (programming part)
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	-

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Please describe unexpected that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this moment as unexpected. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

A.

The 3rd team (group_1, team R2INO) managed to construct the most functional robotic insect, while designing a creative and mechanically advanced mechanism for autonomous movement. After interviewing this specific team, which was not the case study group, one of the students stated that he is familiar with mechanisms as he makes his own constructions at home.

The interview is located in the path ...\\Artefacts of Learning\\Photos\\group_1\\3rd_session_27-03-2018\\Video and photos, files interview_Chara.mp4 and DSC_0048_cut.mp4).

B.

The forth team (named Ploutonas) in group_1 didn't manage to cooperate and only one student actually participated in the project. The other two members were not interested and their behavior was improper, making it rather difficult for the other student to work and implement the desired activities.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier.

- A. I was impressed by the mechanism, congratulated the students and motivated other team members to explore the specific mechanism. All students agreed that this was the best robotic insect in all aspects. I encouraged all the students to think creatively to every case.
- B. I tried to engage the two students by assigning them specific small tasks but I didn't manage to motivate them. In order to help the active team member, I intervened more in their work.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Please describe interesting moments that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

The interesting moment was at the 3rd session of group 2 (case study group named "King of Norway") when a student member decided to design a second pair of robotic legs, in case the first one didn't match. So, he had an alternative solution, which in general is a good strategy.

The interview is located in the path ...\\Artefactsof Learning\\Photos\\group_2\\3rd_session_22-02-2018\\Photos and Video, file DSC_0092.mov

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier

The intervention of the student is referred to phase 3 - Designing robotic legs.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

Most students had never constructed and programmed something from scratch. As stated, it was a very interesting experience, but difficult at the same time. Most of them managed to collaborate successfully with their team members - which were assigned and not selected by them- despite the disagreements that came up. Finally, they understood the importance of combining knowledge of different fields in order to achieve a goal.

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible changes or extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

- Next time I implement the workshop, I will provide two motors to each team in order to help them improve the robot's movement.

Insects' battle

AUTHOR:

Sofia Nikitopoulou

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Provide a short description of the activity so that it becomes clear the theme of the activity, the rationale behind its design and the final products students will construct.

This workshop is designed to engage students in creating the desired functionalities and characteristics of an Arduino robotic insect. To be more explicit, the students are going to explore the usage of a mini breadboard, build all the electronic circuits on it and amend a given Arduino program, so that they would create the form of robot-insects, all of which could be autonomous and move correctly. Subsequently, all the robots are going to participate in a special race, the "Insects' battle"

and in turn they will measure the average velocity of the each robotic insect. The rationale behind the specific workshop brings students in conflict with mistaken conceptions on programming and on circuits, so that the students would discover the solution. The learning process is based on the combination of the specialties, hoping that the students are going to break the boundaries of their specialties-knowledge and move on further to the synergy.

TYPE OF ACTIVITY

Workshop Competition Research/ Paper Other:

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

Not Aligned Partially aligned Fully aligned Subject: Electronics circuits

DOMAINS

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
5	8	0	8	0	0

<input type="checkbox"/> Societal Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Life skills	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify).....
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	0	0

STEP 3. Learning outcomes

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

<i>Subject related</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create the desired functionalities and characteristics of a robotic insect. 2. Study and use a mini breadboard. 3. Build the circuits of LED, Piezo & Sonar. 4. Build the circuits of Servo motors and amend
------------------------	--

	the given Arduino program, so that the robot-insects could be autonomous and move correctly. 5. Check which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle" and measure the average velocity of the each robotic insect.
<i>Skills Learning Outcomes</i>	
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with Arduino.
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas, tips and advices.
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input type="checkbox"/> Critical Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leadership
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	make assumptions, test possible solutions and choose the best solution
	Skills to be fostered: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collaboration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Creativity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teamwork <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Critical Thinking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Problem Solving <input type="checkbox"/> Leadership

STEP 4. Interaction during the activity

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	pre-defined roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Mainly monitor and from time to time facilitator

STEP 5. Artifacts

ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Arduino programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Using the Arduino technology in order to build a

	robot which is formed as 'an insect'.
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STEP 6. Who? Where? How long?

TIME, STUDENTS & SPACE

TIME

Duration: 2 days**Schedule:** 6 hours per day

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Gender and Age:</i>	boys 15-17 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	little if any knowledge of Arduino but 3 students are experts on electronics and 4 students are experts on computer science & programming concepts.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	2 pupils are from Albania and 9 from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	underprivileged area
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Arduino programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: At a Computer Lab of the Electronic Sector of the Laboratory Center of a Vocational Technical School.**Environment:** indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 11 **Tutors:** 1 **Assistants:** 1

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	mixed specialties (Vocational School)
<i>Setting (Style of room):</i>	3 tables at the center of the class for the hands-on team work and 3 available computers for the programming of Arduino.

TECNOLOGY

Technology Used:

Lego WeDo
 Arduino
 Hedgehog
 SLurtles
 LEGO Mindstorms
 MOSS
 Robotic Dreams
 Thymio 2
 Dash & Dot

mBot
 Other

Programming Languages:

Drag/Drop
 Scratch: Open SIM
 C++
 Python
 Java
 C
 Arduino
 Other

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, communicate, create, exchange ideas & answer questions through the platform e-me.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	I will bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions on programming documented in educational research and the students have to find out, discover the solution
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	The learning process is based on the combination of the specialties, thus the hope is that the students are going to break the boundaries of their specialties-knowledge and move on further to the synergy.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to experiment on the structure of an insect’s body in order to make it moves as quick as possible (Physics).

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1-INTRODUCTION AND BULDING THE BODY OF THE ROBOTIC INSECT

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 3 hours

Summary (Description): Students are introduced to available parts, sensors and motors. Furthermore, are engaged in discussion about robotic body, so that they could create the desired functionalities and characteristics of a robotic insect.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 1.

Teaching method: Experimentation

Expected student constructions: the initial shape of a robotic insect

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 2- BUILDING THE ELECTRONIC CIRCUITS OF LED, PIESO & SONAR

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 3 hours

Summary (Description): During this phase are going to build the LED, Pieso and Sonar circuits. Students using the activity sheets are going to build all the electronics circuits. However, it is very significant for the students to explore the usage of Arduino microprocessor and breadboard before they start building the circuits.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 2,3

Teaching method: Exploration

Expected student constructions: the circuits of LED, Pieso and Sonar.

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 3- BUILDING THE ELECTRONIC CIRCUITS OF SERVO MOTORS AND AMEND THEIR PROGRAM

Type:

Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation Construction Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 3 hours

Summary (Description): Build the circuits of Servo motors and amend the given Arduino program, so that the robot-insects could be autonomous and move correctly.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 4

Teaching method: Exploration

Expected student constructions: the circuits of servo motors & an amending Arduino program

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 4- MEASURE THE VELOCITY OF THE ROBOTIC INSECT

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 2 hours

Summary (Description): The students are going to check which is the faster robotic insect during the "Insects' battle" and measure the average velocity of the each robotic insect.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: 5

Teaching method: Instruction

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

PHASE 5-FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Type:

Introductory
 Reflection
 Assessment
 Evaluation
 Exploration
 Experimentation
 Construction
 Other

Orchestration: group work

Duration: 1 hours

Summary (Description): In addition with the activity sheets, students after completing all the activity phases, they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase:-

Teaching method: Discussion

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Step 9 Attachments / Supporting Material

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

MATERIALS

<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheets with instructions for the electronic part and programming part too.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	-

POST ACTIVITY REPORT (FEEDBACK)

This section is expected to be completed right after the implementation of the activity with your students.

UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)

Please describe unexpected that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this moment as unexpected. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

The 3rd team finished their project first of all, so having free time they built a base, put their robot on it and could easily improve the construction. It was an unexpected moment because it was out of the scope of the workshop.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL UNEXPECTED MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier.

The above intervention of the 3rd team isn't referred to any phase of the workshop.

INTERESTING MOMENT(S)

Please describe interesting moments that occurred while you implemented this activity with students. Provide a short explanation why do you consider this incident as interesting. It will be nice if you can include also pictures in this section.

The interesting moment was at the second session of the workshop when a student member of the 3rd team decided to add another LED to their robot and he used his knowledge of his specialty in order to do it.

HOW DID YOU REACT DURING THE CRITICAL INTERESTING MOMENT(S)?

Describe what was happening in the classroom while the critical moment you described above emerged (including teacher interventions – group interactions).

Refer to the part of the activity plan that is connected to the critical moment (s) you described earlier

The intervention of the student is referred to phase 2- building of circuits. The teacher encouraged all the students to think creatively to every case.

EVIDENCE OF STUDENT LEARNING

Include here a short description of what your students learned during the implementation of the activity. Include also photographs of student constructions or student comments.

IDEAS FOR CHANGES/EXTENSIONS/REVISIONS OF THE INITIAL ACTIVITY PLAN

Include here a short reference (in bullets) to possible changes or extensions or revisions that could be made in the initial activity plan based on the implementation you made in the classroom.

Park the Robot

AUTHOR:

Dimitris Diamantidis

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Students firstly make their own LEGO NXT robots. They will work in groups of three. They shall built the robot, with three wheels, following specific steps. Then they have to put on an ultrasonic sensor, taking initiative in the design of the robot, without having any instructions to follow.

The next step is to make the robot ho straight ahead and then turn right. This is an introductory activity to the main challenge which is to make the robot recognize the empty space between two obstacles. Then the robot shall move between the obstacles, simulating a “parking” procedure.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

NO YES Subject: Mathematics\Proportional amounts, Circle characteristics and circumference, algorithmic thinking.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	5	0	7

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study a turn of a robot based on time, or on rotations of the wheel. Choose the best measure to achieve the goal. Program the ultrasonic sensor.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with LEGO NXT in LEGO programming environment

<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution.

TIME

Duration: e.g. 2 weeks

Schedule: e.g. 4 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	LEGO NXT – ‘a simple vehicle’
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	Manual with step-by-step instructions for building the robot.
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	Five stages.

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 12-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Not any knowledge on robotics & programming
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	All pupils are from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	public experimental school

<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants
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SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: After school activity, during the courses of the Mathematics Club – in the school PC Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 15

Tutors: 2 Assistants: 0

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Students that have worked together as a team during Math Club's activities this year – students preferences.
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in groups of three (3), around tables with a desktop and a robot available for them in each group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate – participant observer

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, collaborate, experiment with their constructions, reflect on and elaborate their artefacts, communicate, exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers do not wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on analyzing robot behavior using related measurements and experimentation in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to investigate the structure of mechanisms that use contemporary technological achievements, like auto-parking of a car, or distance-sensors.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 teaching hours

Orchestration: group work in groups of 3

Description: The groups are assembling their robots, following instructions, clearly described on an online manual. The final stage of the construction (placing the ultrasonic sensor) is totally open for the pupils to decide which way to do it. After that, we demonstrate to them which way to program the robot.

Expected student constructions: A Lego NXT simple vehicle

Expected forms of student dialogue: Arguing on which are the right parts of the robot to use and how to put the sensor on the robot.

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot on a predefined path on the floor. The path contains a turn at the end of it. Students use the robots they have just assembled.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A simple program by each group

Expected forms of student dialogue: Argumentation of possible of their program, after testing it on the floor.

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The main goal for the students is to create a new program in order to make the robot recognize obstacles. Then it should change its path, avoiding them. With teacher assistance, students recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure (loop) and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A new program using loops.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion on the way that the loops must be used, in order to make the program work

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation.

PHASE 4: GIVING “SMART” BEHAVIOR: THE USAGE OF SELECTION/SWITCH BLOCKS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A most difficult and challenging task for the students is to make the robot park automatically between two obstacles. In this case, the robot should not only avoid the obstacle, but follow a more specific track, after avoiding it. After that the robot has to stop. This makes the program even more challenging.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A more sophisticated way of using the loops.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion on the way that the loops must be used, in order to make the program work

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 5: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

Design and program robots to solve the maze problem.

AUTHOR:

Vasileios Spahos

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Provide a short description of the activity so that it becomes clear the theme of the activity, the rationale behind its design and the final products students will construct.

Design and program robots to solve the maze problem.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Project

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	6	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study the construction of a robot and the sensors that it should have in order to solve the maze problem and be able to find the solution to every maze. Also get in touch with programming structures
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in LEGO EV3 programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Students make some assumptions about how the robot will react to the environment using sensors based on the program given, design and test possible solutions, choose the best solution, trying to optimize their solution, communicate with other “makers”.

TIME

Duration: e.g. 2 weeks

Schedule: e.g. 4 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	The technology and the robot form a vehicle
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	Manual with a possible design for robot vehicle, student sheet for programming
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes with the three stages of construction

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 15-16 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	little if any knowledge of EV3 with little knowledge of programming concepts
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	22 pupils are from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants but most of students know English

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In School at the Robotics Laboratory; During project time in school.

Physical characteristics: indoors/outdoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 22

Tutors: 1

Grouping:

Grouping criteria	mixed ability, mixed gender
<i>Setting:</i>	students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group students have the ability to make some experiments on a real maze.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, find a solution to a problem, take part in a small competition.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	students are expected to investigate the structure of a vehicle and the basic parts in order to construct their robot and make it more stable and quick.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about robotic behaviors and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are

introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results. They also analyze the problem and come up with the necessary equipment that a robot should have (sensors) make a list and start constructing their robots.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions : One robotic vehicle per group

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 2: PROBLEM SOLVING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description After finishing their robots the groups are assigned to program their robots and their behavior. In order to find a way to solve the problem we use a student as a volunteer and other students try to lead him to the exit of the class by using commands. They use the Programming environment of Lego EV3, using sequential programming, loops, selection. At the same time, they test their robot and its behavior , trying to solve possible problems they face.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions :

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: CODE OPTIMIZATION AND COMPETITION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students try to find a way to optimize their program by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program and they are trying to make their robot faster in order to take part in a small competition. Also they are trying to make their robots more attractive.

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

8 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW	Educational Robotics Workshop
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
REA	Research Executive Agency
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

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